

*Exploring Small Charity Accountability in Scotland:
Perspectives from Charity Managers and Charity Trustees*

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Abstract

The research explored how small charities operating in communities across Scotland are meeting the challenges of managing their multiple accountabilities. The research set out to discover the stakeholders identified by small charities, the nature of their relationships, and the information that is disclosed or shared with stakeholders. The research also investigated the mechanisms used to discharge accountability, and the challenges of accountability for the small charity sector. The research adopted a sequential mixed-method approach utilising a first stage 'pre-interview questionnaire' and second stage qualitative interviews to meet the research objectives and answer the research questions. A sample of small charity leaders, charity managers and charity trustees, shared their perspectives and experiences of accountability in the small charity sector of Scotland. The findings show a variety of understandings of accountability in the small charity sector and a variety of perspectives and approaches to building stakeholder relationships. The findings reveal that a range of accountability mechanisms are being used to discharge small charity accountability to stakeholders, although charities have scope to consider how to make better use of these. The findings also highlight that limited resources in the sector are limiting small charities' ability to provide transparent accounts of their performance and activities. Overall, different forms and characteristics of accountability were found to exist between charities and their charity stakeholder groups. Participant accounts highlight the ongoing challenges of covid and the cost-of-living crisis for the small charity sector, with participants appreciating the urgency for improved information sharing and accountability to their stakeholders. The findings also highlight that tools and resources to support charity accountability are under-employed in the sector. The research recommends that sector support groups, funders and fund providing charities, and charity boards themselves must take a leadership role to support small charities in finding solutions to the challenge posed by their multiple accountabilities.

Keywords: Charity accountability; Multiple accountabilities, Upward accountability, Downward accountability, Accountability mechanism, Charity stakeholder, Transparency, Trust

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Author's declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is entirely my own work, and has not been submitted elsewhere for purposes of DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award. *G. McPake*

Abbreviations

CIC	Community Interest Companies
CSO	Civil Society Organisations
LFA	Logical Framework Analysis
NCVO	National Council for Voluntary Organisations
NFP	Not for Profit(organisation)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPM	New Public Management
OM	Outcomes Measurement
OSCR	Office of the Scottish Charity Regulator
PMS	Performance Management Systems
RACI	Responsible, Accountable, Consulted Informed
R & P	Receipts & Payments
SCIO	Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation
SCVO	Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations
SEO	Social Enterprise Organisations
SORP	Statements of Recommended Practice
SROI	Social Return on Investment
TAR	Trustees Annual Report
TSO	Third Sector organisation
VA	Voluntary Association

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter discusses the issue of trust in the charity sector and the part that accountability plays in enhancing trust in the sector. This chapter also describes the nature of the real-world research problem, the purpose and scope of the research and where the research is situated i.e., the small charitable sector in Scotland. This chapter also briefly outlines the structure of the thesis, the research objectives and questions, and the methodology.

1.1 Introduction to charity accountability

In a recent report that investigated factors associated with public trust in the charity sector, the Charity Commission suggested that “transparency is not enough: charities need to demonstrate authenticity to rebuild trust” (Charity Commission, 2018). Several key components of trust building can be identified from the collection of studies substantiating the Commission’s report including transparency about where money goes, efficiency in the use of charity resources, an ability to demonstrate positive impact, and effective charity management and governance (Bryce, 2016 as cited in Hyndman and McConville, 2018a; Populus 2016; Hind 2017; McConville, 2017). These issues of public concern are obviously not unique to England and Wales, the regulatory domain of the Charity Commission, but are UK-wide and indeed go beyond the UK. The Charity Commission suggests that increased rules and regulation may not be the solution to this problem, but rather that a shift in culture and behaviours towards meeting public expectations could halt this inexorable erosion of public trust in charities.

A report commissioned by the Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) entitled ‘The public view: trust, confidence and support of charities in Scotland’ (SCVO, 2018) paints a more positive picture of trust and confidence in Scotland yet points out that there are warning signs and a need to guard against complacency. Despite some encouraging survey responses (e.g., 73% agreed charities are trustworthy and act in the public interest and 77% believed that

they had a key role in communities), the research revealed some worrying trends. Trust scores in Scotland continued to outperform UK charity trust scores but the gap is narrowing as the Scottish performance dropped over the years 2015 to 2017 (57% of respondents gave charities trust scores of 6/10 and above in 2017 compared to 67% in 2015). The report highlights the high proportion of respondents stating that their trust in charities decreased (32%) that negative media stories contribute to loss of trust (38%) and personal experience was a contributory factor (21%). However, the report also found that personal connections had a significant positive impact on trust. When asked to score charities whose services they had used- trust scores in 2017 increased from a mean of 5.9/10 in 2015 to 7.51/10. The report concludes that good governance, transparency, and communication are necessary to address the erosion of trust in the sector caused by negative first-hand experiences and media coverage.

In view of these findings, it is logical to investigate whether small charities are demonstrating a willingness to disclose several types of information to its local community and the public i.e., to what extent there is a practice of transparent information sharing. In addition, it is worth exploring the variety of format and types of account or disclosure that would be most effective in “demonstrating authenticity” regards their operations, management, and performance in meeting their social mission (Hyndman and McConville, 2016). Are charities considering the needs of its stakeholders and reaching out with relevant information to these varied groups as some academics (Prakash & Gugerty, 2010) recommend? Beyond the need for wider public scrutiny, several internal and external charity stakeholder groups such as funders, charity members or volunteers, beneficiaries and local government agencies would desire, if not demand, this information. Transparency for the sector suggests going beyond minimum disclosures to provide a variety of accessible, useful, and understandable information to stakeholders (O’Neill, 2006). The first steps in developing effective information sharing practices would logically begin with stakeholder identification, which in turn leads to

stakeholder prioritisation (stakeholder salience), and then towards development of stakeholder engagement strategies. Simultaneously, a charity can build a picture of their accountability, identify those to whom they should or must discharge their accountability, and discover those groups that are making demands for charity accountability (Connolly & Hyndman, 2013a).

The research seeks to explore accountability specifically within small charitable organisations located in Scotland. For this study, the small charitable sector includes organisations who have registered and have charitable status confirmed by the charity regulator OSCR. Charitable companies, which are incorporated, registered with Companies House and subject to accruals-based accounting standards, are excluded from the study. Study of companies subject to company law and the filing requirements of Company House are out with the scope of this research. In addition, ‘hybrid’ organisations such as social enterprise organisations (SEOs) or community interest companies (CICs) are out with the scope of this study. The charitable sector is regulated by the Office of the Scottish Charity Regulator (OSCR) with some uniquely Scottish arrangements due to devolved charity law in the UK and a Scottish charity may also seek status as a ‘Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation’ (SCIO). SCIOs are a relatively new legal form of charity, with some benefits of incorporation such as limited liability, but without other company obligations such as accruals reporting and filing with Companies House and thus, they are within the scope of this study. In summary, the small organisations of interest are registered charities (including SCIOs) all operating below a turnover threshold of £250,000. The turnover threshold offers these organisations a choice of disclosure between: ‘Statements of Recommended Practice (SORP) Accrual Accounting’ or ‘Receipts & Payments (R&P)’ cash-based accounting. The definition of ‘small’ can be varied, for example the ‘National Council for Voluntary Organisations’ (NCVO) defines “small” as having income between £10,000 to £100,000 and micro as having income less than £10,000. The SCVO defines small charities as those with income less than £25,000 and ‘The Small Charities Coalition’ defines

small as those with income less than £1,000,000. The OSCR threshold of £250,000 for accounting approach is also important. Combining these definitions for the purposes of this study provides a useful classification and definition of “small” organisation size:

Table 1: Definition of small charities

Income	Definition
Less than £10,000	Micro
£10,000 to £100,000	Very small
£100,000 to £250,000	Small
> £250,000	Organisations out with scope of this study.

Source: Author, based on OSCR, NCVO and SCVO

A search of OSCR’s charity register lists 21,205 active charities with income between £0 and £250,000 (OSCR, 26/05/2023). As well as being defined by size, OSCR provides further categorisation of charities by purpose, activities, beneficiaries, and constitutional form. This provides an understanding of the population of charities relevant to this study. Charity purpose covers a range of areas including for example, ‘relief of poverty’, ‘advancement of education’, ‘advancement of religion’, ‘advancement of health’, ‘relief of those in need by reason of age, ill health, disability, financial hardship or other disadvantage’. Charity activities are defined for example as ‘making grants, donations, or gifts’ or ‘carries out activities or services itself’. Beneficiaries for example are defined as ‘children or young people’, ‘older people’, ‘benefit of the community’, ‘people with disabilities or health problems’. Constitutional form for example includes ‘Trust’, ‘Unincorporated association’, ‘SCIO (Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation)’. The categorisations of charities reveal the complexity of the charitable sector.

In Scotland, the form of charity R&P accounts are comprehensively prescribed by structure, content, and further categories and details required by OSCR. Larger charities with turnover

exceeding the £250,000 threshold and subject to the SORP regime are out with the scope of this study. The SORP is not the focus of this research, although the researcher acknowledges that many studies have investigated accounting and accountability improvements, enhancement of stakeholder engagement and public benefit linked to SORP (Hyndman & McMahon, 2011; Connolly et al, 2013).

The minimum legally required disclosure for those organisations granted charitable status and registered with charity regulator, OSCR is the Trustees Annual Report (TAR) or the published annual accounts. However, voluntary disclosure of information may be of particular importance to the small charity sector. In fact, several academics suggest that such freely shared information can be valued and trusted more than that which is demanded (Seal & Vincent-Jones, 1997; ter Bogt & Tillema, 2016). One major aspect of the research aims to examine the accountability mechanism choices of these small organisations that are used to communicate charity information, be transparent, and discharge accountability to stakeholders.

The research aims to build on that conducted by Hyndman and McConville (2018a) in ‘Trust and accountability in UK charities: Exploring the virtuous circle’. Also, the research here will draw upon on the transparency framework developed by Hyndman and McConville (2018b) in ‘Making charity effectiveness transparent: Building a stakeholder-focussed framework of reporting’. The transparency framework emphasised the need for quality of disclosure, particularly in communication of charity impact and effectiveness. Additional papers influencing and underpinning the study also include those contributions of Ebrahim (2003), a seminal paper in area of “accountability mechanisms” for non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and Smith and Miller (2018), who explored ‘Accountability in the Scottish charitable context’ for a single small Scottish charity. Smith and Miller offered a Balanced Scorecard approach as a solution for capturing and disseminating information to charity stakeholder groups. NGO is an umbrella term capturing a variety of organisations, including charities, that

operate independently from government, are usually non-profit, and pursue social causes. Finally, Cordery and Sim (2018), offer important guidance by providing useful classifications of charities and a general framework for researching accountability in the sector by identifying ‘for whom’, ‘for what and why’ and ‘how’ accountability is discharged.

This study responds to the calls for further exploration of accountability, transparency, trust, and stakeholder relationships in different charitable sector contexts (Hyndman & McConville, 2018a; Cordery and Sim, 2018). The contribution of the present research is to combine the research frameworks to investigate in-depth the issues around stakeholder engagement through information sharing, and challenges of these multiple accountabilities for small charitable organisations operating at local community levels across Scotland. Small, registered charities may (or may not) address accountability in a robust fashion given their regulatory requirements. Guidelines, advice, and standards are more visible and prevalent for larger charities or NGOs, however, special interest or support organisations such as the ‘Small Charities Coalition’, the NCVO, SCVO and OSCR itself offer guidance for the sector. Part of the study queries the level of awareness and use of these types of resources and how these guidelines are or could be used in practice. Hyndman and McConville (2018a) also looked for evidence that one of the underlying motivations driving charity accountability, information sharing, and stakeholder engagement was trust building. Trust would seem to be key to charity sustainability i.e., sustainable finance, volunteer supply and reputation in the community.

The personal inspiration and motivation for the study comes from my previous consultancy work undertaken for a Scottish Third Sector Interface (TSI). TSIs operate in regions across Scotland and their aim is to offer guidance and support to local community-based non-profit, voluntary, social, and charitable organisations. I delivered short courses in accounting and financial management to these organisations and found there to be a variety of understandings and approaches to accounting and accountability to stakeholders. Small, registered charities

were of particular interest since they had the added dimension of accountability to the charity regulator, OSCR. Conversations with organisation representatives, usually treasurers, charity committee and board members or those that identified themselves as managers, inevitably turned to discussion of some of their accountability challenges- these conversations were fascinating. I reasoned that this area warranted in-depth exploration through the formal and rigorous process of doctoral research.

1.2 Research aim, objectives, and questions

Research Aim

The aim of the research is to explore the characteristics, features, and issues and challenges of accountability in the small charitable sector of Scotland. This aim will be explored through the perspective of those in leadership positions within these organisations i.e., charity managers and charity trustees.

Research Objectives

The research has the following objectives:

- To investigate perceptions and attitudes of accountability for small charities. (1)
- To determine the stakeholder groups identified and prioritised by small charities. (2)
- To examine the types, quantity, and quality of information that these small organisations are producing and sharing in their attempts to be transparent (3)
- To critically analyse the accountability mechanisms being utilised by small charities to meet stakeholder information needs. (4)
- To explore whether there are differences in accountability practices and perceptions between charity types. (5)

Although it is not an explicit research objective, it is expected that current issues and challenges pertaining to Covid recovery and the ongoing cost of living crisis, will arise within the interview process and be explored as part of this research.

Research Questions

The research will attempt to answer the following research questions:

RQ 1 What are the accountability perceptions and attitudes of people in leadership positions in small charities?

RQ 2 What stakeholder groups are prioritised by small charities and what is the nature of their stakeholder relationships?

RQ 3 What types, quantity, and quality of information are produced and shared by small charities in their attempts to be transparent?

RQ 4 What are the perceptions and behaviours around use of accountability mechanisms in the small charity sector?

RQ 5 What effect does charity type have on accountability perceptions and practices in the small charity sector?

1.3 Research contribution, approach, and structure

Research contribution

The study primarily seeks to enhance understanding of the accountability landscape for small charities operating in Scotland at national and local community levels. The research adds to the existing literature and academic debate surrounding accountability and transparency of (mostly larger) charities so attempt to fill a gap in the research specifically for small or micro-organisations. The benefit or contribution of the research is to provide a deeper understanding of accountability and stakeholder information management for the small charitable

organisation sector. The findings provide recommendations for the supervision, support, and improvement of small charities.

Outline of the approach to research and structure of the thesis

The research philosophy of the study is pragmatic. A pragmatic approach to data collection and analysis is appropriate given the real-world organisational level research that will be undertaken by the researcher. It is also envisaged that output from the research could have meaningful organisational impact for the small charitable sector.

The research adopts a mixed-method approach to meet the research objectives and find reliable answers to the research questions. The research begins with a general gauge of participant perspectives as measured using a ‘pre-interview questionnaire’; followed by a more in-depth exploration of the key issues utilising interviews. The ‘pre-interview questionnaire’ was used to collect basic preliminary data from participants and to prepare them for the interview stage of research. This has been described as a sequential (quant, QUAL) mixed-method research design, with focus on the rigorous second stage qualitative interviews. This allows for some triangulation, and despite the philosophical challenges, provides a comprehensive exploration of the research issue. As per Hyndman and McConville (2018), a qualitative approach utilising interviews or focus groups to collect primary data was deemed to be appropriate by the researcher and consistent with other research in this area. The research design and strategy required access to a sample group of small charity leaders i.e., charity managers, charity committee members, and charity trustees. Semi-structured interviews were employed, allowing for directed conversation around the issues of stakeholders, accountability, transparency, and mechanisms for dissemination of charity information. As well as looking for specific information regards stakeholder engagement, information sharing practices i.e., accountability mechanisms, the interviews aimed to tease out the underlying motivations and perceptions of

transparency and accountability. The research drew upon sector contacts and gatekeepers within organisations such as Third Sector Interfaces (TSIs), Inspire Scotland, and the SCVO for feedback on the research instruments and questions, and to access small charity participants. Qualitative data analysis was conducted using three stages of bottom up and inductive thematic analysis i.e., descriptive summary and coding of data (1), interpretive coding of data (2), and determination of over-arching themes (3). Analyses sought to determine the following: key stakeholders, mechanisms for information sharing, levels of transparency, perceptions and attitudes of accountability and transparency, motivations, and constraints. Overall, the approach was abductive in nature given that the research was guided by existing theory and empirical findings from the literature but remained open to new interpretations and adaptations.

The remainder of the thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides a critical literature review of the academic literature pertaining to charity accountability. The review explores important theoretical and empirical findings to inform the direction of the subsequent research and closes with a theoretical framework to conceptualise how accountability is likely constructed and enacted in the small charity sector. Chapter 3 discusses the methodology and research approach adopted for the study of small charity accountability. The chapter addresses research philosophy and approach, research design and strategy, mixed method approaches to research, and sampling and data analysis. Chapter 4 presents the data and findings pertaining to the first stage ‘pre-interview questionnaire’, explains the relevance of the findings and how they inform the second stage of the research process. Chapter 5 presents the data and findings from thematic analysis of the interview data relevant to the over-arching themes of ‘Perceptions of accountability’ and ‘Building stakeholder accountability relationships’ in the small charity sector. Chapter 6 offers an in-depth discussion of the research findings in the context of the previous findings and arguments from relevant academic literature. The evidence from the research is critically compared to the assertions and conclusions found in the literature review.

Chapter 7 closes the thesis with conclusions on the research findings and the research process that was undertaken. The chapter considers the research contribution, provides in-depth reflections and recommendations based on the research evidence, and offers closing thoughts on potential for further research in small charity accountability.

Chapter structure is as follows:

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The purpose of the critical literature review is to explore the necessary background, issues, and themes relevant to the study and to critically discuss previous research findings around charity accountability. The literature review aims to paint a picture of the accountability landscape in which the organisations of interest operate. The literature review also offers critical discussion of the academic arguments and debate around accountability of the sector. To this end the literature review is used to identify gaps in the research literature worthy of further enquiry.

2.1 Background to the study and the UK/Scottish context

This section will help to further contextualise the study by identifying the economic and regulatory environment in which the organisations under study operate.

The role of the charity sector is to enhance the provision of public services e.g., linked to health, education, and social welfare, where gaps exist in government or private sector provision. In most countries, charitable organisations enjoy tax benefits and lighter legal and regulatory demands in recognition for their public benefit to society. At the beginning of 2018, there were around 200,000 charities registered in the UK generating an estimated turnover of £80 billion. There exist a few large and very well-known charities such as Oxfam and Cancer Research UK, but a very large number of very small charities permeate local communities and UK society. Small charities, voluntary organisations, and social enterprises (in Scotland ‘small’ can be assumed to be those with an annual income no greater than £250,00, as per reporting threshold laid out by OSCR) make a considerable contribution to the Scottish economy and social welfare. In Scotland, OSCR has power to grant charitable status, it monitors compliance with aspects of Scottish Law, maintains a public register and administers the Annual Return.

Historically, this sector received little in the way of academic attention. Much of this can be explained by a lack of legislation, accounting and audit practice and the obvious focus on larger more visible charities. The Charities Acts of 1992 and 1993 made attempt at resolving the issue of weak and non-standardised accounting practices, but the voluntary nature of SORP meant that practice in the sector remained inconsistent (Connolly and Hyndman, 2000, 2001, 2004). In more recent times, however, the Government has taken a more pro-active role in guiding the disclosure requirements for the sector, especially given the increased role of charities in delivering public services. Mandatory reporting has in many instances replaced the freedoms of voluntary disclosures through SORP and there is increased oversight and scrutiny from charity regulatory bodies. OSCR was established in 2006 and so charity regulation in its current form is relatively new in Scotland. There remain around 25,000 registered charities on the OSCR register (26/05/23), with new organisations roughly replacing redundant ones in equal number.

Currently, around 55% of charities on the register can be described as micro-charities, with annual turnover of less than £25,000. Traditional fundraising methods remain important for the sector, but charities more often engage in commercial activities such as trading to generate surplus funds. This is especially true for larger charities with group structures. However, this also impacts small satellite/local subsidiary organisations, which will be subject to more complex governance and financial arrangements. OSCR became responsible for implementation and oversight of the ‘Charities Accounts (Scotland) Regulations 2006’ in 2006 and embarked on a series of initiatives to improve the understanding of accounting responsibilities in the sector and ultimately, the quality of charity accounts submissions (Anderson, 2017). A substantial part of this was guidance around ‘Receipts and Payments’ for qualifying small charities. OSCR moved from offering simple feedback to outright rejection of poor-quality submissions in 2009 and notes considerable progress since this time.

In 2014, OSCR sought further improvement through their engagement with a range of stakeholders across the charity sector. The result of these consultations generated several changes implemented in 2016: structure and content of the annual return, publishing of charity accounts, and risk identification through reporting of “notifiable events”.

Hyndman and McKillop (2018) identify several challenges facing UK charities both small and large. Firstly, the shift in the economic landscape due to the fall-out from the global financial crisis greatly impacted the UK charity sector. A lengthy period of austerity has been accompanied by squeezed sources of charity finance, both from the government and the public. This is compounded by increased demand for charity services in these austere times. In addition, recent high-profile scandals that have eroded trust in the charity sector have led to demands for increased transparency. Secondly, Hyndman and McKillop suggest that New Public Management (NPM) ideas including Performance Management Systems (PMS) have permeated the charity sector. These philosophies aim to transfer private-sector business techniques and practices into the not-for-profit sector, such as corporate style marketing and fundraising, corporate financial accounting, and management accounting frameworks. Problems arise where these practices are incompatible with non-financial returns and ethical mission focus of the charity sector. This pressure is, understandably, mostly felt in medium to large charities. Those charities manage significant financial resources and are subject to closer scrutiny and control from funders and regulators. However, even within the smaller charitable sector, increased disclosure of financial and especially performance information (outputs, outcomes, impact) is being recommended by sector support groups. There are numerous issues in designing and implementing effective performance measurement and management tools for charities e.g., setting complex social objectives, striking balance between financial and non-financial measures, measuring performance in long-term, measuring quality, and managing

stakeholder needs. Fundamentally, charities must seek to understand the concept of accountability and what this means to them in their charitable context.

Accountability has wide meaning, both conceptually and in practice, but simply speaking can be viewed as a focus on the information needs of stakeholders (Gibelman and Gelman, 2001). The charity-stakeholder accountability relationship involves both the giving of an account and the holding to account. Charity stakeholders are numerous and as per stakeholder theory are described as those who are affected by or affect the organisation (Freeman, 1984). It follows then that in meeting accountability challenges, charities must identify and prioritise their various stakeholder relationships and related information disclosures. Hyndman and McKillop suggest that there are links between accountability, stakeholders and trust that are worthy of further exploration (Hyndman & McKillop, 2018). The ultimate motivation of the accountability agenda should be the building of public trust in the charity sector, enhancement of charity impact, and a healthier more sustainable sector. In meeting the various challenges, Hyndman and McKillop point to the potential benefits of appropriate sector responses such as increased legitimacy and trust, improvements in management and effectiveness; versus the consequences of inappropriate responses such as loss of focus on social mission, and further erosion of trust.

A key area to explore in the small charitable sector is the choice these organisations have between accrual accounting and simplified cash-based accounting. The question of whether simplified cash-based systems are robust and valid is an important one. Alsop and Morgan (2021) examined the drivers of choice between cash based and accruals-based accounting of smaller charities in Scotland. The sample included 90 of those registered charities in the income range of £100,000 to £250,000. The research found that 39% of charities under the study adopted R&P. Several potential drivers such as legal form, income level, funding source, charity type and auditor versus independent examiner role were explored in the quantitative

stage of the research. Overall, the study found only weak correlations for these potential drivers e.g., some tendency for the larger income charities to adopt accruals-based accounting. The interviews revealed that although some established charities were moving towards R&P for the practical matter of simpler preparation, those choosing to keep accruals were doing so because they wished to avoid what was perceived as unnecessary change. There was also some feeling that accruals accounting was more comprehensive. There was some bias towards more recently established charities, with 60% of these adopting the R&P approach. For the charities under study, it was found that charities commissioned by the public sector were more likely to adopt accruals accounting; whereas community based and financed charities were equally likely to adopt accruals or R&P. The researchers draw attention to the work of Morgan (2008) and Cordery and Sim (2014) as explanations i.e., large funder preference for accruals accounting and resource dependency theory respectively; the demand for upward accountability is influencing accounting choice here.

Overall, the study's findings supported the idea that (in Scotland at least) R&P accounting is a legitimate and effective financial reporting method. The researchers suggest that there is merit in both approaches, and regardless of choice, small charities in Scotland are striving to manage themselves professionally, meet their responsibilities and demonstrate their legitimacy. Respondents cited communication and discharging accountability to stakeholders as a major driver of accounting choice, perhaps surprisingly, greatly superseding the cost implications. In addition, "there was agreement that information presented to the trustees and wider membership should be simple to understand and relevant for managing the charity" (p. 10) pointing to both accessibility criteria and a need for reporting processes to enhance the charity itself. In conclusion, the paper supports the current regulatory arrangements for small charities in Scotland. OSCRs robust approach to cash-based accounting is sufficient in discharging small charity accountability to a wide range of stakeholders. The findings give weight to the idea that

small charities can use R&P accounts as the basis for discharging (financial) accountability, although additional mechanisms would seem to be required to address multiple stakeholder accountabilities.

2.2 Discussion of relevant theory

This section discusses the theories that are relevant to and within the scope of the study. Stakeholder theory is a fundamental theory for studies of accountability since stakeholder relationships are required to discharge accountability. Likewise, legitimacy theory offers an important lens through which to understand the motivations and incentives of accountability.

In addition, agency theory and stewardship theory are important theoretical lenses for viewing principal-agent relationships relevant to the stakeholder accountability dynamic. These theories are not the focus of the study but provide the theoretical foundations upon which accountability theory stands. Theories of accountability are the primary focus of this study, which are explored in detail within subsequent literature review sections.

Stakeholder theory

Freeman (1984) provides a broad definition of stakeholders as being those individuals or groups that either affect or are affected by an organisation's achievements. Likewise, Lewis (2004) suggests that a stakeholder is any person or group who may stake a claim on an organisation's resources or is impacted by organisational activity. Furthermore, Savage et al. (1991) recognises stakeholder management as a need to manage a variety of internal and external participating and influencing actors. Roberts (1991) suggests that an organisation must demonstrate its values and worth to a wide variety of stakeholders in order that they help facilitate its survival and success. Building stakeholder relationships and trust legitimises an

organisation and its activities in the eyes of stakeholders and wider society. Mitchell et al. (1997) further considers stakeholder prioritisation or salience by reference to stakeholder attributes of: power, legitimacy, and urgency. Powerful stakeholders have means of imposing their will on an entity; legitimate stakeholders have rights, moral claims, or expectations; and urgent stakeholders call for immediate attention and exert pressure on an entity. This produces a stakeholder typology with seven types of stakeholders when attributes are mapped with 'definitive' stakeholders having all three attributes. In addition, attribute combinations for stakeholders can be dynamic, changing over time and in response to events. Those with most power, legitimacy and urgency are likely to be prioritised by an organisation. As a natural continuation, stakeholder analysis strategies such as the 'power/interest' matrix, have emerged in order that an organisation can identify stakeholders, determine interests, and ascertain their importance and power. Cordery and Baskerville (2005) suggest that less powerful groups such as beneficiaries, whilst legitimate and often urgent, are never definitive stakeholders, since they wield no power.

Whilst acknowledging the complexity and diversity of the charitable sector, Cordery and Baskerville (2010) provide an understanding of the likely stakeholder attributes and accountability relationships in the sector. Firstly, they identify that government regulators and government contractors have significant power through statute and contracts, and legitimacy through legal means. Regulators needs or demands are unlikely to be urgent, but government contracts are urgent since there are possible sanctions on charity funding. These accountability relationships are legal and contractual as opposed to communal i.e., a moral dimension with shared values. Secondly, significant donors and sponsors certainly have legitimacy through their donations, however, they may only have power and urgency to the extent that they can influence or coerce management through board representation. Donors and sponsors are likely to have a communal accountability relationship with charities, although contractual

relationships are also possible. Finally, the donating public and charity beneficiaries are unlikely to have any true power or urgency yet are certainly legitimised through their donations and their connection with the charity mission respectively. The accountability relationships here are characterised by their moral dimension and shared values and are unlikely to be contractual in nature. Taylor and Taylor (2014) suggest that as stakeholder attributes of power, legitimacy, and urgency increase, then so too does management focus and attention towards a stakeholder's needs and demands. Certainly, the donating public and charity beneficiaries may be in the most precarious of positions in terms of how charities choose to direct their resources and attention towards an accountability for aligned objectives. However, normative approaches to managing the interests of charity stakeholders are well established in the academic literature, which suggest that charities will seek to satisfy all legitimate stakeholder groups, not just those with power (Miles, 2017).

In the non-profit, charity or voluntary sector the Charity Commission (2004) draws attention to the importance of stakeholders by highlighting the need for good relationships with stakeholders, and the need to meet their information needs. Hyndman and McDonnell (2009) employed stakeholder analysis to show that there is indeed wider stakeholder influence in the non-profit sector beyond the primacy of shareholder influence in the for-profit sector.

Agency theory and Stewardship theory

Accountability can be understood by examining stakeholder relationships in more detail. Agency theory and stewardship theory can be utilised to shed light on the role, duties, responsibilities and indeed motivations and behaviours of different actors i.e., contractual relationships.

Jensen and Meckling (1976) argue that it is perfectly reasonable to expect that agents, with their own personal agendas and objectives, will not always act in the best interests of principals.

This is known as the agency problem. To control, direct and constrain agent activities then agency costs are incurred. Principals can counter agency problems with incentives and monitoring activities that help to align interests towards common purpose and goals. Lehman (2007) and Loft et al. (2006) suggest that information asymmetries between principal-funders and agent-non-profit managers may permit managers to drift away from their organisational objectives and mission. Stewardship theory offers an alternative theoretical foundation to agency theory for understanding non-profit governance and principal-agent stakeholder relationships. The need for accountability of charities, their trustees and members when examined from the perspective of stewardship theory questions the need for extensive external charity accountability. Stewardship theory suggests goal congruence, collaboration, and trust rather than goal conflict and distrust between principals and agents. Governance mechanisms empower managers, employees, and volunteers in a stewardship model rather than seek to control and monitor its actors through an agency theory lens. In stark contrast to agency theory, stewardship theory assumes that agents closely identify with organisations and their missions and have high personal utility in contributing to organisational success. Taking this further, other research suggests that motivations can be intrinsic and collectivist in nature i.e., a charitable activity in and of itself brings personal reward, especially if it is to the benefit of all (Sundaramurthy and Lewis, 2003).

Both theories are not necessarily mutually exclusive since both might be used to explain principal-agent or stakeholder relationships in non-profit organisations, or alternatively stewardship theory may be viewed as a complementary theory to agency theory. Puyvelde et al. (2012) utilise a stakeholder approach to identify principal-agent relationships and suggest that both stewardship and agency theories can be applicable in understanding the various dynamics. Puyvelde's (2012) map is taken to be a useful framework for this research, capturing stakeholders and potential principal-agent relationships, agency, or stewardship, for the sector:

Figure 1: Principal-Agent relationships in the charitable sector

The principal-to-agent relationship is indicated by direction of the arrows

Source: Puyvelde et al. (2012) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Please contact the author for further information.

The suggestion is that a principal-agent theory of non-profits should consider both the potential for goal conflict, agency theory, and situations where agents have aligned or partially aligned interests i.e., a stewardship view. Donors become principals and charitable organisations become their agents when decision making around the allocation of funds is ceded to the charity. Agency theory suggests that financial reports and other information disclosures are therefore required of the organisation to ameliorate the agency problem; this is termed a bonding cost (Jegers, 2008). Alternatively, Kelly (2001) as cited in Pressgrove et al. (2015), suggests that a non-profit organisation can employ stewardship strategies with their donors since their objectives are fundamentally aligned. These strategies build donor-organisation relationships incorporating four themes: relationship nurturing, reciprocity, responsibility, and reporting.

Beneficiaries can be viewed as principals and charities as their agents, albeit in a non-profit distributing context. Anheier (2005) suggests that there is less incentive for opportunistic behaviour on the part of the agent; a view that is contested by Cordery and Baskerville (2011) and Desai and Yetman (2015), who recognise that information asymmetries between a charity and its funders present these opportunities for self-serving behaviours. In addition, beneficiaries can further reduce the agency problem with direct involvement in setting organisational objectives through board membership. Members can also be viewed as principals and have a special relationship with non-profit organisations given their role as both funder and beneficiary. Chen (2004) acknowledges the complexity of this relationship by identifying a range of member incentives and organisational inducements. Four incentive types are recognised: purposive incentives (belief in mission) material incentives (gain tangible rewards), solidarity incentives (gain social ties), and informative incentives (gain knowledge and information). This points to the relevance of both stewardship theory and agency theory in examining relationship of charities with its members.

Principal-agent relationships also exist between organisation boards (principals) and managers (agents). In non-profit scenarios, and certainly where there is little or no managerial financial remuneration, intrinsic motivations are more relevant than extrinsic motivations (Frey and Jegen, 2001). The motivation of managers and indeed all agents can be understood by examining their utility from combination of personal goals, organisational goals, and beneficiary goals; consistent with agency theory, an internal stewardship, and an external stewardship respectively (Caers et al., 2009). Likewise, employees in the non-profit sector receive relatively small financial remuneration compared to the for-profit sector and in this sense make a labour donation to their employer, suggesting a weighting towards stewardship theory of principal-agent relationship. Of more relevance to the small charity and voluntary sector is the interaction between managers and volunteers; agency problems exist where the

personal goals of volunteers are at odds with the goals of the organisation and its managers. In these circumstances managers must find ways to incentivise and motivate volunteers towards a common goal, as well as creating the conditions that will attract and maintain volunteer supply (Handy et al., 2000).

The theoretical stance for this research assumes that stakeholder theory, agency theory and stewardship theory may all be relevant to understanding the challenges of multiple accountabilities to multiple stakeholders in the small charity sector.

2.3 Accountability in the charity sector

This section explores various arguments, issues, and findings from the research literature around accountability for non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and charities. The sections discuss the main theme of accountability, transparency, and trust; issues around accountability to different stakeholder groups; different characteristics and forms of accountability identified from the literature; and the ways in which charities and voluntary organisations have been categorised in studies of accountability.

2.3.1 Accountability, transparency, and trust in the charity sector

There is much disagreement and uncertainty over the actual definition of accountability, which only compounds the problems of understanding what it means to be accountable in the charity sector. Several academics have wrestled with this issue in the wider sense, noting that accountability is only loosely defined and appears ambiguous in nature (Connolly and Hyndman, 2004; Roberts, 2009). Gray et al. (2006) found that there was a dearth of academic literature at the time that specifically addressed the issue of accountability in the NGO or non-profit sector. Furthermore, there are fundamental ethical and moral standards assumed of

charitable or voluntary organisations. Across several sectors such as health, education, social welfare, the charitable sector advocates for human rights, environmental protection, social justice, and fairness - these causes are underpinned by notions of honesty, transparency, and integrity. Dhanani and Connolly (2012) suggest that in this sense a charity would be perceived as contradictory if these features were not integrated in their own organisational operations, activities, governance, and disclosures. Contradictions do exist, for example Sinclair et al (2010) found that indeed some charities engaged in practices to circumvent information disclosures such as seeking company status to withhold sensitive company information or withdrawing accountability on religious grounds.

Several articles point to the difficulties in defining accountability, but most suggest that it involves both “the giving of an account and the holding to account” (Stewart, 1984). Accountability mechanisms can promote trust but may also be the only solution where trust is absent or difficult to establish. Academic work also suggests that trust is essential to the non-profit sector where organisational goals and outputs may be less than clear and difficult to measure. A charity must not only demonstrate appropriate charitable behaviour, legal and regulatory compliance, but must convince society of its effectiveness in achieving charity purpose and mission (Anheier, 2005). Anheier goes on to suggest that “social accountability” instruments such as social reports are as essential to this sector as financial reporting standards are to the for-profit sector. Accountability for the charitable sector is multi-faceted since charity reporting must go beyond communication of financial performance (Keating and Frumkin, 2003). Relationships with stakeholders are important, as are governance and management, and appropriate measures of performance towards the social mission (Ebrahim, 2010). The giving of information can build trust and in the act of being transparent i.e., freely giving accessible and useful information without holding to account, trust can be re-enforced. However, there is

scope for over-enthusiastic levels of transparency, where this information can be taken as ‘tick-box’ or merely providing quantity over quality.

Demand for increased transparency and accountability in the not-for-profit sector is not new. Negative publicity and the resultant threats to the legitimacy of the not-for-profit sector can seriously undermine ability to raise funds and carry out charitable activities (Hyndman and McMahon, 2011). It has been suggested that there could be more scope within the charitable sector for fraud, misappropriation of funds, careless and accidental errors, often due to poor practices and a lack of expertise (Smith and Miller, 2018). Gray et al (2006) suggests that the charitable sector is, rather unfairly, being placed under undue pressure to legitimise itself. Indeed, some researchers have commented that the charitable or NGO sector must be held to higher standards of transparency and accountability than the corporate sector. Suspicion and mistrust arise since the not-for-profit sector is a complex network of organisations that vary by type, size, operations, mission, and objectives (Cordery and Baskerville, 2011; O’Dwyer, 2005).

Hansmann (2003) argues that to understand the charitable sector, it is essential to understand the fundamental concept of trust. Furthermore, Hyndman, Liguori and McKillop (2020) argue that trust is critical to the sustainability of the charitable sector and that charities must work hard to protect and build perceptions of their own trustworthiness to survive. Both Das and Teng (2001) and Bourassa and Stang (2016) point to the risk and fragility of organisation stakeholder relationships, where positive expectations of fairness, reliability, ethics, and competence are viewed as a state of trust. Trust can take various forms in the charitable sector. Goodwill trust, affective trust, and relational trust are similar notions of trust based upon perceptions or pre-conceptions of good faith and integrity- often borne out of previous positive interactions (Rousseau, 1998, Svensson, 2001; Columbo, 2010). Alternatively, a contractual, calculative, or cognitive trust requires an organisation (charity) to provide convincing

information regards its plans and its assessment of its chances of success. Going further, a credibility-based trust for the sector is recognised as being a belief that a charity will use its funds in an appropriate and efficient manner; and a competence-based trust implies that an organisation has the technical capability of delivering on its promised outputs and outcomes (Luhmann, 2000). Wider consideration of the concept of trust from political theory literature points to the distinctions between distrust, and mistrust. Citrin and Stoker (2018) for example suggest that mistrust reflects a doubt or scepticism about the trustworthiness of another party; whereas distrust reflects a more solid belief that another is untrustworthy. The issue is that in the absence of trust, the public and other charity stakeholders may become mistrustful or distrustful of charities and the charitable sector. The challenge for the sector, therefore, is to build and maintain trust, address, and ameliorate mistrust where it arises through actions such as being accountable and transparent; this to avoid the more serious situation of distrust and cynicism.

Keating and Thrandardottir (2017) cast doubt on the ability of the accountability agenda to increase trust in charitable organisations and the charitable sector. The paper argues that proponents of increased transparency and accountability, including academics, practitioners, government, and donors, often take a narrow view of trust- a model of rational trust. Here it is assumed that accountability and trust building are highly correlated. A rational model of trust assumes that 1) information disclosure is required to build trust and 2) punitive actions or legislation for those that fail to meet disclosure or external accountability demands, incentivise these disclosures, further enhancing trust. One interpretation is that a rational trust model has a starting position of untrustworthiness and perceived high organisational risk, ameliorated, and eventually reduced by effective information sharing or accountability mechanisms. Keating and Thrandardottir argue that this limited view of trust ignores the social trust perspective, although both forms can obviously co-exist. Co-existence of rational trust and

social trust greatly complicate the accountability and trust relationship. A social trust model starts from a position of intrinsic trust between an NGO (or small charity) and its stakeholders, largely due to the sharing of a common goal, set of beliefs and values, and their pursuit of a shared social mission. Social trust greatly reduces the need for verifying information since very little information is required to enhance perceived trustworthiness or reduce perceived risk. Rational trust and social trust therefore operate at opposite ends of a trust spectrum, having serious implications for the causal relationship between accountability and trust building. It is argued that the accountability agenda is effective in developing rational trust; but from a social trust perspective, these calls for increased transparency send signals that can create perceptions of untrustworthiness in the sector.

Keating and Thrandardottir suggest that the uniqueness of the charitable sector leads society to view NGOs as essentially trustworthy. However, the accountability agenda has potential to do more harm than good by creating further distrust and at significant cost, such as through the proliferation of resource-intensive voluntary accountability programmes., creating a downward spiral of decreasing accountability and trust in stark contrast to Hyndman and McConville's virtuous circle of trust and accountability. In exploring motives that underpin small charity accountability practices, the issue of whether rational trust or social trust models are adopted with different stakeholder groups is worthy of further exploration.

Several studies suggest that external stakeholders are most interested in effectiveness reporting e.g., reporting of benefits and social solutions (Connolly & Hyndman, 2013b; Populus, 2016). Hyndman and McConville (2018b) examined the issue of transparent reporting on charity effectiveness, specifically towards meeting the needs of stakeholders. The researchers developed a framework to enhance the reporting of charity effectiveness. Using this framework, they investigated the current state of play of charity effectiveness reporting. The concepts of stakeholder engagement and transparency “reporting useful, good quality,

understandable information as a basis for meaningful engagement (and perhaps ultimate accountability)” (p. 135) underpin the research. The researchers define charity effectiveness as “the comparison of outputs and/or outcomes from charitable activity to specific measurable targets related to the mission of the organisation” (p. 135). The researchers also provide clarification on the distinction between outputs (immediate or direct services) and outcomes (effect of an organisation on individuals or society). The paper also points to the absence of regulatory requirements regards outcomes. Social outcomes and/or outputs can be difficult to quantify or objectively measure both in the short and longer term; the wide variety of charity structures, activities and missions makes standardisation almost impossible.

Drawing on previous academic findings and sector discussion, the stakeholder focussed framework was constructed across 6 different dimensions, namely: measures, context, format, reliability, causality, stakeholder involvement. The key themes and desirable characteristics of useful and transparent reporting for stakeholders are thus captured in the reporting framework e.g., accessibility, demonstration of effectiveness, accessibility enhancing explanations and contextualisation, and stakeholder consultation. The top 100 UK charities, encompassing a broad range of social areas or functions, were tested against the framework. The data utilised included: Trustees Annual Reports and supplementary (beyond regulatory requirement) information sources such as Annual Reviews and website disclosures. Content analysis methods were used to identify and record disclosure elements against a framework checklist.

The findings of Hyndman and McConville (2018b) show upward trend in disclosures in terms of measures of output, outcomes, and effectiveness. However, a worrying pattern of inadequate reporting of effectiveness information was identified. The researchers suggest that a perceived lack of stakeholder interest, resource constraints and difficulties in setting targets might explain these findings. In addition, the reporting of “missed targets” represent evidence of charity or management failure, which can threaten legitimacy and harm the organisation. In terms of

volume of reporting, the researchers found that output and outcome information was reported on extensively, particularly within Annual Reviews. In contrast, charity effectiveness measures were found to be largely reported within the TARs. The researchers conclude that this provides evidence of some tailoring of information needs towards stakeholder's preferred communication mechanisms. Furthermore, it is noted that a large quantity of data provision does not necessarily enhance transparency and accountability. It was found that few charities provided context through benchmarking their outputs, outcomes, or effectiveness over time or against the sector. Explanations were also a rare occurrence in the sample investigated, although these were on the increase. The researchers suggest that a lack of benchmarking and poor explanation of charity performance seriously undermines accessibility, assessability i.e., transparency of charity disclosures. The research found that output-based measures were largely reported on numerical or quantitative basis, whereas outcomes reporting took a narrative approach. A trend towards increased quantification was identified and coupled with an increase in the variety of reporting mechanisms, it suggests there has been a general shift to communication by both story and numbers.

Adding to the challenge of transparent reporting in the sector are the difficulties associated with measuring performance. Hayes (1996), as cited in Cordery and Baskerville (2005), suggests four accountability requirements to measure efficiency and effectiveness in the sector. Financial accountability (as to how money has been spent); process accountability (as to extent that proper procedures are followed); programme accountability (as to effectiveness in achieving desired results); accountability for priorities (in fulfilling user needs). Drucker (1990) identifies the potential for imbalance where fiscal accountability utilising quantitative data is prioritised at the expense of qualitative information that can better serve process, programme, and accountability for priorities. To this end, Drucker suggests that long term goals should determine performance measures to drive improvement in charity operations and

management. These accounts of charity performance would likely require both quantitative and qualitative information to fully discharge accountabilities. Performance evaluation tools can be used to assess the extent to which both immediate and longer-term objectives have been met through a charity's programmes; these evaluations can be performed internally by staff, externally by funders, or independent parties, or through a combination of both.

Ebrahim and Rangan (2014) point to the difficulties in measuring social impact outcomes that can only be realised over time and at community and society levels. However, the pressure exists to provide upward accountability of this type to funders and regulators and tools such as the logical framework analysis (LFA) have emerged to assist NGOs. Ebrahim (2003) suggests that LFA allows objectives to be clearly expressed and linked to performance measures to the benefit of both NGOs and their funders, but this framework is less accommodating in complex NGO or charity interventions and activities. There are resource implications of performance evaluations; these performance evaluations are costly in terms of time and the staff expertise required, diverting charity focus and resource away from the charity activity and mission. Ebrahim (2002) further suggests that this information may be of only limited use to the internal decision-making of the NGO or charity. Evaluations that focus on short-term and easily quantifiable tangible outputs may result in an inefficient allocation of funds towards those charities who can simplify their programme output data and information; and away from those with more complex programmes and interventions. Ebrahim (2003) concludes by arguing for more focus on self-evaluation, with the aim of reflection, learning and self-improvement. Funders or donors should not be alarmed by a charity's failure to meet simplified performance criteria but should seek evidence that charity's offer honest account of their activities, learn from their mistakes and are able to grow and improve.

Summary

The literature examined reveals that accountability for these sectors is far from straightforward- to begin with there is no universally accepted definition of charity accountability. Part of the problem was that historically there was very little academic research dedicated to the issue. Most academics agree on the principle of “the giving of an account and the holding to account”. It has been suggested that charities by their very nature have high standards of integrity and honesty and so are quite naturally transparent in their activities. This virtue notwithstanding, accountability is multi-faceted and challenging for the sector, since wider social reporting is required to convince society of effectiveness in achieving charity mission. Building relationships and trust with stakeholders are important and can be achieved through sharing of useful and transparent information; whilst being cautious of tick-box approaches that provide quantity over quality. The charitable sector has endured negative publicity- and as such their legitimacy and sustainability have come under threat. The sector is perhaps being asked to do too much and some academics argue that it is being held to higher standards of transparency and accountability than the commercial sector.

2.3.2 Accountability to stakeholders in the charity sector

This subsection discusses the stakeholders identified from the academic literature and the challenges and issues around meeting stakeholder needs and expectations.

A discussion of accountability leads naturally to consideration of stakeholders or stakeholder relationships and user needs. There may be disagreement over the exact nature of the information that a charity should release, but Connolly and Hyndman (2004) and Hyndman and McDonnell (2009) conclude that user needs can at least be partly met through the release of the annual report. Hyndman and McMahon (2009) warn of the negative impact on public

confidence where charitable organisations fail to produce high quality accounting information. Research conducted by Parsons (2007) supports this conclusion where it was found that accountability in the form of financial reports and financial statements influenced donor's perceptions of a charity and the decision to donate, as well as aspects of non-financial disclosures. It could be argued that even small charitable organisations should adopt good practice here, even where annual reports, reviews and financial statements could be viewed as being basic in nature.

Hyndman and McConville (2018a) promote the idea that accountability through various disclosure mechanisms can be used to develop and maintain trust in individual charities and in the sector. Key to this is the tailoring of reporting and communication mechanisms used to engage with charity stakeholders, where an effective mix of public and private mechanisms can cement trust between charity and multiple stakeholders. The researchers frame the discussion around the recent erosion of public trust and suspicion over charity activity and financial management. The paper also references the work carried out by the Charity Commission for England & Wales to address this issue i.e., the refinements of SORP. Hyndman and McConville (2018a) argue that trust is essential to charity sustainability and achieving the charity mission. A wide variety of stakeholder relationships are underpinned by trust e.g., donors, volunteers, and the public; in the absence of trust these stakeholder groups are likely to withdraw their financial and human capital. Charities that fail to meet their social objectives, have poor financial management, pay their managers to excess, and exploit their donors, will erode public trust, and endanger charity survival. The paper used interviews with charity financial managers and other representatives to explore the mechanisms used to discharge accountability to their stakeholders. Hyndman and McConville (2018a) found that accountability was an important concept to charity managers, recognising the need to offer an account of how resources were utilised to deliver on social objectives. Many participants in the

study made the connection of accountability to trust building, whilst even more highlighted the importance of managing stakeholder relations and meeting their expectations for legal, regulatory, and moral reasons. Interviewees identified several “main stakeholders” i.e., beneficiaries, large funders, smaller donors and the public and provided their view of their information needs. The findings suggested that charities identify the public both as a complex and vague stakeholder group, as a funder through public tax funds or public donations or as beneficiaries. Charity managers highlighted their eagerness to engage with, be accountable and build trust with the public, but often wrestled with the uncertainties around what information the public would find useful and engaging. The relationship with the public operates at a distance and so there is difficulty in assessing and meeting information needs.

Connolly and Hyndman (2017) explored the challenges and potential conflicts that arise in meeting the accountability needs of both charity donors and beneficiaries. These stakeholders exist at opposite ends of the accountability spectrum in terms of their power, legitimacy, and urgency (Mitchell et al., 1997). A logical conclusion of stakeholder salience theory suggests that because large charity donors exhibit all three of these features this leads to a situation where “charities may focus on accounting to major donors at the expense of others (raising the potential for mission drift)” (Connolly and Hyndman, 2017, p.158). However, the authors argue that whilst stakeholder conflict is a safe assumption in the corporate context, conflict between donor and beneficiary in a charity setting is less likely since their interests, values and objectives are more closely aligned. Indeed, the paper sets out to challenge this assumption. Alternative stakeholder models have been proposed, for example Goodpaster (1991) and O’Dwyer and Unerman (2007) suggest going beyond a financial stakeholder focus since there are benefits to wider or more holistic stakeholder engagement.

The sample for the Connolly and Hyndman (2017) study included representation from four key stakeholder groups: charity auditors, charity managers and the beneficiaries and donors. Each

interviewee offered a particular insight into the challenges around meeting the accountability needs of two seemingly disparate stakeholder groups. As regards defining charity accountability there was consensus around the idea of accountability as stewardship, demonstrating that charity funds were being used to achieve the charity aims. This could be reinforced through good accounting systems and following SORP. As regards recognising and prioritising stakeholders, participants acknowledged that charities have a wide variety of stakeholders. Managers identified the challenges of meeting both donor and beneficiary needs; donors and managers highlighted the difficulties in engaging with beneficiaries; and auditors presented the view that whilst beneficiaries should perhaps be the focus, donors can be an effective proxy since they have the interests of the beneficiary at heart. In terms of the instruments or mechanisms of accountability, it was found that small donors and beneficiaries had little appetite for formal communications such as annual reports, preferring the less formal magazines and stories, consistent with a communal or socialising form of accountability. However, these groups did expect more formal communications such as the annual report to be available for scrutiny by those more able than themselves. Small donors were less inclined to base their giving behaviour on analysis of accountability information and more inclined to base this on reputation and the charity mission itself. Large donors expected formal regulation compliant annual reports as well as more detailed internal management accounting information and often regular reports regarding specific projects. Beneficiary groups stated that formal communications should include additional explanation or narratives to support the numbers, including more detail on performance, managers suggested that even smaller charities would have this information at hand internally. Managers cautioned though that performance measurement remained a difficult task in terms of finding useful and reliable measurements and the resource required to develop and monitor these.

Measurements of social impact or outcomes were particularly troublesome. The researchers suggest that since donor and beneficiary interests are aligned, an instrumental approach, focussing on donor needs, can in fact result in a ‘multi-fiduciary’ model i.e., accountability processes and practices that serve a multitude of stakeholder groups. The researchers concede that there remains uncertainty over whether donors or beneficiaries should be the focus for charity managers when discharging their accountability. The researchers observed that in many instances donors cede or share power with “weaker” beneficiaries, and managers themselves seek to engage with these beneficiary groups thus tempering any potential over-bearing demand/focus for upward accountability. The study re-iterates the importance of donors to charity survival and whilst the risk of mission drift is real if donors lose sight of charity mission, this risk is small. The paper points to the challenges of managing the seeming paradox that the best way of serving beneficiary interests could be by meeting the interests (and accountability demands) of donors. The authors suggest an “interplay of donor and beneficiary accountability” (p.157), where each can re-enforce the other. In conclusion, the researchers optimistically suggest that focus on either the beneficiary or the donor interests has a circular effect that can serve to strengthen all stakeholder accountability.

Smith and Miller (2018) investigated accountability mechanisms and accounting procedures utilised by small charitable organisations in Scotland. The purpose of the paper was to investigate the issues, challenges and tensions faced by small charities in meeting the information needs of various stakeholder groups. A single case study charity was used involving fieldwork, underpinned by both qualitative and interpretivist design, the research utilised interviews to collect the data. Smith and Miller found that small charities experienced significant pressure of upward accountability towards regulators, legislators, accounting standard setters and donors. Indeed, the charity was found to be anxious and insecure in terms of the accounting procedures required to satisfy the Scottish regulator and the large funding

bodies. Methods and practice of accounting developed in an ad-hoc and organic way in response to the demands placed on the organisation by these powerful stakeholders. Accounting practices and the annual report were found to be an essential accountability mechanism in meeting the needs of these financial stakeholders. The charity in question also did acknowledge a need to involve and communicate with the local community beneficiaries out of a moral duty more than anything else.

Overall, it was found that whilst most reports demanded of the organisation were not particularly onerous on their own, the various information requests from multiple stakeholders imposed significant burden. Smith and Miller suggest that a balanced scorecard approach or model could help charities to understand and simplify their accountability issues and responsibilities. The proposed model highlights three perspectives: learning and growth, internal processes, and the stakeholder perspective- with all perspectives operating to enhance the charity mission. The model suggests splitting of stakeholders between financial and beneficiary groups to differentiate their information needs. Financial stakeholders would require various financial performance measures; whereas beneficiaries would require careful consideration of measurements related to impact, utility or value added. Smith and Miller argue that such a model would facilitate both upward and downward accountability, and even help identify common objectives and measures that could serve multiple stakeholders. The research adds significantly to the question of how small charities in Scotland are managing and responding to information needs of stakeholders. The research offers valuable insights into the accountability issues faced by these organisations and a possible solution. However, the sample under investigation was limited to one charity, a community park facilities charity, a wider study is justified to incorporate different charity types/sectors and their alternative perspectives.

Summary

Accountability is inextricably tied to an organisation's stakeholders. There is no absolute agreement over the exact nature of information that should be shared with stakeholders. Research suggests that formal annual reports and financial statements can meet the needs of some users and influence perceptions and donations. However, Hyndman and McConville (2018a) argue that reporting and communication mechanisms must be designed to effectively engage with charity stakeholders. They argue that a wide variety of stakeholder relationships are underpinned by trust and that accountability builds this trust. The research showed that charity managers make the accountability and trust connection, and many strive to manage stakeholder relations and meet their expectations. Connolly and Hyndman (2017) set out to challenge the assumption that there is conflict between key stakeholders in a charity context i.e., between donors and beneficiaries. The researchers suggest that there is often an alignment in their interests, values, and objectives; there is scope to design accountability processes and practices focussed on donor needs, but that do indeed serve a multitude of stakeholders. Smith and Miller (2018) found that small charities can experience pressure and anxiety in satisfying upward accountability to regulators and donors; it was found that information requests from multiple stakeholders imposed a significant burden.

2.3.3 Characteristics and forms of accountability in the charity sector

This sub-section provides a summary of academic research that has attempted to characterise accountability and identify different forms of accountability in the sector. These theories of accountability underpin the research that is to be undertaken.

Ebrahim (2003) offers several definitions and perspectives on accountability from the academic literature. Reference is made to the notion of accountability as responsibility, being held

responsible and taking responsibility i.e., accountability has both external and internal dimensions (Chisolm, 1995; Fry, 1995; Najam 1996). The author draws attention to important dichotomies to further distinguish between upward and downward accountability and functional and strategic accountability. Upward accountability refers to the relationship between an organisation and its provider of funds e.g., donors and governments; whilst downward accountability refers to relationships with beneficiaries and local communities impacted by the charity activity. Within this complex scenario of multiple external stakeholders not-for-profits also seek internal accountability to their own mission, staff, and to themselves (Najam, 1996). Ebrahim argues, therefore, that “NGOs face the competing demands of multiple stakeholders more acutely and regularly than do private firms” (Ebrahim, 2003, p.814).

Functional accountability offers information regards resource utilisation and outcomes in the short-term to easily identifiable stakeholders, whereas strategic accountability refers to long term impact for the whole sector and the wider social mission. Given the difficulty in identifying stakeholders, measuring impacts, and establishing control or agency relationships, it is no surprise that strategic accountability would be weak in the not-for-profit (NFP) sector. And, by a similar logic, it follows that functional upward accountability to more powerful external stakeholders such as donors and regulators would be more prevalent than functional downward accountability to beneficiaries or clients (Najam, 1996). Ebrahim (2003) notes the contribution of organisational behaviour literature to the ongoing discussion and scrutiny of accountability. For example, resource exchange or resource dependence theory can help to explain the exchanges of information and resources between organisations and their stakeholders. In this context, information asymmetries notwithstanding, organisations and large donors are inter-dependent. Patrons of NFPs require an account of how their money has been spent by the managers of these organisations and the extent to which these funds have furthered charity activities and mission.

Reports and disclosure statements, in the form of the ‘Trustee Annual Report’ in the UK are legally required by the Charity Commission or OSCAR. The regulatory bodies oversee the sector and can investigate and intervene where concern is raised over the quality, authenticity or performance revealed by the annual report. These legal disclosures offer a degree of accountability to regulators, donors, beneficiaries, and members with both the will and expertise to access these types of documents, but often more detailed and more frequent reporting would be required e.g., for donors and members. Ebrahim (2003) defines this category of accountability primarily as a tool of upward accountability, primarily focussed on financial performance, and of limited use in facilitating downward accountability. Furthermore, these tools are outward-facing or externally driven, motivated by threat of loss of charitable status or withdrawal of finance. It is unclear to what extent these reporting tools would encourage internal accountability or responsibilities. Also, there may be some scope for exploring strategic accountability in periodic reports and reviews, but a narrower entity-focussed functional accountability is more likely for small charities.

In consideration of what small charities should be accountable for, several academics distinguish between functional accountability as being accountable for short-term resource use and performance; and strategic accountability as being accountable for long-term outcomes and mission achievement i.e., outputs versus outcomes (Ebrahim, 2003; Najam, 1996). Cordery and Sim (2018) identify assorted reasons cited for accountability from the literature that can be described as either functional or strategic accountability. Examples of why small charities made themselves functionally accountable included: to obtain funds and donations, to continue to deliver services, to satisfy lenders, to ensure the community is content with current activities, and to ensure they are internally effective and efficient. Examples of why small charities made themselves strategically accountable included: to show delivery on the organisation mission, to show they are responsive to community’s ongoing needs, to show they can collaborate and

support other community voluntary organisations, and to show they are being honest about long term impact.

Parker (2003) also highlights the challenges of meeting multiple accountabilities in the sector. There is a conflict between addressing the needs of the widest range of stakeholders and serving the interests of a narrower group of powerful and salient finance providers. In characterising accountability, Roberts (1991) describes accountability as being either hierarchal/upwards or socialising/downwards. Several academics identify a potential lack of downward accountability due to a lack of power and urgency (Cordery and Baskerville, 2011; Dixon et al, 2006; Mourey et al, 2013). Cordery and Sim (2018) pull together various findings and arguments from the literature to describe and explain accountability across their six types of civil society organisation (CSO). CSOs encompass voluntary and community-based organisations, including small, regulated charities, but also including informal, non-regulated community groups. For example, studies of ‘Classic Charities’ have shown that there is often a lack of mechanisms to facilitate downward accountability (O’Dwyer and Unerman, 2007; O’Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015). Whereas literature around ‘Membership CSOs’ suggests that (normative) downward accountability should be a natural priority for encouraging participation and serving member interests (Ebrahim, 2003). This is despite the potential for “multiple accountabilities disorder” (Koppell, 2005, p.94) where charities are overwhelmed by numerous stakeholders that are connected due to the various activities and finance sources of charities. Drawing upon numerous academic sources, Cordery and Sim (2018) present a summary of stakeholder groups classified as either upwards e.g., donors, funders, and grant makers or downwards e.g., members, staff, and beneficiaries. This provides the framework for their investigation to identify to whom CSOs are reporting and the balance between upward and downward communication.

Roberts (1991) suggested that there exists a hierarchy of accountability and Baur and Shmitz (2012) point to the phenomena of co-optation, where upward accountability demanded by powerful regulators and funders detracts from service provision and accountability to less powerful beneficiaries. This movement to upward accountability manifests in the increased emphasis on reporting of financial performance metrics as demanded by the regulations of OSCR and standards of SORP. Smith et al (2018) recommend that organisations identify their hierarchal position by asking the question “To whom are we accountable?” (Smith et al, 2018, p5). The answer to this question, a charity must examine their stakeholders and understand the powers within these relationships. Several case studies conclude that there exists a tension in seeking to satisfy the information requirements of disparate stakeholder groups, and often to the detriment of the charity mission and those less powerful groups (Williams and Taylor, 2013; O’Dwyer and Boomsma 2015). O’Dwyer and Boomsma (2015) and Agyemang et al. (2017) distinguish between formal, legal processes of ‘imposed’ upward accountability to funders and regulators; and the moral, ethical ‘felt’ accountability to beneficiaries, communities, and the social mission.

This again adds to the argument around a need to balance the complex array of stakeholder relationships and information requirements between ‘imposed’ and ‘felt’ accountabilities. ‘Felt accountability’ can be more precisely specified by further sub-categorisation into either ‘internal accountability’ or ‘identity accountability’, where there exists a value-driven accountability to charity mission at organisational level (Ebrahim, 2003) or individual actor level (Unerman and O’Dwyer, 2012) respectively. Identity accountability pertains to individuals and their belief in what they do but results from a strong belief in the charity mission. Identity accountability can exist alongside other accountabilities, but certainly there can be conflict with upward accountability demands if they are incongruous, distracting, or disruptive to the charity mission.

Roberts (2009) offers an alternative to hierarchal accountability in the form of a socialising accountability. In this setting stakeholders have similar power, have closer relationships, and in the case of small charities, usually have a shared social mission or objective. However, both forms of accountability need not be mutually exclusive and may co-exist to connect the charity more meaningfully with its network of interdependent stakeholders. Smith and Miller (2018) suggest that to ascertain the dominant type of accountability, a charity must examine its stakeholder relationships and their prioritisation. The researchers also explored the mechanisms employed and the extent to which accounting information will “help or hinder it in undertaking its duties and meeting its responsibilities” (Smith and Miller, 2018, p7). Academic work has also progressed from exploring the benefits and possibilities afforded by accountability to caution over its limitations, unintended consequences, and usefulness (Roberts, 2009; Messner, 2009). O’Dwyer and Unerman (2008) found that conflicts can arise where a charity attempts to balance its accountability to stakeholders with their charitable activities and mission.

Summary

Several characteristics and forms of accountability have been identified from the literature. These characterisations are important to understand the various accountabilities that are of relevance to organisations in the charity sector. For this research, it is important to determine to what extent these different forms of accountability are: perceived and understood; prioritised and utilised, dominant, or absent; and presenting challenges to the organisations under study. The following table summarises the characteristics and forms of accountability:

Table 2: Characteristics and forms of accountability identified from literature

Accountability	Description	Source(s)
External accountability	Multiple external groups e.g., funders, government, regulators, beneficiaries, communities. Impacted by charity activities. Being held responsible.	Chisolm (1995); Fry (1995); Najam (1996)
Internal accountability	Accountable to charity mission, volunteers & staff. Value driven.	Chisolm (1995); Fry (1995); Najam (1996); Ebrahim (2003)
Upward accountability	Accountability to providers of funds and regulators. Powerful. Urgent. Focus on financial performance. Formal and Legal.	Ebrahim (2003); Roberts (1991); Cordery et al, 2011; Dixon et al, 2006; Mourey et al, 2013; Baur and Shmitz (2012)
Downward accountability	Accountability relationships with beneficiaries and local communities. Lack power and urgency. Often voluntary.	Ebrahim (2003); Roberts (1991); Cordery et al, 2011; Dixon et al, 2006; Mourey et al, 2013; Baur and Shmitz (2012)
Hierarchal accountability	Aligned with upward accountability. Formal. Stakeholder power is important.	Roberts (1991); Smith and Miller (2018)
Socialising accountability	Aligned with downward accountability. Informal. Close stakeholder relationships are important. Shared social mission.	Roberts (2009)

Functional accountability	Accounts of short-term outputs and resource use. OM can be designed. Stakeholders easily identified. Narrow.	Ebrahim (2003); Cordery and Sim (2018)
Strategic accountability	Accounts of long-term impact and outcomes towards social missions. Difficult to measure. Stakeholders are vague. Wide.	Ebrahim (2003); Cordery and Sim (2018)
Imposed accountability	Aligned with upward accountability. Demanded. Formal. Often legal.	Fry (1995), O'Dwyer and Boomsma (2015), Agyemang et al (2017)
Felt accountability Internal- at organisation level Identity- at individual actor level	Aligned with downward accountability. Voluntary. Moral and ethical. Strong belief in charity mission.	Fry (1995), O'Dwyer and Boomsma (2015), Agyemang et al (2017); Ebrahim (2003); Unerman and O'Dwyer (2012)
Instrumental accountability	Transactional relationships or exchange of resources both internal & external. Focus on reporting and outcomes.	Knutsen and Brower (2010)
Expressive accountability	Articulating values and beliefs. Wider accountability to mission, community, beneficiaries. Difficult to measure. Aligned with Downward.	Knutsen and Brower (2010)

Source: Author

2.3.4 Accountability research by organisation type

This section reviews literature that explores distinct categories of charities and voluntary organisations within their accountability research. A charity can be categorised in several ways if its features are closely examined. Accountability perceptions, practices and challenges might be better understood by differentiating between various categories or types of charity.

It is possible to classify organisations in the charity sector by funding type, recognising three broad categories, namely: (1) service-providing charities that employ fund-raising for charity activity, (2) grant-making charities that generate funds from fundraising, investments, and issue of grants; (3) endowed charities that generate income from property and investments to provide services or gifts. Cordery and Sim (2018) categorise CSOs as belonging to six types, whilst also being cognisant of management, activities, financing, and regulatory features. Accountability was explored through rigorous survey analysis across three dimensions or characteristics, namely: to whom CSOs are accountable; for what CSOs are accountable; and how accountability is discharged. The six different charity types recognised by Cordery and Sim were: Advocacy (advocate for change); Classic Charities (e.g., supporting disadvantaged groups); Infrastructure CSOs (provide facilities and support systems); Membership CSOs (serve interests of members e.g., sports); Trusts/Grantors (make investments and issue grants); Service Providers (deliver goods and services, but non-profit making). Cordery and Sim (2018) tested the validity of these CSO categorisations by ascertaining the similarities and differences between their accountability characteristics. In a similar vein, Hayes (1996) as cited in Cordery and Baskerville (2005), had previously suggested that charities could be characterised by their function e.g., service provision, pressure group, mutual aid, and resource co-ordination functions.

CSOs can also be defined and categorised by examining their legal structures, financing, and activities (Salamon and Anheier, 1992a, b). Many authors have attempted to dichotomise CSOs in attempts to understand and categorise these organisations e.g., Hansmann (1986) as cited in Cordery et al., (2017), suggests member-controlled vs independent management or donation dependent vs commercial. Unerman and O'Dwyer (2006) identify both welfare and advocacy organisations. In addition, a categorisation of CSO would be incomplete without consideration of stakeholders. Several academics recognise that stakeholders such as regulators, finance providers, local communities, beneficiaries, and volunteers define a charity and the context in which it operates (Cordery & Baskerville, 2011; Mitchell et al, 1997). A potential imbalance has also been highlighted between the demands from powerful stakeholders such as regulators and funders and potentially marginalised, less-powerful groups, such as communities and beneficiaries. Mitchell et al. (1997) suggests that CSO categorisation must consider the power and legitimacy of finance providers and regulators.

Cordery et al. (2019) suggest that organisations can be defined and contextualised by their regulation, financing, governance, purpose, stakeholders, and activities. The authors set out a framework for understanding NGO accountability by mapping or cross-referencing these definitional characteristics of NGOs with the accountability demands of external regulators, internal managers, and other stakeholder groups. Regulators, acting on behalf of stakeholder groups, demand mostly financial accounts of charity activity. These accounts can serve to protect interests of weaker stakeholders but may be directed primarily towards the needs of more powerful financial stakeholders i.e., donors and funders. However, research suggests that regulations may fall short in facilitating comprehensive stakeholder accountabilities, including internal, felt accountabilities (Cordery et al., 2019; Kemp and Morgan, 2019; McDonnell and Rutherford, 2019) and so alternative, informal, voluntary, and enhanced accounts can emerge to address stakeholder needs (Lehman, 2007). It seems obvious that the source of funding for

charities would dictate accounting and accountability requirements i.e., what a charity accounts for and to whom it offers its account. Indeed, a small charity would have to adopt various accountability processes to accommodate the accountability preferences of its various funders. Governance can influence accountability attitudes and practices and so it can be useful to categorise NGOs and charities by governance arrangements. Cordery et al. (2019) identifies organisations as being either member-controlled or controlled by an independent governing body. However, the authors highlight the importance of context since “governance, purpose, finance, regulation and accountability are reflexively inter-related” (p5). Certainly, accountability of small community member-based organisations will contrast with accountability of large independently managed charities (Yates et al, 2019; Uddin and Belal, 2019). Lehman (2007) suggests that NGO governance includes taking responsibility for impact of activities at local community-level, which means going beyond accounting for use of financial resources to produce detailed qualitative, and sometimes subjective, accounts of activity. Charities have a wide range of social purposes, missions, and activities and so there is difficulty in finding a one size fits all approach to accounting standards, annual reports, and accountability processes. Indeed, Cordery and Sim (2018) found that there were distinct differences in the accountability practices and processes between charities engaged in different charitable activities.

Charity or NGO purpose can be viewed as a critical defining characteristic of these organisations and should be a hugely influential driving factor to focus mission driven activities and accountabilities (Cordery et al., 2019; McDonnel and Rutherford, 2019; Kemp and Morgan, 2019; Uddin and Belal, 2019; Yates et al., 2019). Accountability to beneficiaries can be a means to achieve this purpose driven accountability with the advantage of linking performance to purpose and simultaneously discharging accountability to multiple stakeholders (Uddin and Belal, 2019). Cordery et al (2019) conclude that there is ample

research evidence to suggest that organisations have genuine commitment to serving a wide range of stakeholders, serving the many rather than the powerful few, and to disclosure of accounts that have strong links to charity purpose. In addition, the proliferation of “alternative accounts” have shown that accounting and accountability can be forward facing by communicating future problems, actions, and solutions to ongoing social issues. This contrasts with a mere historic performance summary. Ultimately, this leads to improvement in dialogue between charity and its stakeholders and can sustain focus on charity purpose and its effectiveness. Within service clubs, Yates (2019) found that accountability processes and mechanisms were being customised to fit the needs of local communities and strengthen community relationships.

Yang (2017) investigated accountability within the hierarchy of large high profile service clubs. The paper adopted institutional work theory and identity accountability to explore how charity actors shape charity outcomes measurement (OM). The two charitable service clubs under investigation provided mixed results e.g., charity actors from one charity perceived conflict of the imposed OM with charity mission and identity so engaged in practices to disrupt institutional practices. In stark contrast, actors for the other charity strongly believed that funder relationship was key to survival and so engaged in their institutional work to support the OM practices of current and even anticipated upward accountability. The research concludes that upward accountability does indeed drive OM practices, but often interacts with identity accountability to further align OM with charity mission. However, the research found that in instances where charity actors suggested more meaningful OM that would capture key indicators for service improvement, funders failed to use these for accountability purposes. Yang concludes that conversations are required between knowledgeable charity actors and their funders to “facilitate the co-construction of accountability relationships by NFPs and their funders” (p 224).

Summary

In many instances, charity categories or types can be useful in explaining aspects of accountability. These include advocacy, classic, infrastructure, membership, trust/grantors, and service providers. Several researchers also point to other characteristics such as: management and governance, activities, legal structure, financing, and regulation. Researchers also point to dichotomies of charity type such as: member-controlled vs independently managed and donation dependent vs commercial. These dichotomies can be useful but an oversimplification, context is important since governance, purpose, finance, regulation, and accountability is inter-dependent. Several academics also recognise the stakeholder view of charities suggesting that charities can be categorised by for example: regulators, finance providers, local communities, beneficiaries, and volunteers. This stakeholder context is important to define in understanding the characteristics of charities under study. Charities have an extensive range of activities and these activities have been found to partly determine accountability practices. The wide range of charity mission and activities creates an accountability challenge since there might be no one size fits all approach to standardisation of reports and accountability processes. Charity purpose is an important defining characteristic and should direct charity activity and accountabilities. Purpose driven accountability links performance to purpose and could be effective in sustaining charity focus and to discharge multiple accountabilities. Charity structure may also be an important defining characteristic for understanding accountability processes since those operating under a larger umbrella organisation e.g., local clubs might have accountability demands imposed by central managers. Local level organisations may be in conflict or harmony with these centralised accountability arrangements dependent upon for example felt or identity accountability at local level. To summarise, the findings here suggest that there are several important defining charity

characteristics and types that should be considered in research of small charities and voluntary associations.

2.3.5 Disclosure mechanisms for discharging accountability

This section builds on previous sections by exploring the practical ways in which organisations can share information with their stakeholders. There are numerous mechanisms that can be used to address the accountability aims of the organisation and meet stakeholder needs and/or expectations. Disclosure mechanisms may serve single stakeholders or have multiple use. Benefits, issues and challenges in selection and adoption of various mechanisms are discussed in the subsequent section.

Academics have identified two broad mechanisms for discharging their accountability: public and private mechanisms. Publicly available information manifests in the prescribed Annual Reports for the sector, and in a range of unregulated voluntary reports and, for example, website communications. This publicly available information aims to serve the broad and general needs of various stakeholder groups.

Hyndman & McConville (2018a) found that an array of both public and private information and communication mechanisms were used to meet the actual or perceived information needs of stakeholder groups. Public communications being annual reports, annual reviews, and websites; private mechanisms being direct reporting, participation, observation, and feedback. The researchers suggest that there is an interplay of mechanisms of accountability and trust, where multiple mechanisms can be employed to meet the needs of individual stakeholders or stakeholder groups. The study reveals that charities believe that public and formal accountability such as annual reports have limited use to beneficiaries, whereas private mechanisms such as direct observation of activities, participation in activities e.g., board

presence and feedback on charity activities, are appropriate and effective. The data shows that large funders as a stakeholder group demand information on outcomes (including beneficiary experience) and spending. To this end, private direct reporting is used to provide the specific financial and performance information that is required. Interviewees identified the challenges of meeting these tailored demands for information, but many managers viewed this as essential to being transparent and promoting trust building.

The paper argues that a “virtuous circle of accountability and trust” (p.227) can be created where charities use effective public and private mechanisms of accountability to build trust; an established trust will then facilitate ever more detailed and transparent private channels of communication. Trust building could be more effective if specific private communication channels or mechanisms are developed to address information needs of individual stakeholders regards performance or outputs. In addition, mechanisms that create opportunity for stakeholders to participate in charity activity and providing evidence of self-regulation go beyond publicly available information.

Disclosure mechanisms such as annual reports and performance reviews are used to both maintain and attract further funds. Ebrahim (2003) describes accountability as being both “complex and dynamic” and “operates along multiple dimensions- involving numerous actors (patrons, clients, selves), using various mechanisms” (Ebrahim, 2003, p. 815). Ebrahim distinguishes between accountability mechanism tools and processes. Here a mechanism tool refers to discrete or easily identifiable devices or techniques used to discharge accountability e.g., periodic documented reports or reviews of performance. In contrast, accountability processes as the name suggests, are less discrete, are likely to be on-going and multifaceted such as participation and self-regulation. The distinction may not be so clear where these processes may incorporate several tools. Five broad categories are identified by the research regards the mechanisms of accountability available to NGOs: reports and disclosure

statements, performance assessments and evaluations, participation, self-regulation, social audits. The two foremost being tools of accountability and the latter three best fitting description as accountability mechanism processes.

Ebrahim (2003) offers four generalisations regards participation. One “level” refers to publicly available information such as public meetings, dialogues and communication with charity members and community leaders. The second level of participation would actively involve the public in charity or NGO activity through a contribution of capital i.e., finance or labour towards charity programmes. A third level of participation suggests a shift of power and control to the public and local communities where the public can determine which charity activities take place and which will receive funding. A fourth level of participation regards the power of the public to mobilise themselves for social change without any need for formal organisations like NGO or charities.

Najam (1996) calls into question the extent to which participation at the first two levels can have any meaningful impact on a community’s ability to exercise influence over decision-making since these stakeholders do not have power to withdraw funding. Increased dialogue, collaborations, information sharing and participation in decision-making regards programmes and financing can go some way to re-dress the imbalance of power between donors and NGOs and clients. Charities should seek community representation on Boards and widening of voting membership. In addition, processes and tools of evaluation should not neglect the views and needs of those less vocal stakeholder groups who require representation. Downward accountability can be enhanced through this power sharing, where communities can be involved in both the development and assessment of performance objectives.

Ebrahim (2003) presents the ‘social audit’ as a complex and stakeholder focussed accountability mechanism incorporating several tools and processes. Although assorted

designs and methodologies exist, the key components of a social audit are the following: stakeholder identification, stakeholder communication, use of performance indicators, paths to improvement, and public disclosure. The benefits of the social audit process summarised by Ebrahim (2003) include development of information systems, enhancing mechanisms and indicators for accountability to all stakeholders, incorporating stakeholder feedback into future decisions, and lastly enhancing trust and legitimacy especially where there is external verification. However, these benefits cannot be realised without significant cost, this being especially burdensome on small organisations. Indeed, unless information systems are designed to be simple and tailored to each NGO, then the additional strain of social audit could overwhelm smaller organisations. Adopting the principles of social audit may offer a less costly path. A principles-based approach may be more viable than a complete overhaul of data, information processes and systems. Short term performance indicators can be tweaked, long term impacts can be incorporated into assessments, and weaker stakeholder groups can be invited to participate. The concern remains over whether the proliferation of social audit and its standards function as an effective mechanism for accountability or merely serve as a mechanism for marketing and legitimising.

Despite the concerns, Ebrahim (2003) concludes that the social audit can incorporate many desired accountability-enhancing features. Multifaceted stakeholder involvement facilitates both upward and downward accountability e.g., collaboration on development of performance indicators and dialogues on performance assessments.

The mechanisms of accountability can be retrospective i.e., historical reporting or prospective i.e., forward facing. O'Dwyer and Boomsma (2015) suggest that donors can impose budgets and quality systems on classic charities thus limiting retrospective mechanisms to narrow quantitative reporting. Patel and Cordery (2011) also found that there was inadequate prospective accountability within formal accounts and disclosures filed with regulatory bodies.

Connelly et al. (2013) suggest that the most essential information around beneficiaries is therefore often overlooked. Regarding membership organisations, several mechanisms can be used to share information regards charity activities such as the AGM, communication from the chairperson and organisation newsletters (Ospina et al, 2002). Open meetings and elections can serve as effective prospective mechanisms where consultations can occur and organisational change considered (Koppell, 2005). Cordery and Sim (2018) pull together the various accountability mechanisms identified in the literature and classify these as either retrospective or prospective mechanisms.

Websites and social networks are viable as disclosure mechanisms for sharing voluntary information beyond mandatory reporting requirements. Standalone online reports also serve as effective ways of sharing information regards mission, activities, and social impact. Waters et al., 2009 and Greenberg and Macaulay, 2009 both point to the benefits that social networking can offer in its ability to connect with various stakeholder groups. The goal of strengthening these relationships is to attract both human (volunteers) and financial resources. Saxton et al (2014) confirm that increased disclosure via the medium of charity websites does in fact lead to an increase in charitable contributions. Saxton and Wang (2014) also found that social networking established new ways of fund-raising for charitable organisations. However, Greenberg and Macaulay (2009) cautioned that causation can be difficult to establish, and the inverse of the revenue-social network relationship could be just as likely. They argued that the costs of maintaining social network technology could be prohibitive for smaller organisations and so higher revenues would lead to higher levels of social networking rather than the other way around.

Bellante et al. (2018) evaluated the impact of additional voluntary disclosures on performance. The analysis was conducted using data from a random sample of 200 UK charities registered on the Charity Commission Register of England and Wales. It was found that disclosure of

strategic plans was not a significant variable for performance; however, publication of volunteer information had a significant if only weak positive effect. Of most significance was the finding that the use of social networks had the strongest significant positive effect on performance. Importantly, the study was framed in the context of a regulatory environment with medium-high level accountability requirements i.e., Charity Commission Register of England and Wales. Further analysis of variable relationships showed that small charities were less likely to use social networks. This raises the issue of whether these conclusions are valid in the context of small Scottish charities and voluntary organisations. The question of whether small Scottish charitable organisations consider the potential income benefits of increased voluntary disclosures through social networking is an interesting one.

Summary

Broadly speaking, accountability mechanisms have been described in academic research as either public or private in nature. Typical public communication mechanisms include annual reports, annual reviews, and websites, whereas typical private communication mechanisms can include direct reporting, participation, and direct observation. Publicly available information can be used to build trust amongst a wide variety of stakeholders, but a charity may have to employ several private mechanisms to provide more detailed and targeted information to different stakeholder groups. Large funders, individual donors and beneficiaries can benefit from this enhanced private accountability. The web and social media can be an effective mechanism for sharing information with the wider public. Informal, accessible, and engaging formats such as annual reviews and stand-alone reports can be most effective in meeting the information needs of the public and individual donors i.e., non-specialists.

The following table collates the literature review findings across the previous sub-sections that discuss the challenges, and workable solutions, for managing multiple accountabilities in the charity sector:

Table 3: Challenges and Solutions for multiple accountabilities

Author	Multiple Stakeholders & Accountabilities	Challenges	Solutions
Hyndman & McKillop (2018)	Yes, to improve trust, General public as wider stakeholders	Building public trust	Sector wide responses.
Alsop and Morgan (2019)	Yes, to be accountable to stakeholders- mainly trustees and members	Argument that accruals accounting is more comprehensive.	R&P accounts effective for financial accountability. OSCR is robust.
Anheier (2005)	Yes, to be accountable to wider society	How to convince of effectiveness in achieving purpose and mission	“Social accountability” e.g., social reports
Hyndman and McMahon (2011)	Yes, to improve trust, General public as wider stakeholders	Negative publicity, impact to funding	Increased transparency
Keating and Thrandardottir (2017)	Questions the need for accountability. Rational trust vs social trust argued.	Accountability agenda can harm charities- create distrust and financial cost of accountability processes.	NGOs taken as trustworthy (social trust). Match stakeholders to types of trust.
Hyndman & McConville (2015)	Yes, to be accountable to a wide range of financial and other stakeholders.	Balance the reporting of outcomes, outputs, and effectiveness. To be more transparent.	Combination of narrative and numbers- satisfy wide range of stakeholders. Their ‘reporting framework’

Ebrahim (2002)	Yes, but with focus on needs of funders & donors- upward accountability.	Designing performance measures. Costly & limited benefit. Charity complexity.	Improve relationships. Reduce importance of performance criteria. Improvement, learning and honest accounts of activities focus.
Hyndman and McMahon (2009)	Yes, wide range of stakeholders including public	Negative impact on public confidence where high quality accounting information not available	Stakeholder needs at least partly met by high quality annual report
Parsons (2007)	Focus on donor as key financial stakeholders	Financial and other aspects of non-financial disclosures influence giving	Balance between financial and other (voluntary) non-financial disclosures
Hyndman and McConville (2017)	Wide variety of stakeholder relationships- underpinned by trust.	General public information needs are vague (charity view).	Tailor reporting mechanisms- mix of public and private mechanisms.
Connolly and Hyndman (2017)	Accountability to donors and beneficiaries. Upward, hierarchal, contractual accountability- to powerful funders.	Potential conflict. Holistic accountability desirable- but requires resource.	Potential harmony- since interests are aligned. Donors share power. Focus on one group could benefit all.
Smith & Miller (2018)	Accountability primarily to funders and regulators (upward), but also (downward) to beneficiaries	Demands from multiple stakeholders imposes significant burden.	BS approach proposed- incorporating the stakeholder perspective e.g., financial vs beneficiary.
Najam (1996)	Wide range of stakeholders- donor & regulators are more visible in short term.	Strategic accountability weak. Powerful donors and regulators dominate accountability	Re-balance downward accountability towards beneficiaries or clients.
Ebrahim (2003)	Wide range of stakeholders- complex & dynamic.	Accountability tools focus on financial performance,	Clarify tools and processes. Participation is

	Accountability focussed on upward accountability- limited downward accountability.	outward facing, limited internal use. Narrow functional accountability.	important. Social audit. Self-regulation. Find the balance: external/internal, upward/downward, functional/strategic
Cordery & Sim (2018)	Wide variety of stakeholders- community, lenders, donors, internal	Extensive information requirements of stakeholders- both functional/strategic and upward/downward	Call for stakeholders to adapt their expectations- context specific. Principles of “variation”, “balance”, “multiple use”
Parker (2003)	Multiple accountabilities to wide range of stakeholders	Conflict in addressing needs of wider stakeholders vs narrow powerful groups	Solutions?
Loft et al (2006)	Several stakeholder groups- donors, beneficiaries, members	Potential for dominance of upward accountability	Participation and serving member interests- is a natural priority i.e., downward accountability
Baur and Shmitz (2012)	Potential for multiple stakeholders and accountabilities. Upward vs Downward.	Phenomena of ‘co-optation’. Upward accountability demanded by powerful regulators and funders- detract from service provision	Re-balance upward and downward. Focus on service provision. Add to this?
Roberts (2009)	Multiple stakeholder groups- hierarchal accountabilities.	Hierarchy of power potential to focus on powerful stakeholders only	An alternative ‘socialising accountability’- closer relationships and shared missions. Can co-exist to connect charity to stakeholders.
Smith et al (2018)	Multiple stakeholders- require prioritisation. What	Accounting information can help or hinder.	Examine stakeholder relationships and prioritise to determine

	mechanisms are employed?	Determining the dominant type of accountability.	dominant accountability
Cordery, Belal and Thomson (2019)	Wide range of accountability demands placed.	Accountability is complex- charity context mixed with wide range of potential accountability responsibilities.	Propose a framework for mapping characteristics e.g., regulation, financing, purpose with accountability demands.
Lehman (2007)	Accountable to wider society	Unelected and unaccountable. Limited by the current economic/political system.	Alternative, informal, voluntary, enhanced accounts to address stakeholder needs.
Bellante et al (2018)	Accountability to financial stakeholders- donors, grant makers, sponsors (revenue sources)	Establishing variables that positively affect performance e.g., governance, increased voluntary information, social networks	Use of social networks can positively affect income- provide voluntary and supplementary information. Governance can impact income.
Cordery and Sim (2018)	Accountability to wide range of stakeholders	Reporting historic information of limited use to improve charity. Distractions to charity purpose.	Alternative accounts. Forward facing- actions and solutions to improve dialogue and sustain charity focus.
Yang (2019)	Upward accountability to funders; identity accountability at local levels	Outcomes measurement (OM) demanded by funders can conflict with mission and identity	Conversations between charity actors and funders- build relationships- potential to design OM that enhance upward and identify accountability.
O'Dwyer & Boomsma (2015); Patel and Cordery (2011); Connelly et al (2013);	Accountability to wider communities, beneficiaries, and members	Imbalance between retrospective- limited to narrow quantitative reporting and	Open meetings, elections, consultations- all to consider change. AGM, newsletters,

Ospina et al (2002)		prospective- often overlooked to detriment of charity future and its beneficiaries	publish long term plans.
Waters et al (2009); Greenberg and Macauley (2009); Saxton and Wang (2014)	Various stakeholder groups. Accountability primarily required to attract volunteers and funders	Voluntary information required beyond mandatory reporting. How to attract and build relationships.	Social networking for connecting with stakeholders and building relationships, new ways of raising finance- to share stand-alone reports of activity (could be costly).
Cordery et al (2019); McDonnell and Rutherford (2019); Kemp and Morgan (2019); Uddin and Belal (2019); Yates et al (2019)	Accountability to multiple stakeholders- accountability to beneficiaries is important-	Potential for mission drift, need to consider charity purpose	Accounts with strong link to charity purpose. Accountability to beneficiaries to link performance to purpose and serve multiple stakeholders.
Taylor et al, 2013; O'Dwyer and Boomsma 2015	Various disparate stakeholder groups	Tension to satisfy information requirements- charity mission and less powerful groups suffer.	Stakeholder analysis- examining power and hierarchical positions.
Cordery et al, 2011; Dixon et al, 2006; Mourey et al, 2013	Numerous stakeholders- upward/downward	Lack of downward accountability- lack power or urgency.	Recognise power dynamics- do not neglect the less powerful
O'Dwyer and Unerman, 2007; O'Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015	Numerous stakeholders upward/downward	Lack of downward accountability- lack of mechanisms	Explore downward accountability mechanisms, possible multiple use

2.4 The research gap and a theoretical framework

The literature review has revealed a gap in the research literature within the broad area of non-governmental organisation, voluntary organisation and charity accountability that is worthy of further investigation. Specifically, within the area of charity accountability, medium to large charities have a substantial accountability literature, yet there is a dearth of academic literature that explores the phenomenon of accountability within micro and small charities. This research project aims to fill the research gap in small charity accountability literature by setting out to describe, explain, and explore aspects of accountability in the small Scottish charity context. The research, therefore, will undertake a unique study to enhance understanding of how accountability theories and stakeholder accountability relationships apply within small Scottish charities.

Based upon previous literature the following framework is proposed to describe and explain the accountability dynamics between small charities and stakeholders. Accountability forms emerge and are constructed between small charities and stakeholders whilst accountability is discharged and enacted through mechanisms of accountability. Senior decision-makers' perceptions of accountability i.e., to whom and for what they are accountable for, may not necessarily be evident in the discharging and enacting of accountability. This may be due to a "multiple accountability disorder", and a failure on part of the organisation to find and implement appropriate mechanism solutions for discharging accountability.

Given that the study is centred around the "small" sector then limited resources are expected to limit the scope of accountability i.e., forms of accountability will be constrained rather than holistic, transparency will be limited, and the mechanisms of accountability will be few. It is anticipated by the researcher that small charities will demonstrate external, upward, hierarchal, imposed, instrumental and functional forms of accountability since resources will necessarily

focus on demands from funders and regulators. It is also anticipated that the mechanisms employed will be low in number, be public to the extent that the annual report is disclosed, but mostly private, and be retrospective. It is anticipated by the researcher that small charities will demonstrate ‘felt’ accountability due to moral and ethical values and belief in the charity mission. The following model represents the accountability dynamic at play in the small charity sector that is interpreted from the academic literature and proposed by the researcher to help guide the research:

Figure 2: Constructing and enacting accountability in the small charity sector

Source: Author

The model shows the exchange of information between small charities and their stakeholders, either voluntarily or demanded. Information sharing is constrained to the extent that organisations have resources and capability to provide useful and transparent information. Stakeholders can supply resources such as finance, volunteer supply and legitimacy to small charities. Rational trust suggests that stakeholders require relevant quality information for trust building; whereas social trust perspectives suggest that stakeholders already begin from a position of trust, thus requiring reduced disclosure of charity information.

Small charities perceive and construct their accountability through the relationships they build and the information they share with stakeholders. This is influenced by stakeholder theory, agency, and stewardship theories, and the charity attitudes and motivations around accountability to stakeholders. Small charities enact or discharge accountability through their various accountability mechanisms, the choice and implementation of these is critical to charity accountability. The outcomes of the model are the different forms of accountability created or constructed between a charity and its stakeholders.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This chapter describes the methodology adopted to answer the research question and meet the research objectives. The chapter begins with a discussion of research philosophy and the research approach to be undertaken. The discussion then turns to the research design and strategies adopted to collect the relevant data required to answer the research questions. The research tools and techniques used to collect and analyse the data are then outlined with consideration of the validity and reliability of the data and findings. Finally, the chapter closes with discussion of research ethics and researcher reflexivity.

3.1 Research Philosophy and Approach

The view of this researcher is that taking one philosophical stance may not necessarily be the most effective way of addressing the research objectives and questions. In consideration of the epistemological, ontological, and axiological assumptions for the study a multi-dimensional and dynamic view of philosophy seems appropriate (Niglas, 2010, as cited in Tashakkori and Teddie, 2010). This suggests that extreme fixed views of the research phenomena may not always hold true- acknowledging the possibility for research operating somewhere between that which is objective and subjective; that which is independent and socially constructed; and that which can be generalised or is specific. This view is most closely aligned with pragmatism, a paradigm that permits various philosophical positions and may often accommodate multiple methods, certainly allowing freedom in methodological choice.

The two aspects of ontology: objectivism and subjectivism, must be considered as ways of viewing the world and its phenomena. Objectivism takes the position that social entities exist, external to and independent of social actors. For purposes of this study an objective view of the research phenomena would conclude that accountability is something that is well defined and can be objectively measured. The objectivist would surmise that charitable organisations

are bound by established policy and practice for the sector, constitutions, and regulatory rules i.e., accountability is a function of these objective factors. Stakeholder interactions and disclosures are, therefore, prescribed by the prevailing formal structures. This seems reasonable for aspects of mandatory disclosures and the processes of ‘upward accountability’ and ‘imposed accountability’ identified from the literature, but these objective views of accountability may be less useful when observing or seeking to understand voluntary or ‘downward accountability.’ The mechanisms and artefacts of organisational disclosures can be objectively measured, but the role of charity social actors in bringing about the multiple accountabilities suggests that a subjective view would also be required to understand the research issue and find answers to the research question.

At the other end of the ontological spectrum, subjectivism would assert that the social phenomenon of charity accountability is created or socially constructed by charity actors and their stakeholders because of their various perceptions and interpretations. This is a more complex view of the world where accountability is context specific, constantly changing and co-created by social interactions. This certainly seems a reasonable way to view voluntary reporting practices and the various alternative forms of wider accountability identified in the literature e.g., ‘downward accountability’ and ‘felt accountability.’ Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012, p.132) offer guidance and re-assurance along these lines by pointing to the fact that “in your research it is possible make use of both objective and subjective lenses”.

Epistemology is concerned with the nature of knowledge and the features or viability of the data in research disciplines. A positivist philosophy in social science aligns with the natural sciences where collection of observable data leads to quantification, statistical analyses, and generalisations. The positivist stance would reject data collected on human attitudes and perceptions for example since these are viewed as being unobservable social phenomena, although the positivist might look more favourably on this data if measurements and statistics

are presented. As suggested, certainly there are aspects of accountability that could be identified as being objective and therefore the positivist would seek to describe and explain accountability through quantifiable observation e.g., of disclosure practices, mechanisms, and artefacts. These observations being independent of the social actors involved in bringing about their existence. The positivist would also argue that their research is value neutral given that they and their research activity can exist independently of the data. Overall, the positivist researcher would claim to be objective in their pursuit of facts to describe or explain a research issue.

In a similar vein, the philosophy of realism would argue that a reality exists that is independent of the human mind and so can be observed and measured using scientific approaches. Bhaskar (1989), as cited in Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012), identifies two opposing forms of realism, direct realism, and critical realism. Epistemology of direct realists argue that that which can be observed is real, accurate and measurable, whereas critical realists counter that that which is observed is only part of a larger social picture. The direct realist would argue that full understanding and knowledge can be gained by direct observations of different variables; whereas the critical realists argue that knowledge can only be gained by understanding the influence of underlying social structures. A realist would view the issue of accountability as something that can be observed and measured in a scientific way to fully explain and understand it. A critical realist on the other hand would observe, measure, and describe accountability scientifically, but acknowledge the underlying social structures that explain it, through the theoretical lenses of social science.

In contrast to these philosophies, interpretivist traditions view the world as more complex and impossible to explain by the hard data, simplifications and generalisations offered by positivist research and scientific methods. Interpretivist philosophy acknowledges the roles of humans and their interactions as social actors within unique organisational and social contexts. The

interpretivist researcher is respectful of the interpretations of the social world taking place in the minds of both researcher and the research subjects. Humans interact, interpret, and construct the world around them in different ways, attaching different meanings to phenomena (Andrews, 2012). Social constructionism describes this situation where knowledge is actively constructed by social actors and is a key consideration in interpretative approaches. Certainly, research objectives that seek to gather data on charity actor experiences, perceptions and attitudes to accountability align with the interpretivist philosophy rather than the positivist view. The nature of the small charitable sector organisation, with its limited human resource, simple structures, and less prescribed procedures, policies, and roles, suggest that the perspective of the individual social actor is extremely important to the study of these organisations. However, other objectives seeking to describe the accountability mechanisms employed across the sector align more readily to positivist or realist approaches to observation, measurement, and analysis.

To meet the research objectives and answer the research questions, the research will avoid the limitations placed on it by these philosophical choices and favour the “anti-philosophy” of pragmatism. This is to echo the initial arguments that there may be multiple acceptable ways to answer a research question: using observable phenomena and subjective meanings, quantitative and qualitative data in the pursuit of knowledge.

The research could take several approaches in finding answers to the research questions. This also includes a consideration of the role of theory in the research design. A deductive approach or deductive reasoning begins with theory and academic literature as the basis for forming testable propositions and hypotheses i.e., theory testing. Existing theory or laws that have been established can be tested under new and precise conditions and contexts. The deductive process is scientific in nature and most often utilises quantitative data to measure concepts and variables and establish causal relationships between these. Through this process existing theories are

corroborated or rejected (Blaikie, 2010 as cited in Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Variables require a strict definition before they can be measured and so a reductionist view of phenomena would be required i.e., the data variables are reduced to simple measurable elements. Generalisation is only permissible to the extent that a sample is representative of a larger group. Inductive approaches and reasoning, in contrast, begin with data collection to explore the research issue with the aim of creating new theories i.e., theory follows data. Inductive approaches serve as an alternative to the simplifications of deductive approaches, proponents arguing that the variables of social research have a more complex human dimension and explanation. The inductive approach appreciates context, favours more flexible research designs, and more often draws upon qualitative data from small samples to explore phenomena.

An abductive approach to research offers an alternative to both deduction and induction, in fact it is an approach that combines both (Suddaby, 2006). The approach has both elements of theory building, or at least theory modification, and theory testing. As per inductive approaches, data can be the starting point to explore a phenomenon, leading to the identification of themes and patterns to create a theory or understanding. As per deduction, the theory can be assessed through further data collection. Abductive research may flow back and forth between these two approaches as theory is modified, tested, and refined. Importantly, the place of theory in the design is more flexible since it can be incorporated at whatever stage is deemed appropriate. Abduction therefore opens the possibility of combining research approaches.

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012) suggest that the choice of approach should be determined by several factors including: time constraints, the target audience, risk of failure, availability of literature and data, but the choice is determined by the research questions and objectives. The abductive approach would seem to be most appropriate to meet the research objectives and answer the research questions.

The existing accountability theories offer a solid theoretical framework for the study- but they are modified for the context of the small charity sector. This modification of theory (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012) is achieved through qualitative data collection and analysis in a first stage of inductive type enquiry. A purely inductive approach is ruled out on the basis that there is no intention or perceived need to build a brand-new theory of accountability. A purely deductive approach is ruled out on the basis that the researcher seeks to be open to the potentially unexpected explanations offered by qualitative data and inductive enquiry. Further justification of research approach follows in discussion of the research design and strategy.

3.2 Research design and strategy

Quantitative and qualitative research in the purest sense can be thought of as occupying two extremes of a research design spectrum: quantitative utilising numbers; and qualitative using non-numeric data such as narrative or video media. However, as per previous discussion of research philosophy and approach, many research projects in the social sciences would occupy a space within these two extremes, utilising both numeric and non-numeric data in data collection and analysis. Both quantitative and qualitative research designs should be considered as being suitable to answer the research questions, and in fact a combination of these could prove most effective and justified i.e., a multiple methods research design.

Quantitative research design is primarily associated with positivism and the scientific method but may also be adopted for use in research following other approaches such as pragmatic or interpretivist philosophy. Quantitative research and methods would normally employ statistical techniques to summarise numerical data, establish relationships and make comparisons. Quantitative research would also typically be consistent with the deductive approach, where data can be collected and analysed in attempt to test theories. An aspect of quantitative research

design would be useful for describing and summarising basic views on accountability for a sample of small charities utilising, for example, ranking and rating scale questions.

Qualitative research design is most often associated with an interpretivist philosophy where interpretations of subjective or socially constructed participant narrative or words are required. However, qualitative research design can also be consistent with realist and pragmatic philosophies. Qualitative research design seeks richer explanations and deeper understanding of research issues from the perspective of its participants. Qualitative research is most often conducted through process of inductive enquiry, where either new theory is created or revised and developed- but use of qualitative data to test existing theory in a deductive manner would also be possible. Qualitative data would typically be collected from small and non-probability-based samples of participants in attempt to explore the research issue in detail e.g., through extended discussion and narratives within open interviews, case studies or ethnography. Qualitative research design could be used to answer the research questions in several ways. For example, qualitative data from interviews or small focus groups could be used in a deductive manner to test existing theories of accountability, in an inductive manner to propose a new theory of accountability or using an abductive approach to develop existing theory.

Pragmatists would argue that both quantitative and qualitative research design are acceptable, and in fact any combination of quantitative and qualitative methods and data are acceptable where this will produce good answers to the research question(s). Pragmatists bypass the need for a consistency of research design with either positivism or interpretivism, seeing no value in adopting one extreme of this unhelpful dichotomy. Hence, pragmatists often adopt more flexible and non-restrictive multiple-method research designs. Researchers adopting multiple methods use more than one approach to data collection and analysis in attempt to explore a research issue from different angles with more comprehensive data collection and analyses. This is justified, given there are potential drawbacks of utilising only quantitative or only

qualitative data methods. Tashakorri and Teddlie (2010) and Natasi et al. (2010) detail several multiple methods approach as alternatives to the traditional mono methods of either quantitative only or qualitative only. Multiple methods research projects can be further characterised as either multimethod or mixed methods. Multimethod research projects involve more than one type of data collection process or tool but would use only quantitative data or qualitative data techniques. In context of small charity accountability research for example, a multimethod qualitative study could utilise both in-depth focus groups and in-depth interview data, whereas a multimethod quantitative study could utilise both highly structured surveys and highly structured interviews. The research is consistent in use of either quantitative or qualitative methods.

Mixed methods research usually involves the use of more than one data collection process or instrument (but can in fact also use just one) and utilises both quantitative and qualitative data. Many researchers have attempted to define mixed methods research design, but there is consensus that this is a design that combines or mixes both quantitative and qualitative approaches, techniques, and data into a single study (Tashakorri and Teddlie, 1998; Greene et al., 1989; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). There are of course many ways to combine or mix research methods so the researcher must consider the most effective way of integrating the methods and data. How, where and when data collection, data analysis, data presentation and interpretation take place are all key questions in a mixed method research design. There is vast methodological choice.

A mixed methods approach to small charity accountability research could take many forms, possibilities include: a questionnaire containing both quantitative and qualitative questions, a quantitative questionnaire and qualitative interview, a quantitative analysis of charity financial reports and qualitative focus group. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012) and Bryman (2017) summarise many of the reasons that justify a mixed methods design. A single method (the

method itself) may dictate the findings and produce limited or narrow results; whilst mixed methods may allow for triangulation, provide diversity of views and data, generate more complete knowledge, or provide answers that a single method previously failed to provide. Importantly, mixed methods compliment or support each other e.g., one method can be used to facilitate, explain, clarify, confirm, and enhance results of the other. For these reasons a mixed methods research design is attractive for this study of small charity accountability.

As suggested, there are several ways to integrate or mix quantitative and qualitative methods. At one extreme, mixed method research can be fully integrated e.g., both quantitative and qualitative data are collected, analysed, interpreted, and presented simultaneously or concurrently. Alternatively, the research can be conducted in distinct quantitative and qualitative stages, commonly referred to as partially integrated mixed methods research. This study will favour the use of a sequential or two-phase research design. This affords flexibility or opportunity to adapt a second phase in response to findings from the preceding phase one, and as stated previously, can be used to explain, clarify, confirm, or enhance the findings.

This design uses quantitative data (with some limited qualitative data) in the first phase, followed by a more detailed qualitative study of several cases or participants. To begin with, and in line with the research objectives, this study will begin with an introductory quantitative phase in attempt to describe aspects of small charity accountability. This will be followed by a substantial qualitative phase to explain and explore aspects of small charity accountability in more detail. This implies a descripto-explanatory type study, although phase two has an exploratory element, where an in-depth understanding of participant perspectives, attitudes and behaviours will be sought. In summary, the initial phase of research will understandably be descriptive in nature, whereas the main qualitative phase of research will offer richer explanation and exploration of the issues.

Thus, diverse designs are feasible in the study of small charity accountability, but ultimately the research question and objectives should dictate the selection of a particular research design. Several academics provide guidance in this selection process (Creswell, 2009; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2006; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2010). Creswell and Plano Clark (2010) provide a concise summary of decisions or steps to be undertaken, namely: establishing the degree of interaction between quantitative and qualitative (1), prioritising quantitative or qualitative (2), determining the timings of quantitative and qualitative (3), and deciding how and where to mix quantitative and qualitative (4). Drawing upon the notational system established by Morse (1991) and Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), a summary of the full range of mixed method groupings (4) and typologies (9) are as follows:

1. Equivalent status/simultaneous design: QUAL + QUAN (1)
2. Equivalent status/sequential design: QUAL -> QUAN; QUAN -> QUAL (2)
3. Dominant/simultaneous design: QUAL + quan; QUAN + qual (2)
4. Dominant/sequential design:
qual -> QUAN; QUAL -> quan; quan -> QUAL; QUAN -> qual (4)

Where + indicates simultaneous design; -> indicates sequential design

Where Uppercase represents dominant; Lowercase represents supportive

In conclusion, the research design chosen is a sequential two-phase mixed method research design, prioritising a dominant phase two qualitative method preceded by a supportive or complementary first phase quantitative method, or more succinctly: **quan -> QUAL**.

3.3 Phase one 'Pre-interview Questionnaire'

3.3.1 Overview

The survey strategy for phase one of the research design will use an online, self-completed, questionnaire. Robson (2011) as cited in Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) suggests that the questionnaire is well suited to standardised questions, but care must be taken to ensure these questions are clear and unambiguous to all respondents. In fact, this understanding between respondent and researcher must work both ways, since researcher must interpret data in the way intended by the respondent. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) suggest that a questionnaire requires careful planning beforehand given it is usually a one-shot opportunity at data collection. This requires careful design to capture all the data required to address the research questions and objectives. This process involves development of necessary investigative questions mapped against appropriate variables and the level of detail required of those variables.

As stated previously, the intention is for the research to be conducted in two phases, with the phase one questionnaire used to discover and describe organisational attitudes, opinions, and practices. Phase two is used to explore these findings in more detail, however, the questionnaire in phase one is still viable as a means of seeking some explanations within the data. Data is often explained through making comparisons and evaluating data relationships. This requires a rigorous process starting with review of literature and theories, to careful construction of research objectives and questions, and yet more care in the precise design of questionnaire to facilitate explanatory research (Gill and Johnson, 2010; Ghauri et al., 2020). The mixed-method design offers advantage in that explanatory research can be conducted over two phases. Relationships between dependent and independent variables for example can be analysed to an extent in phase one questionnaire data but the effect of more complex variable effects (multiple,

mediating, and moderating variables) could be explained and explored in phase two. The phase one questionnaire will primarily focus on closed questions, although carefully constructed open questions will be used sparingly to capture some more detailed personal responses. A variety of closed question type will be used including list and category questions (primarily to measure attributes and behaviours); ranking and rating/scale questions (primarily to measure attitudes or opinions).

3.3.2 Sampling approach

Moxham (2009) recognises the challenge of sampling in the small and micro third sector- suggesting that larger regulated organisations make for more consistent and straightforward research. With fewer resources and smaller pools of voluntary unpaid staff, the micro sector offers fewer potential participants who would be willing to participate in research projects. Non-probability sampling, and in particular volunteer sampling and its sub-sets of self-selection and snowball sampling, have been chosen for this study. Self-selection asks participants to volunteer or choose to take part; this is consistent and appropriate for the study of small voluntary organisations or charities (Sharma, 2017). In addition, the utilisation of snowball sampling seems appropriate where networks of organisations, support groups and third sector interfaces can encourage each other to participate in worthwhile sectoral research. These sampling approaches reduce level of time required to recruit participants and attract those with a willingness to provide insights into the issues being explored here. The study is transparent regards the weakness of non-probability sampling and potential for self-selecting bias. Furthermore, the study itself is conducted in two stages and is mixed method, so is not entirely quantitative in nature. The first stage data and findings will be supported, triangulated and followed-up with more in-depth second stage qualitative interviews.

The researcher reached out to gate-keeper contacts in Third Sector Interfaces (TSIs) for Scotland, Inspire Scotland, and the Institute for Voluntary Action Research (IVAR) to share researcher contact details with its members and encourage both participation in interviews and the 'pre-interview questionnaire' as well as wider sharing of the questionnaire through further contacts in the sector (see Appendix 1: Invitation to an interview). Willing interview participants were sent an online link to the 'pre-interview questionnaire'. The 'pre-interview questionnaire' achieved several aims: to introduce the study, provide explanations of potentially confusing terms and concepts around accountability, and to collect preliminary data to inform the follow-up interviews.

A total of 23 respondents contacted the researcher and expressed a willingness to take part in interviews. This number was deemed adequate to provide sufficient qualitative data to meet the research objectives and answer the research questions. In advance of interview, all 23 respondents completed the online 'pre-interview questionnaire', which produced interesting and valuable quantitative and qualitative data, and revealed some issues ripe for further exploration in an interview setting. As expected, the challenges of conducting research in the small and micro third sector compounded with ongoing challenges of Covid recovery, and the cost-of-living crisis, impacted the number of respondents willing and able to progress to the interview stage of research. Gatekeepers had previously advised that these ongoing challenges would indeed limit the response rates and participation of small charity actors in the research project. The final number of participants that would agree and progress to take part in interview numbered 13. However, during data collection and analysis it became clear that the project was reaching data saturation at around 10 to 11 participants. Certainly, no new issues and themes were identified beyond 12 or 13 participants. The researcher is happy that data saturation was reached and so mitigated the negative impact of a lower participation rate.

3.3.3 Questionnaire data analysis

The design and coding of the ‘pre-interview questionnaire’ questions dictate the level and types of statistics and statistical tests that are possible with the data. Given that the sample is small, then only basic descriptive statistics, counts and relative frequencies are applicable in the first stage of data analysis. A variety of charts are used in the research to provide a visual representation of the data and findings. Inferential statistics are not relevant since the first stage does not set out to conduct a large-scale quantitative study of the sector that would utilise probability sampling approaches. A limited thematic analysis is used to identify common themes and issues emerging from the limited qualitative responses of the questionnaire, these findings are represented with direct quotes. A more rigorous approach to thematic analysis of qualitative data is undertaken in the subsequent interview stage of the research.

3.4 Phase Two Qualitative Interviews

3.4.1 Overview

Ritchie et al., (2013) suggest that qualitative methods are appropriate in exploratory research where the aim is to uncover the perspectives and personal accounts of the research participants. To this end, phase two of the research design will employ qualitative methods to find rich explanations of practices and perceptions of the actors within the complex and dynamic setting of the charity sector. The research here builds upon previous studies that have framed voluntary sector and charity accountability research as an exploration of who, what, why and how of accountability. Flick (2014) suggests that qualitative methods and their interpretative perspective are appropriate when seeking answers to these questions of who, what, why and how, underpinned in this research by important concepts of stakeholders, accountability, and

transparency. Flick (2014) describes the ability of qualitative methods to facilitate a deep interpreted understanding of how social actor participants make sense of such concepts within their social environments. Both Ritchie (2013) and Flick (2014) identify several specific methods and research tools to enable qualitative enquiry, namely: interviews, focus groups, case study and observations. To explore a variety of perspectives within a variety of sectoral contexts then interview or focus group were deemed appropriate for this study. Focus groups can encourage debate and conversation and through this can also enable development of collective group understandings (Bryman, 2004). However, interviews were deemed most appropriate as they would facilitate the most in-depth exploration of the issues and ensure confidentiality for potentially sensitive issues arising for small charities in discussion of accountability and transparency. In addition, individual interviews would better facilitate comparisons of accountability practice and perceptions between individual organisations (Ritchie et al., 2013). Overall, the interviews allowed important issues identified from the initial survey questionnaire stage to be explored in more detail, whilst being open to emergence of unexpected findings.

The interview stage is as previously stated interpretivist and inductive in nature. However, the mixed methods approach avoids the polarities of both positivism and interpretivism. Likewise, the research can be more accurately described as abductive, rather than simply inductive or deductive. Inductive approaches are said to build theory from observations; whilst deductive approaches are said to simply test theory. Ritchie (2013) suggests this is an oversimplification since theory underpins and pervades all stages of research. The interview phase is informed by both previous observations and theories so cannot be described as purely inductive, though it is open to finding new modified theories to explain accountability in unique settings. The interview stage is interpretivist in nature and acknowledges the influence of social constructionism where social actor interviewees actively construct their own knowledge.

3.4.2 Interview design and structure

Flick (2014) points to the strengths of interviews to gather context specific information that can support other methods. Interviews allow for a deep exploration of new fields and can help to develop an ordered understanding or theory for a research issue or phenomenon.

It is important to identify and select participants from each organisation who have knowledge and experience of the phenomenon under study, namely, the dynamics of accountability relationships. This encompasses their management of stakeholder relationships and skills and expertise in communication and sharing of information. Field specialists would normally be preferred since they have the requisite knowledge to answer and expand upon lines of enquiry. However, as previously stated, given the limited resource of small organisations, it was deemed appropriate to leverage the opinions and perspectives of experienced board members or committee members or charity managers i.e., small charity leaders. For such small and tight-nit organisations the board members, committee members and charity managers may take on numerous roles and responsibilities, so whilst not accountability experts or specialists, they have a wealth of valuable experience, perspectives, and insights. The level of expertise and knowledge of these organisational representatives is indeed part of the research investigation. In addition, Flick (2014) recommends that the interviewer has sufficient context specific knowledge and technical knowledge to guide the interview sessions. The interviewer's (researcher's) previous experience of developing and delivering financial management and budgeting courses for the sector provided the necessary background and experience to support exploration of the issues. These previous consultancy experiences naturally involved deep discussion of accountability challenges with course participants and were in fact the inspiration and motivation behind the research project. This alludes to the issue of researcher reflexivity, which is discussed elsewhere in the methodology chapter of the thesis.

Saunders et al. (2012) identifies structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews as research tools and approaches. Semi-structured interviews were deemed most appropriate to meet the research aims and objectives. The research has several clear objectives to meet as well as several thematic areas to address; this provides an outline structure to guide the interview. It would be advantageous if this structure were not entirely rigid, having flexibility to adapt to the needs of interviewee as they convey their understanding of thematic areas and phenomena (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The semi-structured interview is less constrained than the fixed questions of the structured interview since richer explanations can be uncovered from exploring wider thematic areas (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Both literature review and the first stage 'pre-interview questionnaire' findings led to further development of the research objectives and identification of important research themes for interview. These thematic areas included:

- The nature of stakeholder relationships for the organisation.
- The types of information prepared and shared by the organisation.
- The types of accountability mechanism employed by the organisation.
- Meeting the challenges of multiple stakeholder information needs with accountability mechanisms.

These thematic areas took the form of these more specific questions in the interviews (see Appendix 5: Semi-structured interview schedule):

1. Who are your stakeholders and how would you describe the relationships you have with them?
2. What types of information does your organisation prepare and share?
3. What are the challenges you face in producing information about your organisation?
4. What (accountability) mechanisms does the organisation use to share information?

5. What is the potential of (accountability) mechanisms to help or improve your information sharing and your relationships with stakeholders?

3.4.3 Preparing participants for interview

The interviewer was at hand to expand upon these questions to clarify concepts such as stakeholder, accountability, accountability mechanisms and wider connotations of information sharing. However, the interviews were part of a two-stage process, so participants had already considered the fundamental concepts and the issues at hand (see Appendix 2: Extract of ‘pre-interview questionnaire’). Participants were also provided with guidance prior to interview to allow them to prepare and be confident in addressing the areas that would be explored during interview (see Appendix 4: Interview preparation guide). The interviewer was also able to prompt interviewees to dig deeper and further explore the issues implied in the questions through further probing questions where required e.g., asking interviewees to consider which stakeholders were most important and challenging to them, asking why certain types of information were produced and for whom, asking about experiences of implementing mechanism and their usefulness, asking about the potential of different mechanisms to solve information sharing problems (see Appendix 5: Semi-structured interview schedule).

Recruitment of participants began in February 2022 and lasted until April 2022. As previously discussed, social media and gatekeepers for the sector were used to reach out and engage potential participants. During this period, respondents expressing an interest to take part in the study were directed to the online ‘pre-interview questionnaire’ to begin the first stage of data collection. The subsequent interview stage of research was arranged and conducted in the months of July and August 2022. Microsoft Teams was used to facilitate the online interviews, producing both a video and a draft transcription that were both used to produce a more accurate

and complete transcription of participant accounts. Interviews were scheduled to last for 1 hour, but the average time for an interview was around 1.5 hours, with all interviews conducted within 1 to 2 hours. Participants expressed enthusiasm for using extra time beyond their 1-hour slots where they felt that this was needed.

3.4.4 Thematic analysis of interview data

A thematic approach to analysis will be undertaken specifically to address the lived experiences of the participants. In terms of the transcription process, guidance for a basic transcription system as proposed by King et al. (2019) was considered. Contextual features e.g., tonality, physical and facial gestures are of particular importance when transcribing; these paralinguistic features should be incorporated in the transcription where there is possible impact on the meaning of the communication from participants. However, the video recordings of interviews provided a visual and audio record for use in transcription, ensuring that no contextual features were missed during the transcribing process. The purpose of the transcription is to produce an accurate account of what was said. To this end the transcriber did not attempt to tidy up natural conversational language e.g., to remove grammatical errors and mispronunciations; the transcriptions represent participant accounts verbatim without correction, edit or abridgement.

A theme involves making a choice about what to select, discard and how to interpret participants responses. A theme would usually be repeated across different participants and would mostly be distinct from other themes. King et al (2019, p.200) suggest that themes are: “recurrent and distinctive features of participant’s accounts, characterising particular perceptions and/or experiences, which the researcher sees as relevant to the research question.” The researcher must consider the balance of within-case and cross-case themes emerging from analysis of the data. Themes within individual case participants are important to recognise

unique firsthand experiences, and themes emerging across all participants are important to identify broad patterns. The research will focus on cross-case themes but will also draw attention to important within-case themes.

There would normally be a hierarchal relationship with main themes incorporating sub-themes. There can also be links between hierarchies or in fact we may have integrative themes that seem to sit across different hierarchies. Once more there is a balance to be struck between simplicity and complexity in developing a hierarchal structure; a simple structure is more palatable for the reader but may exclude the richness of data gleaned from the research. A thematic structure can take the form of a numbered list, or tree diagram or mind-map approach. The tree diagram approach is adopted for this research to best visualise the thematic structure and is presented in the findings chapter.

A basic system for thematic analysis, as proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006) and King et al (2019), is used in this research and is conducted as follows:

STAGE ONE: Descriptive Coding.

Identify the parts that are of interest from the participant transcript text. Highlight parts of the transcript that help in understanding participants' views and experiences as related to the topic, then write a brief comment indicating what is of interest. Produce short descriptive codes, staying close to the data, without interpretation or speculation at this point. Where there appears to be overlap between codes, these can be merged. Move on to next transcript and repeat- where a previous descriptive code is relevant then this is used again. The first stage is dynamic; the researcher will go back and re-code previous transcripts as coding progresses and develops.

STAGE TWO: Interpretive Coding.

We now move from describing to interpreting. This would normally involve pulling together descriptive codes that share common meaning into a larger encompassing interpretive code.

Situations where descriptive codes fit too many interpretive codes are avoided- clearer definitions are required here. Specific theoretical frameworks are not applied at this stage since this can limit the analysis. Again, this process is repeated for subsequent transcripts and then interpretive codes are revised/redefined where appropriate for previous transcripts, in attempt to capture all meaning from the texts. The research objectives and questions are considered to provide necessary focus for this stage.

STAGE THREE: Identify overarching Themes.

Overarching themes are built from the interpretive themes/codes- at this stage the researcher can draw upon relevant underpinning theories. Overarching themes are restricted as far as possible e.g., between two and five themes only. Themes are only be identified where they apply to sizeable number or proportion of cases- although there can be value in identifying themes for just a few cases too (over-arching themes are cross case). A diagram is presented showing the hierarchy of overarching theme to interpretive codes to descriptive codes, for each over-arching theme (King et al., 2019)

3.4.5 Assessing the quality of the analysis

In qualitative research there is no general agreement over the criteria to apply in assessing quality of research and data analysis. One position would be to apply the same criteria of quantitative research e.g., reliability and validity, whereas another position would argue for a distinct set of criteria for qualitative research. LeCompte and Goetz (1982) suggest that qualitative research has a firm footing regards validity given its attention to context and its method of concept development through careful attention to the data. Reliability proves to be a more troublesome criteria for qualitative research since researcher influence negates the possibility of replications, even when closely following methodology (King et al, 2019). The

work here follows the guidance offered by Yardley (2008) as cited in King et al (2019), offering four criteria or principles to consider in overall appraisal of the quality of the research and data analysis. Firstly, the researcher demonstrates sensitivity to the context of each charity and charity actor both during the interview process and post-interview during data analysis and write-up. This sensitivity to context includes an appreciation of the social purpose and activities of small charities and the sensitivity of the issues and charity information around their beneficiaries. Secondly, the research demonstrates commitment and rigour to the research process, particularly the engagement with a large volume of qualitative interview data that is collected, presented, and analysed in detail and depth. Thirdly, the research is coherent and transparent in that the thesis has a logical and coherent flow of activity through the thesis chapters and powerful arguments and conclusions are made based on the findings. The research also demonstrates reflexivity on the part of the researcher since reflections are made on the role and influence of the researcher on the entire research process. Finally, the researcher would argue strongly that the research findings or outcomes will have significant impact and importance for the small charity sector. The value of the work is clearly demonstrated by the engagement with small charities and small charity support organisations such as TSIs, who have requested a brief on the findings and recommendations of the research to inform their practice.

3.5 Reflexivity and Ethics

Overall, the researcher must acknowledge that both participants and researcher actively constructed and jointly directed the conversations to determine understandings and knowledge of small charity accountabilities (Bryman, 2004). Researcher interest in the subject of small charity accountability began several years ago whilst delivering short courses in financial

management, in a professional capacity, for the TSI Engage Renfrewshire. Certainly, the researcher has experience and previous knowledge of some of the challenges and issues facing small charities, particularly in relation to financial responsibilities and financial accountability in the sector. This could be considered a disadvantage in terms of the loss of objectivity and the unintentional biases brought to the research by the researcher. Despite the inability of qualitative research to be completely subjective and value free, I have strived to be reflexive regards the role and influence of the researcher at the various stages of the research. Indeed, I acknowledge that I come to the research with preconceptions around the challenges facing small charities and that these preconceptions influenced the research aims, objectives and questions. Within the interview setting I must also appreciate that previously held beliefs and personal opinions likely had an influence on the direction of conversation and therefore the participant accounts and its qualitative data. It must also be conceded that my own personal views and past experiences influenced the data analysis that was undertaken and the conclusions that were drawn. Thus, I have taken time to reflect on my own personal role in influencing and shaping every stage of the research project. However, the researcher agrees with Unluer (2012) that the informed perspectives of both researcher and participant can produce more balanced accounts and that there are benefits if the researcher understands the culture of the researched. In addition, the knowledge and expertise of the researcher created trust between researcher and participants (Bryman, 2004), which led to sharing of rich participant accounts of their experiences. After interview, all participants commented favourably on the value of the interview process and the time it had afforded them to reflect on these critical issues for their charities.

Following the University of the West of Scotland ethical review procedures, approval was sought from the Business and Creative Industries School Ethics Committee (SEC) prior to data collection. In support of the application, the SEC was provided with draft copies of the research

instruments i.e., questionnaire and interview schedule, a summary of the research aims and methodology, and copies of participant consent forms and information sheets. An assessment of the ethical risks for the project led to the decision to employ Google Survey tool for online questionnaire and Microsoft Teams software for online interviews. This approach to interviews was consistent with the approach to formal meetings already established for the individuals in their roles within their organisations. Participants were assured of their anonymity prior to both the 'pre-interview questionnaire' and the interviews, they were informed that they would be identified by role and type of organisation only. Similarly, participants were assured that their data would be protected and confidential as per the requirements of the SEC ethics application and approval. Participants agreed to recordings and were informed that these would be deleted after completion of transcriptions. The participants were reminded that their participation was voluntary, and that they could withdraw at any point prior to or during the questionnaire or interviews. Participants gave their informed consent to take part willingly and voluntarily in a study that was relevant to their knowledge and experiences of the small charity sector. The SEC granted ethics approval on the 18th November 2021 prior to the collection of data from participants (see Appendix 6: Ethics Approval Letter).

Chapter 4: 'Pre-Interview Questionnaire' Data and Findings

This chapter presents the findings from the 'pre-interview questionnaire', which is the first stage of the mixed-method research. A total of twenty-three respondents initially volunteered to take part in an interview and were invited to complete a pre-interview questionnaire. The pre-interview questionnaire was used to confirm participant willingness to take part in the study and to introduce and explain key concepts and terms pertinent to the area of research. The short questionnaire was also used to collect some basic quantitative and qualitative data to identify and confirm areas for further in-depth investigation in an interview setting. The data here can also be triangulated to some extent with the interview data; of the twenty-three respondents, thirteen progressed to take part in the interview.

4.1 Demographics

Figure 3: Charity area of activity

Each charity sub-sector had representation amongst the initial cohort of respondents (23). All sub-sector areas above were represented in the final cohort of interview participants (13), with exception of 'Environment and Animals'.

Figure 4: Age of organisation

What is the age of your organisation?

23 responses

The respondent data for age indicates that new or early-stage charities will not be represented in the data. This means that the study avoids the complications associated with establishing operational systems, including information and accountability processes, for early-stage organisations and draws upon experienced participants and established organisations.

Figure 5: Sources of finance

What are your sources of finance?

23 responses

The data shows that the initial cohort of responding charities have various sources of finance. Grants (82.6%), Donations (60.9%), and Fundraising Events (52.2%) account for most finance sources, whilst Membership funded charities (34.8%) are also well represented in the sample. The data shows that most respondents will reflect upon their accountability to these key funding groups. Other sources of finance are not as significant for the cohort of respondents.

4.2 Accountability questions

Participants were provided firstly with a brief definition and explanation of the term and concept of accountability (see Appendix 2: Extract of ‘Pre-interview questionnaire’ guidance).

The following Likert scale questions were used to collect preliminary data on respondent perceptions of their organisation’s understanding of accountability.

Figure 6: Understanding of who we are accountable to

The data indicates a perception amongst 100% of respondents that they either strongly agree (78.3%) or agree (21.7%) that they have a clear understanding of who they are accountable to.

Figure 7: Understanding of what things we are accountable for

Our organisation has a clear understanding of what things we are accountable for.

23 responses

The data indicates a perception amongst 100% of respondents that they either strongly agree (82.6%) or agree (17.4%) that they have a clear understanding of what they are accountable for.

Figure 8: Why it is accountable to some parties and not to others

Our organisation has carefully considered why it is accountable to some parties and not to others.

23 responses

The data indicates that 67.2% of respondents either strongly agree or agree that their organisation carefully considers the reasons why it is accountable to certain parties. The data indicates that 34.8% of respondents are uncertain whether their organisation carefully considers its accountability to certain parties.

The data indicates confidence amongst respondents that their charities understand their basic accountability (who and what), whereas there is considerable doubt evident when respondents were asked if their charities consider the reasons why they are accountable. This warrants further investigation in the following interview stage of research.

4.3 Stakeholder questions

Participants were provided with a brief definition and explanation of the concept of a charity stakeholder (see Appendix 2).

The following Likert and List style questions were used to gather data on respondent's basic perceptions of their charity's stakeholders. This section was also followed by a short qualitative question to identify issues and challenges for the cohort.

Figure 9: Identify our organisation's stakeholders

The data indicates that almost all respondents (95.6%) either strongly agree (65.2%) or agree (30.4%) that they can identify their stakeholders. One respondent disagreed with this statement.

Figure 10: Identify our stakeholder's information needs

We can identify our stakeholder's information needs.

23 responses

The data shows that 56.5% of respondents strongly agreed and 26.1% agreed that they can identify stakeholder information needs. 13% of respondents were uncertain of their charity's ability to identify stakeholder information needs. 1 respondent disagreed with the statement.

The data shows that most charities in the sample are confident that they can identify stakeholder information needs (82.6%), but those that are uncertain or disagree are not insignificant (17.3%).

Figure 11: Indicate your stakeholders

The data shows that respondents identify a wide range stakeholder group. 87% of respondents recognise Board, Committee and Members as stakeholders and 82.6% of respondents recognise their Beneficiaries as stakeholders. 78.3% of respondents recognise their Grant providers and 78.3% recognise the Regulator as stakeholders. 73.9% of respondents recognise their staff or volunteers as stakeholders. The data here suggests that not all respondents and their charities hold the same definition of stakeholder (despite the researcher providing a definition as part of this questionnaire) since Board, Committee, Staff and Volunteers, Beneficiaries, and Regulator might be seen as obvious stakeholders for the whole sector. 47.8% of respondents identified their local community as a stakeholder and only 4.3% of respondents recognised both Support groups and Affiliated organisations as stakeholders.

The data here indicates that several stakeholder groups are under-appreciated or lack recognition from the cohort of respondents. Some stakeholder groups are obvious for charity existence e.g., Board, Staff, Beneficiaries and Regulator, whilst others seem essential to charity survival and success e.g., local community and sector support groups. The findings here warrant further investigation in the interview stage of research.

Participants also had opportunity to provide brief comments on the following question:

What are the issues and challenges you face in meeting information needs of your stakeholders?

“We provide information which some stakeholders do not understand(accounts).”

“Time and volunteer availability.”

“As a small organisation we are not always set up to provide information in particular formats or in a particular way.”

“Multiple platforms for reaching stakeholders with information and not enough volunteers to manage the different platforms.”

“Making sure that the information is in plain English and accessible for all.”

“Demands on staff time to provide the inputs and to collate and present the information.”

“We have a diverse community with a small charity operating at national level, so it is challenging to identify needs and communicate effectively across the range of people that we interact with.”

“No challenges at present as robust reporting procedure templates are in place.”

“Digital capability.”

“The range of prospective info needs can be significant. Therefore, producing meaningful information within the capacity of a small org can be challenging.”

“Providing different levels of information to different stakeholders. Also, as we work in an area of deprivation, we cannot publicly provide information that may be insensitive to the community we work with.”

“Because we have a wide range of stakeholders who all have their own reporting systems, duplication and repetition of information can be challenging and time consuming.”

“There is usually no one size fits all when it comes to reporting to funders meaning that at times you report the same information several different ways.”

The findings indicate that the sample of small charities find it difficult to identify and serve different stakeholder needs including use of different platforms and formats for sharing information. The qualitative data also indicates that resource constraints of time, money and people are an issue when trying to satisfy various stakeholder information needs. Accessibility and understanding of information represent a further challenge to meeting the various requirements of different stakeholder groups. One respondent expressed confidence in robust financial processes to serve stakeholder needs. The challenges and issues raised here are worthy of further in-depth exploration in the interview stage.

4.4 Accountability mechanisms questions

The participants were provided with a brief definition and explanation of the concept of accountability mechanisms (see Appendix 2).

The following List and Matrix style questions asked respondents to identify the accountability mechanisms used by their charities and the types of information shared through each mechanism. A qualitative question was used to collect participant final comments on issues and challenges around use and selection of accountability mechanisms.

Figure 12: Indicate the accountability mechanisms

The data shows that the sample of small charities employ a wide range of accountability mechanisms. All respondents indicated Website/social media and Board/Committee meetings as accountability mechanisms used by their charities. 91.3% of respondents indicated use of the Annual Report, 78.3% indicated use of Newsletters, and 78.3% indicated use of AGM. 73.9% of respondents indicated that they had direct communications with individual stakeholders. Interestingly, the Annual Report and AGM are not recognised by all respondents as accountability mechanisms that they use, despite these being mandatory for registered charities; this could be due to interpretation of what constitutes an accountability mechanism. Collectively the data shows that the charities employ a mix of public (e.g., annual report, website) and private (e.g., board meetings, direct

communications) mechanisms for both internal and external accountability. However, it is not clear from the data which mechanisms are strictly public or private (e.g., newsletter, AGM).

Other interesting data show that 52.2% of sample charities allow stakeholders to observe or participate as a mechanism of accountability, 43.5% consult with their beneficiaries, and 34.8% indicate that they have meetings open to the public. The data here indicates that some charities are making use of a wider range of accountability mechanisms to engage stakeholders and discharge their accountability. The reasons behind the use or under-use of these accountability mechanisms warrants further investigation in the subsequent interview stage of research.

Figure 13: Indicate the type(s) of information shared

Identify the type(s) of information shared

The charts above show the distribution of distinct types of data disclosed through each accountability mechanism. Respondents were given the choice of six different data types identified in the charity accountability literature as being important for transparency: financial, output, impact, mission, management, narrative (explanations). Participants were also provided with short definitions and explanations of the data types. The findings demonstrate that both the Annual Report and Board/Committee meetings are the most transparent accountability mechanisms, closely followed by the AGM. Distributions of data type are broadly similar,

although unsurprisingly the Annual Report prioritises financial data. Overall, the findings show that that charities have further scope to be more transparent across the different data types.

Other interesting data show that Newsletters and Website/social media prioritise mission, impact, and narratives, with less emphasis on financials. Likewise, those charities utilising Meetings open to the public or Consultation with beneficiaries as mechanisms do not prioritise financial data, but outputs, impact and mission information are emphasised. Stakeholder observation/participation and Direct communications both show reasonably uniform distributions- although Direct communication has priority for narratives. Those charities indicating that they consult with beneficiaries prioritise outputs, impact, and mission related information. Those charities Producing plans show a uniform distribution of data type.

It is unclear from the data to what extent charities are carefully considering the types of data that can be shared with stakeholders through different accountability mechanisms. The data could be interpreted in several ways. One interpretation is that charities are failing to be transparent since they fail to share adequate types of information through several of their mechanisms. Another interpretation is that charities are enhancing transparency by tailoring the types of information it shares through different mechanisms to meet stakeholder needs. This issue of accountability mechanisms and their transparency are worthy of further investigation in the interview stage of research.

Participants also had opportunity to provide brief comments on the following question:

What are the issues and challenges you face in selecting and using accountability mechanisms?

“Use what stakeholders request.”

“The feeling that no one reads the information we do provide - particularly service users. It is difficult to do more when you struggle to find time for what you do need to do.”

“Ensuring all stakeholders informed.”

“Making sure we use the correct one to give the regulators, funders and members the correct information when we only have 2 staff members whose time is limited”.

“Cost/benefit - balancing what is ideal with what is practical.”

“People and time. Either in the recording of info during the processes or time at the time of collation, assessing and then constructing reports.”

“No issues at present as reporting procedure templates are clearly documented and implemented.”

“Time and skills of board members who are all volunteers.”

“In demonstrating and meeting our accountability to stakeholders we need to address their specific needs. This requires considerable time and effort in understanding these needs, determining how we address them and then to put in place appropriate mechanisms.”

“Formal/regulatory driven mechanisms (e.g., annual report and accounts) often feel less valuable in terms of the contribution these processes make to demonstrating the impact of our work (e.g., to funders and beneficiaries).”

“Time and money really. We try to work smart, not duplicate, we would like to present information to the fullest, but we have no time or money to pay for this to be done.”

The qualitative responses indicate that the resources of time, money and people are limiting or restricting the accountability mechanisms used by small charities; there is a cost/benefit trade-off. The data shows that the sample of respondents are concerned at the lack of interest from stakeholders in their reports and disclosures and the ability of formal/regulatory mechanisms to demonstrate charity impact. The data also highlights that some charities struggle to understand various stakeholder needs and find the appropriate accountability mechanisms. One respondent indicated that reporting procedures and templates are available for use to ease the burden on the charity and one respondent indicated that the charity simply uses the mechanism that stakeholders request. The attitudes and behaviours around accountability mechanisms warrant further exploration in the interview stage of research.

4.5 Summary

The preliminary data shows that charities believe that they understand to whom they are accountable and for what they are accountable i.e., they can differentiate and identify stakeholders and their information needs. However, there is straightforward evidence that whilst charities may report that they understand to whom they are accountable, and what they

are accountable for, they are less confident in conceptualising or understanding why they are accountable. A deeper interrogation specifically around stakeholders reveals that not all charities recognise what would seem to be obvious stakeholder groups for organisations in the charitable sector, and data also highlights that there are indeed difficulties for some charities in identifying stakeholder needs. The data shows that resources of time, money and people place significant constraints on a small charity's ability to meet the needs of various stakeholder groups. The data shows that, overall, there are a wide range of information dissemination or accountability mechanisms employed by organisations in the small charity sector. Whilst some accountability mechanisms are common: social media, board meetings, annual reports, AGMs, direct communications; the data suggests that other mechanisms are under-used in the sector: open meetings, consultations, and participation opportunities.

The pre-interview questionnaire provides a mix of valuable quantitative and qualitative data to inform the line of enquiry in the next stage of research, the qualitative interview stage. In summary, areas identified for further in-depth investigation include charity understanding of accountability, challenges of identifying and meeting stakeholder information needs, issues around the selection and implementation of effective and transparent accountability mechanisms.

Chapter 5: Interviews Data and Findings

This chapter presents the findings from the second stage of research i.e., the qualitative interviews. The chapter contains two sub-chapters, which present the participant accounts within their over-arching themes and overall thematic structures. The themes emerged from analysis of the qualitative interview data in three stages of thematic analysis as outlined in the methodology.

An overview of the participants, their roles and charities are provided in Appendix 3. In addition, Appendix 7 contains findings from a third over-arching theme: Need to change & Find solutions. These findings are supplementary to the main findings and do not relate specifically to the research objectives. However, the findings here contribute considerable evidence to inform the recommendations which are made for the small charity sector within the closing conclusions and recommendations chapter. Further reference to Appendix 7 is made within the conclusions and recommendations chapter.

5.1 OVER-ARCHING THEME 1: Perceptions of Accountability

This over-arching theme addresses the issue of participant perceptions of the concept of accountability: what it means to them and what they feel it means to their colleagues and the organisation more widely. This can include both personal accountabilities and a collective organisational accountability. This perception of accountability includes the who, what and why of accountability: to whom are they accountable, for what are they accountable, and why is there a perceived accountability. Within these perceptions participants will often identify and distinguish between internal accountabilities and external accountabilities. In summary, the data analysis i.e., thematic analysis stage of the research found that the over-arching theme of ‘perceptions of accountability’ captured the three interpretive sub-themes of ‘identifying

external accountability’, ‘identifying internal accountability’, and ‘understanding accountability’. At the preceding or subordinate descriptive level, the identification of descriptive themes recognised that ‘identifying external accountability’ encompassed the descriptive accounts of accountability ‘to the funders and regulators’ and ‘to the beneficiaries, partners and community’. The sub-theme of ‘identifying internal accountability’ emerged as capturing the descriptive accounts of accountability ‘to the mission’, and ‘to the board, staff and parental structure’. The interpretive sub-theme of ‘understanding accountability’ captured more general participant accounts of their understanding of terms and concepts, their explanations of what and why they are accountable, and the description of resource constraint impact. The resulting thematic structure emerged from a bottom-up process of defining low-level descriptive themes, captured by higher-level abstraction for interpretive themes, and finally drawing upon some aspects of literature to arrive at the over-arching theme.

Figure 14: Thematic structure 'Perceptions of Accountability'

Source: Author

5.1.1 Identifying External Accountability

After relaying the role and accountability of the board for internal governance and control participant 1 explained that they were also accountable to their fund providers, comprising government, local authorities, and partnerships. In terms of further external accountability participant 1 acknowledged a responsibility to the regulator OSCR but stated that their main responsibility was to the funders. Going further participant 1 then identified that they were also responsible and accountable to their beneficiaries. When asked further about the idea of accountability participant 1 again pointed to the importance of funders and meeting their requirements.

Participant 2 suggested that accountability to funders was and is obvious.

Participant 3 stated that they had an obvious accountability to OSCR to provide their accounts and went on to add that they were accountable to those that provided their finance, needing to provide accounts to show that they were doing what they said they would do, and providing the details of how this was done. It was explained that external accountability was about meeting external expectations, to provide what was asked for; participant 3 thought that they didn't just do the minimum but emphasised doing what was needed:

And then for the external, it's more about what they are expecting from us. So, they can set out the stall in terms of what they're looking for and we do that. I mean, I don't think we just do the bare minimum, but we certainly do what's needed (Participant 3).

Participant 4 believes that there is an accountability to funders to give them an understanding of their impact on the community, and that the level of detail in the information should vary in line with the size of the funding. Participant 4 continued by explaining that they had accountability to their clients or service users whom they worked with in extreme situations and would share information with. It was also explained that they had accountability to their

legal advisors and felt that they should hold themselves accountable to stakeholder partners that help inform their practice.

Participant 6 identifies an internal accountability to their strategy, values, and mission; it was further explained that when undertaking work in the community, the mission is a reference point and staff are reminded to have focus on mission and objectives:

And also, our strategy or our values and our vision and our mission. So, we always try to come back to that. So, if we're doing something, we think maybe, wait a minute, is that what we set out to do? And if it's not, because when you're working in the community there's lots that we could do, there's lots that we know needs done, but we need to sometimes just be able to say to staff, you know, stay focussed on your mission and your objectives (Participant 6).

Participant 6 elaborated further by stating that the board was also in place to ensure that the charity and its staff were focussed on the mission and the funding purpose. There was a strong belief that organisations should be accountable in this way, like theirs is. Participant 6 commented that the charity had been approached by other bodies to get involved in wider activities, but they made the decision that they could not be all things to all people and took a purposeful step back. In wrapping up, the point was made that although there remained a danger of drifting away from priorities and objectives, it was her experience that this was more problematic in larger geographically spread-out charities.

Participant 7 perceived funders and finance as their big area of accountability, stating that they were accountable to the money that is given for their projects. They must explain to their funders how money has been spent and must indicate this in their applications. Participant 7 supposes that accountability arises when they apply for funding and give specific details about what they plan to do with the funds:

I suppose the big one is finance and that is linked to I suppose intrinsically to our funders. So, we are accountable to the money that they give us to run the project basically. So, at the end of each funding period, we have to kind of go back and say, well you gave us 50 grand and this is how it's been spent. And I suppose the accountability for that links to when you apply for funding, you have to be very specific about what you plan to do with that funding. You are very much accountable as to have you spent in the way you said you would when you applied for it. And if you haven't, then why haven't you? (Participant 7)

The main accountability identified by participant 7 was accountability to funders for impact, outcomes and any statistics that were related to this.

Participant 8 recognised an accountability to auditor and OSCR as part of the regulatory process.

Participant 10 began by explaining that they had accountability to young people and the people they serve; this by extension also included an accountability to their parents. It was pointed out that the young people and parents paid a member subscription so there was an accountability for the scouting activities that were undertaken with these funds. Participant 10 felt there was an accountability to the parents because of the trust that was shown in them to take subscription funds and use it for the benefit of the young people:

So, I suppose for me we are accountable first to the young people in the scout group to give them activities that we feel they need to build them up. Then accountable to the parents because they are trusting us with their young people, and they're also trusting us that we are going to take any money that they gave us to help benefit the young people. And that's the key thing for me is that we make some money some years, we

lose money other years, but my prime responsibility is to show that the money that they're investing towards their young people has been used properly (Participant 10).

Participant 10 felt that he became accountable when funders would ask where money had been spent; this involved showing the accounting books and filling in funding report forms.

Participant 11 began by recognising an external financial accountability to the regulator OSCR, explaining that they were answerable to OSCR because of the statutory regulatory requirement. It was then explained that they were accountable to trust funds to provide details of what money was spent on and for reaching goals and targets. The process of preparing reports for this was described as time-consuming, tedious, and boring. However, participant 11 felt an accountability to the membership to do what they asked them to do; this accountability to members was seen as more important than accountability to funders and regulators.

Participant 12 recognised an accountability and responsibility to the community for how money was spent since the money was raised on their behalf. In addition, it was stated that they have responsibility to the community and to the public since they held some public funds. Later it was explained that they were trying to be accountable to the media to share their achievements and stories.

Participant 13 pointed to their ability to inform members of their different sources of finance, they were also able to tell members where that money was spent such as on maintenance and running costs. They also felt it was important to explain to the church family where surplus funds at the end of each year would go. Participant 13 expressed a strong belief that there were clear benefits of being self-funded, meaning that they had no external ties or accountability obligations to funders that they had to meet:

We would never take money from any other organisation. We are self-funded in that way and that keeps us, it means there are no ties on us. There's no obligations that we

have to meet for some others, no rules, or regulations, we keep ourselves free. So yeah, we're self-funded in that way (Participant 13).

5.1.2 Identifying Internal Accountability

When asked to explain what accountability meant to him and his organisation, participant 1 began by identifying the responsibility and accountability of the board for internal governance and control. As a final thought regards accountability and responsibilities, participant 1 added that employees were a group that they were accountable to, for looking after their well-being and interest. Participant 1 identified a clear responsibility to their mission and part of this was to consider the flexibility and scope of the constitution to be inclusive of a wider range of beneficiaries.

Participant 2 raised the issue of a multi-generational staff, where several generations of staff and volunteers may work for the same organisation. It was further explained that many organisations were now realising that they had to be responsible and accountable to multiple generations, generations that had different needs since they understood the world differently. The participant believed organisations were having difficulty in understanding and solving this accountability issue:

Suddenly people woke up to the fact that, oh my goodness, we do have multiple generations working for us, so you have to be accountable to those different generations because they understand the world differently. They communicate differently and across those four generations. And so that's been quite a complex landscape for some organisations to get their head around in terms of accountability (Participant 2).

The issue of internal board accountability for governance was raised by Participant 2. The suggestion was that boards should be more governance focussed with a need for regular monitoring and improvement, otherwise issues that may arise would have very severe consequences. The participant then went on to explain that boards should move away from involvement in operations to focus on governance. It was suggested that there was a need to educate boards on their roles, accountability for how an organisation is run, and their accountability for governance:

So, are you more inclined to do some regular maintenance around, you know, how well is the organisation running? Are we complying with all the policies, and do we know we are complying with them, and we keep the policies up to date in terms of regulation, all that stuff. It's educating board members to realise they are accountable for knowing all of that is running well (Participant 2).

It was then suggested that board accountability for governance could be set out using a governance timetable along the lines of the Scottish government's code of good governance.

Participant 3 stated that they had an obvious internal accountability to their parent organisation and the remit of their constitution that dictated how their resources of time and money would be used. The national body would require information around how they were following the rules, and the annual report was necessary for them to keep their affiliation. It was explained that it was the committee that ultimately decided how resources were used and what the organisation would engage with. It was later explained that everything would be minuted to monitor consistency. In terms of internal responsibility as accountability, it was the treasurer and secretary that would do this background handling of membership data and the paperwork and reporting.

It was explained that organisation accountability involved high standard accountability to their legal advisors; this accountability was an issue that was brought to the board for discussion, and it was felt that these accountability responsibilities ought to be spread or shared across both the organisation and its board. It was supposed that this was part of risk management and good governance. Participant 4 stated that the board were excellent people doing a very good job but wanted them to be more proactive in how they weighed up organisational versus individual accountabilities. Participant 4 thought that accountabilities were not discussed enough between the charity and its board, going on to suggest that this was perhaps due to fear on the part of the board in having an accountability connected to such big issues:

I mean, I think the accountabilities are not discussed as often as they should be. I think sometimes a board are a little bit afraid of it and I get that because it's such a gravitas piece of work we're doing sometimes. But I think that you do feel that weight of accountability and getting it right, you know, and that pressure does take its toll, and it did, you know, it was a real struggle during lockdown cause the increase in particular types of things just were significant (Participant 4).

Participant 5 connected the responsibilities of secretaries for minute taking with internal accountability; this she believed was the most important role within the board to ensure that detailed and accurate minute taking was done to capture information about decision-making. The board also has responsibility for oversight to make sure that policies were in place and being followed. Furthermore, participant 5 added that the board should not get involved in the operational side of charities, mostly because they did not understand the charity operations, and that this would be disliked by the charity itself:

So, that's the board's responsibility, you know, it's that oversight. So, use your eyes and so you're seeing everything that's going on but don't interfere because you don't

know what you're doing. Yeah, organisations hate it when their trustees actually start doing the doing, because they'll get it wrong (Participant 5).

Participant 6 identified an internal accountability to their strategy, values, and mission. It was further explained that when undertaking work in the community, the mission is a reference point and staff are reminded to have focus on mission and objectives:

And also, our strategy or our values and our vision and our mission. So, we always try to come back to that. So, if we're doing something, we think maybe, wait a minute, is that what we set out to do? And if it's not, because when you're working in the community there's lots that we could do, there's lots that we know needs done, but we need to sometimes just be able to say to staff, you know, stay focussed on your mission and your objectives (Participant 6).

Participant 6 elaborated further by stating that the board was also in place to ensure that the charity and its staff were focussed on the mission and the funding purpose. There was a strong belief that organisations should be accountable in this way, like theirs is. Participant 6 commented that the charity had been approached by other bodies to get involved in wider activities, but they made the decision that they could not be all things to all people and took a purposeful step back. In wrapping up, the point was made that although there remained a danger of drifting away from priorities and objectives, it was her experience that this was more problematic in larger geographically spread-out charities.

Participant 7 identified an accountability to the parent organisation and a need to share financial information with them. Accountability to their community and service users was seen as essential, explaining the need to demonstrate their progress towards the community activities that were requested of them. Accountability to the community was seen as an aspect of accountability that could be misunderstood for their organisation.

Participant 8 stated that the charity, largely through the personal accountability for her role as treasurer, has an accountability for income and monetary matters such as member subscriptions and fundraising. The treasurer has responsibility for these monetary aspects; whilst the other committee members were more concerned about the activities and community involvement. Participant 8 described the internal accountability processes, beginning with accountability of the internal scouting groups to provide their own financial accounts to the treasurer, and for the treasurer to then collate, prepare final accounts for audit and then external publication to the regulator, OSCR. It was explained that the accounts were also submitted to the main scout parent since they were accountable to them too.

Participant 9 explained that there is an internal accountability to the charity mission and believes that there is responsibility to wind up the charity if not adhering to the mission; he felt that this was an area of misunderstanding within the charity. Some activities were good, but the charity failed to look at their actual purpose and stakeholders involved. There were disagreements on the board regards following the charity mission, despite some good things being done by the charity:

But yeah, I think there's a great responsibility there and similarly if that's not being done you've got responsibility to wind the thing up. You know, if it isn't doing, and that's kind of one of the things that some of my colleagues couldn't understand, there was a thought that doing anything in any way, as long as it was for the community, was a good thing. Not necessarily. It might be a good thing for individuals or groups, but there is a mission, and I felt that very strongly and it wasn't shared by some of the other members of the board I'm afraid to say (Participant 9).

Participant 9 expressed a belief that “doing good stuff” was important but explained that he became increasingly frustrated with the disagreements on the board around this and indeed how

this should be communicated. He later added that he believed people were more concerned with pursuit of personal preferences over pursuit of the charity mission, again he explained that this was a source of great frustration. Participant 9 then began to provide details of other areas of concern around internal accountability, pointing to his frustration and anger at the lack of management accounts provision for internal accountability and therefore to facilitate wider accountability. He explained that he often had to sign-off accounts as the chair, despite being dissatisfied with the level of financial detailed, indeed he felt he was coerced into this. There was a belief that the chief executive was keeping data and information to themselves and didn't share with the board. This led to questions around the motives of the paid chief executive who he felt was increasing wages without proper disclosure:

If you can't see, you know, regular accounts of where money is coming from and going to, how on Earth can you possibly be accountable to yourself or anybody else? Uh, there was sort of coercive control type arrangements, you know, the chair had to sign the annual accounts, but they gave no detail, you couldn't really work out exactly where money had gone and for what. You know, who was getting paid what for what? It was something that, you know, in a situation like that where you've got a very powerful employed person who's there every day and it's their livelihood and who's keen to make their livelihood even better, like for example paying themselves pay increases (Participant 9).

Participant 9 then went on to add that he felt he was identified as a troublemaker for asking for detailed accounts or financial accountability to the board. Participant 9 felt strongly that accountability requires a foundation of good basic governance to be effective in helping the community. In summing up his experience of serving on the board of the charity participant 9 said that this was a case of a failure in accountability and governance.

Participant 10 described the process of how financial accounts and financial accountability would move up the levels of the organisations; he seen a personal responsibility for accounts submitted to all levels of the organisation. This process of sharing accounts through the levels of the organisation he described as an explicit internal accountability.

In terms of internal accountability, participant 11 identified unexpected events as an area of accountability to be discussed within the organisation. Board meetings were identified as a platform for accountability where things that haven't worked or didn't go to plan could be discussed between board members. It was felt that internal accountability is about reporting all information back to the board, including negative aspects, so that everything was open and transparent.

Participant 12 recounted occasions when she had witnessed organisations changing what they do to access funding opportunities. These charities were moving away from their charitable purpose to pursue the funds. Although she understood that these organisations were often delivering good services, she could see that this was not why the charities were set-up and they were guilty of mission drift:

And also, you get organisations, you see where, I mean what we call mission drift, where organisations have seen an opportunity to get some funding, which isn't quite exactly what they do, and they go get that funding and they deliver that. They deliver a great service and then something else comes up that isn't sort of, well it's further away, and they just lose the basic charitable purpose if you like. They're chasing the money all the time and it's not like they're not doing a great service and a great activity, but they're not doing what they were actually set up to do (Participant 12).

Participant 12 then expanded on this by explaining that she thought that too many organisations had skewed views of how important some social issues were and that they acted on this too quickly without taking time to think about their own objectives.

Participant 13 explained that they wished to be accountable to their members for how they use their money, and this was done through several mechanisms. An internal accountability towards staff was described in terms of providing them with the appropriate training that they deserved and that they expected.

5.1.3 Understanding Accountability

Participant 1 conveyed his understanding of accountability as being accountable for the performance of the organisation as it related to the strategy. There was also by extension an accountability here for how resources were being used to achieve their strategy and overall mission. In summarising accountability participant 1 recognised accountability as a responsibility, revealing his understanding of accountability as being for the impact of their operations and their governance and control of the organisation. When pushed further on the idea of accountability participant 1 thought that accountability wasn't a term that was used or discussed in the organisation, but they would however discuss the interests of different groups. Participant 1 later re-iterated the non-use of accountability terminology, but that accountability was the identification of responsibility to different groups:

I mean I don't think we would say we were accountable and it's not a term that we would use in terms of recognising our responsibilities. I think when we start to use the term accountability, we probably talk about that in terms of OSCAR and probably, actually, you know, maybe there's accountability to some of the funders (Participant 1).

Participant 1 concluded the interview by observing how the interview was an important exercise to allow time to reflect and think hard about their accountabilities and stakeholders.

Participant 2 has attempted to improve understanding of accountability and the accountability landscape by stressing the importance of the context in which organisations operate. From her experience no organisation was clear on this approach to understanding their accountability, suggesting that this approach is missing:

I've not got any organisation where this has already been in place. So, this has been a concept I have tried to introduce, and I've always been keen to get organisations that I have been involved with to understand the context in which they operate (Participant 2).

For organisations to understand their environment she cited the need for an ecomap to place the organisation at the centre within layers of stakeholders that surround them. Participant 2 suggests that organisations need to consider their first layer of key stakeholders or those required to exist for example their staff and volunteers. The participant goes on to explain that this thinking can then be extended out to consider local people of interest that could be partners or competitors, that may work in the same space as the organisation. Lastly, she explains that organisations should widen out to see a national and international context:

I think looking at your own organisation, what sits around you, then what's a bit in the locality, the national, and then the global perspective? That really allows you to understand where your accountabilities lie and how effective you are at managing those accountabilities (Participant 2).

This, the participant explained, could be implemented through an ecomap. From her experience she surmised that there were different degrees of excellence around this contextual thinking and use of ecomap type tools. To wrap-up this thinking participant 2 pondered whether

organisations also had accountability for understanding the big trends that could impact the organisation, citing mega trends such as the pandemic and digital transformation. Participant 2 reflected further on similar ways of enhancing understanding of accountabilities and explained that the RACI diagram was useful. This was a tool that could inform people of their responsibilities and their accountability for certain things. An additional area of internal accountability raised by participant 2 was both a personal accountability and organisational accountability for staff and volunteer induction; it was suggested that both parties should be accountable for learning, knowledge, and training within the organisation. The participant later expanded on this line of thought by explaining that whilst it is not necessary for operational staff to understand all terminology used by the board, they must understand the purpose and direction taken by the board, and their role in that.

Participant 3 began to explain her understanding as being an accountability for appropriate spending of money that is taken from organisation members. In terms of an overall understanding of accountabilities Participant 3 ranked the various people to whom they were accountable: firstly members, then parent, funder, other bodies with an interest in what they do, and lastly OSCR as the main reporting regulatory body. The ranking clearly prioritised internal over external accountabilities and she thought the most important aspect was to feedback to members on what was done with the money they paid. When asked if accountability was discussed in the organisation participant 3 explained that it is raised when decision come up and when they think about people with an interest in that decision. In further reflection on why the organisation was accountable participant 3 went on to add that it was because there was a commitment of funds and, they were recognising their own commitment to their national body. The motivation behind accountability was also described as a desire to be transparent to avoid accusations of misuse of money or not doing things right:

I mean it's really important because sometimes it's a commitment of funding or a commitment of being associated with the national body. But also, we would just want to be transparent because you wouldn't want to be accused of everything personally or collectively that you're misusing money or you're not doing things appropriately (Participant 3).

This was re-iterated by the participant when it was explained that the committee wanted peace of mind from external scrutiny, by an auditor for example.

Participant 4 reasoned that sensitive and public affecting issues would make them accountable and responsible to everybody involved in their service including a responsibility for the safety of the public. Participant 4 described a feeling of accountability in a small local community where everybody knows everybody. This is also seen as an accountability for making long-term, rather than simply short-term impacts. Participant 4 went onto explain that he could see accountability as being linked to the levels of stakeholders and pondered on the magnitude of this.

Participant 5 pointed to an accountability for financial performance regards trust fund investment portfolios and an understanding here that those funds must be sustainable in order to continue to provide income to those in need. Likewise for other service providing charities it was explained that there was a general accountability for making sure that those organisations were sustainable, resilient and that involved looking after contracts, funding, staff, and ability to adapt. Participant 5 also suggested that part of this accountability for sustainability could also accommodate risk taking, which can be justified where there are potential benefits to the charity. The board has responsibility here for discussing risk, making people aware of risk, and calculating risk and then ultimately accountability for undertaking and explaining risky courses of action:

A big part of this is taking risks, so not to be risk averse because you're not gonna grow unless you take risk, but it should be calculated risk which is discussed in the boardroom, and everyone is aware of. Yeah, this is a great new project. There risks are, but we're still willing to do it. And you're accountable for that. Yeah. We made this decision because of XY and Z at the time we thought this was a really good decision to make because it was going to make the charity more sustainable, deliver, you know, a service that was more tailored to the end users, whatever it happens to be. Yeah. But that involves taking risks. A lot of boards are very risk averse (Participant 5).

Participant 5 added that the process of minute taking would create lots of board accountability for risk since the record of what was discussed and why decisions were made would be available. Based on experience, participant 5 believed strongly that accountability was neither well understood nor discussed within organisations. An explanation for this was that there was a fear of being accountable amongst board members; this fear could be ameliorated when boards began to understand that there was a collective whole group accountability rather than individual accountability. Furthermore participant 5 suggested that it is helpful to have someone that understands roles and responsibilities to explain this to new board appointees since they would often not really know. From experience it was explained that financial figures, despite their importance, were not liked by many trustees. Participant 5 sympathised with this view recognising that financial information was boring but a necessary feature of every board meeting.

Participant 6 explained that accountability to the funding purpose and mission was discussed quite regularly at the board and in team meetings.

Participant 7 observed that people can fail to understand the need to be accountable to the local community and users of their services, suggesting that there was a need to share information

with them otherwise they would not exist. The community was described as the essential driving force who would dictate the community activities rather than the organisation itself. It was commented that the organisation must be accountable for progress they make and must demonstrate that they are listening to their community. In terms of further understandings of accountability, participant 7 reflected on the fact that they probably do not discuss accountability as often as they should, although questioned if any organisation does. They might not phrase it as accountability but believed that being accountable was a large part of the work that they did.

When asked if the issue of accountability was discussed in the organisation Participant 8 suggested that accountability was something that they didn't worry about since they were trusted by the members and the community. This she reasoned was somewhat due to an appreciation by people for volunteers. However, they wanted to be accountable because of this trust that was placed in them:

I wouldn't say we worry about it. I would say that we're conscious that we know we are trusted. We're trusted, you know, by the community and by the parents, and because they know we're all doing it as volunteers. There's nothing in it for us kind of thing. So, we're conscious that we want to be accountable because they are placing trust in us (Participant 8).

It was later explained that they felt the need to impose accountability mechanisms and checks upon themselves because of the amounts of money involved. In a similar vein participant 8 later added that she felt a need to be "squeaky clean" and to be ready for queries.

Participant 9 thinks there is a great responsibility to the public, users, and funders and that the public should expect confidence in charities since they enjoy legal and financial benefits as part of their charitable status. It is then explained that he believes there is responsibility to offer

value for money for stakeholders, being accountable for good value for money in delivering services within the mission. Overall, participant 9 thought that accountability comes from money, but added that this would just be part of the picture, money just facilitates. Participant 9 felt that accountability was selective within his organisation for example when seeking external funds; this was part of recounting a very negative trustee experience. He went on to add that the charity had an image of accountability and productivity, but they were not making progress. He felt that this could be an issue for the whole sector, where there could be management of the external image to hide poor internal accountability.

Participant 10 explained that accountability is linked to the process of preparing financial accounts and stated that accountability comes from their connection to stakeholders. From the perspective of a treasurer participant 10 understood that his own accountability was to the scout leaders and saw that he had an accountability to look after the money and advise people on spending. There was a personal responsibility to the executive, the trustees, and “everybody else”, to ensure that money was not wasted. Participant 10 viewed personal responsibility and accountability from the local young people through the levels of the organisation up to the parent headquarters and ultimately to the regulator, OSCR. It was explained later that he believed that the process of preparing all accounts in the OSCR format satisfied all financial accountability for the regulator and the levels of his organisation; the audit process also took care of his personal accountability. Participant 10 explained that he understood that there was a potential conflict of interest between trustees or treasurer and role of group leader and was happy that they had a warrant arrangement that kept these roles separate. Participant 10 also felt a need to be “above board” when it came to personal accountability, so made sure that his accounts were externally audited or examined. He explained that he felt this need to do the right thing personally, even though it may not be strictly required. Participant 10 went on to explain that he felt that part of his accountability within the organisation was to use his expertise

to advise others and in fact took up an advisory and guidance role within the larger organisation to set up the executive committees and help other treasurers. He reflected on the fact that there was more limited accountability when it came to his role and work with the non-charity voluntary associations.

Participant 11's understanding of accountability was that they were accountable for the actions of the charity, including how they spent their money. In terms of the board of trustees this would tend to be those that had some understanding of accountability, governance and what it took to run a charity. However, participant 11 did find the idea of discussing accountability within the organisation as "funny" since she thought the board were not really interested in this and just wanted to get on with actual activities. On further reflection she reasoned that discussions around achieving what they set out to do would count as a discussion of accountability. Continuing, participant 11 believed most people didn't understand issues such as governance, stating that it was tedious to most people. It was believed strongly that board members did not understand concepts and phrases around accountability, and she expressed frustration that board members didn't wish to learn. This extended to a lack of knowledge around financial terminology and techniques that she could understand was boring and complicated but was an essential area of accountability that was needed by the organisation.

As a funder or charitable trust fund participant 12 stated that there was a legal accountability to the fund provider since they managed the funding on their behalf. In addition, there was accountability in meeting their community benefit agreement. It was also believed that, in their role as a funder in the sector, they had to execute their accountability to a high standard to give them the authority to hold others to account; they would hold themselves to higher standards even though SCIO status did not require this:

So, obviously we do all the stuff to OSCR, and we are really clear that we can't hold other organisations to account if we aren't ourselves, absolutely, you know, accounts on time, you know, meetings are minuted and signed. I mean all of that stuff we absolutely do, and we think it's important to do because that then gives us, I suppose the ability to go back to organisations and say, yeah, the constitution is great, but we wouldn't fund you because your dissolution clause isn't appropriate. So, we hold ourselves to the highest standards but obviously, you know, that absolutely isn't a requirement of being an SCIO, but we're also still a charitable trust, and it's not a requirement either to do that, but as trustees we think that's important (Participant 12).

Participant 12 then explained the stark contrast in perspectives of accountability within other organisations she had previously worked with. Several organisations, such as grant makers, did not believe they were accountable to anyone since they were using their own funds. Another issue identified was that new people to the sector coming from other sectors did not understand that there was a need to report back to funders; this concept of accountability was new and foreign to them. Participant 12 also observed that a positive experience of accountability was through previous work with a charity that prioritised the beneficiaries over the accountability demands of legislation, governance and overseeing bodies. It was considered that compliance was another area connected with accountability and from experience suggested that this was a tricky area for organisations to navigate in terms of knowing what to do and where to go for help.

Participant 13 began by identifying finance as an area of accountability and went on to explain that the amount contributed by members was flexible, in line with biblical principles. It was felt that they were accountable for the suitability of their membership since they would at times need members to help in spiritual matters; there was also an accountability for sharing information about and between members in this respect. Participant 13 expressed that he was

confident that the board of trustees know their responsibilities such as the role of the chair. The organisation used a professional accountant to keep them in check with their different accounts and cost areas.

5.1.4 Summary

The findings demonstrate that small charities are holding themselves accountable to a wide range of external stakeholders including funders, beneficiaries, and local communities. Accountability to funders and the regulator OSCR are viewed as being an obvious requirement, whilst accountability to beneficiaries and the community are identified as being extremely important in the sector. The findings show that trust is an important determining factor of accountability in the sector; it both motivates charity accountability and lessens the need for it.

The findings reveal that charities and charity boards often struggle with the charity-board relationship and dynamic. Charities and boards require more clarity around their roles, responsibilities, and accountability to each other. The findings highlight that charities are accountable to their charity mission, yet mission drift is still a major issue for the sector. The findings demonstrate that charities are being accountable to parent organisations and recognise the chain of internal accountability.

The findings show that charities and charity boards make the connection between accountability and responsibility to stakeholder groups. Charities also perceive accountability for performance linked to the charity mission. Charities with subscribing members prioritise accountability to these stakeholders. The findings illustrate that accountability is a phrase that is not commonly used nor well understood by many charities and charity boards. The findings also show that financial accountability is an area of weakness for many charity boards who are unwilling or unable to engage with financial terms and concepts. The findings demonstrate that

treasurers are satisfied that OSCR format accounts facilitate personal and organisation financial accountability.

5.2 OVER-ARCHING THEME 2: Building Stakeholder Accountability Relationships

This over-arching theme explores participant accounts of how they perceive their accountability relationships with their stakeholders. Participants will often describe these relationships and interactions with stakeholders from a personal perspective but also from a larger organisational point of view. The relationships described ranged from simple routine distant interactions to more dynamic frequent close relationships. The over-arching theme captures lower-level interpretive sub-themes that emerged from the participant data around ‘identifying and understanding stakeholders’, ‘finding effective communication and accountability mechanisms’, ‘being transparent’ and encountering ‘stakeholder apathy’. At the lowest descriptive thematic level many issues were uncovered and coded including identifying external and internal stakeholders, using formal, informal, private, public, multiple use mechanisms. In addition, the lack of board interest amongst stakeholder groups and the characteristics of information such as sensitive information, targeted information and performance data were also evident in the participant accounts. The process of defining, applying, re-defining, and re-applying thematic codes at the different levels eventually produced a coherent thematic structure. The resulting thematic structure emerged from a bottom-up process of defining many low-level descriptive themes that belong to higher level interpretive themes, which in turn were captured by the single over-arching theme. The theme of trust was raised by several participants in multiple contexts and could be viewed as an integrative theme that cuts across all interpretive themes.

Figure 15: Thematic structure 'Building Stakeholder Accountability Relationships'

Source: Author

5.2.1 Identifying and Understanding Stakeholders

Participant 1 began by acknowledging that there was accountability to OSCR, but this was described as simply procedural. It was stated that OSCR was important but questioned how often they would need to communicate with them beyond submitting accounts. Their main responsibility was to their funders and in making sure they were meeting their requirements. It was also felt that it was important to seek feedback from government and their public sector partners around their effectiveness or impact in their charity aim of influencing change at local and national level. It was reasoned that there was lots of value in the information that the charity had, and this could be used not just for the primary purpose, but in fact to influence others such as government. It was further reasoned that there was power to influence with information even though its primary use might be to secure funding. Participant 1 went on to explain that they wished to connect to and influence a wider set of stakeholders through wider dissemination of information about their different outputs:

A lot of public sector organizations and providers of self-directed support services don't understand the basics. So, we're doing an awful lot of training just now building the capacity and capabilities of those individuals as well. So, there's an output settlement too as well. How many people have we trained? What have we trained them in as well as what difference might that make to their day job? I think what can influence them a little bit is actually sharing that information you know and that's a wider dissemination of what we have learned whether it's from evaluation or feedback or the level of change is disseminating that information and trying to influence other parts of the system (Participant 1).

When asked to consider performance measurement Participant 1 considered that beneficiaries were in fact the focus of the organisation since they existed to serve their interests and improve

their lives; it was also important for them to understand that they were doing that through their advocacy work. It was explained that the charity had a very large number of wider beneficiary stakeholders that they did not have a close relationship with but there was a closer relationship with those beneficiaries that interacted through their website and social media. Scottish government was identified as an important stakeholder since they were a substantial fund provider. The relationship with government was described as a strong one since they would work together, consult, and influence each other in areas of policy. In terms of other funders, participant 1 explained that they would engage to different degrees based on the level of funding; engagement would be scaled up and down appropriately. Other stakeholders identified by participant 1 were described as “system players” including local authorities, care providers and care partnerships who delivered the self-direct support for which the charity advocated. It was explained that there was a strong relationship with a few of these partners and this was often complicated since their role was to educate and to criticise practice. Their responsibility was primarily to beneficiaries, so it was difficult to balance good working relationships with sector partners when demanding that they had to change. Participant 1 identified a partner charity as an important stakeholder; they shared premises and leant on them substantially for their specialist financial and IT knowledge. The partner charity shared policies and practices, allowing them to grow as an organisation. Furthermore, the charity had a wider network of stakeholder partners within the national working groups they were involved with. In terms of internal stakeholders, there was a need to look after the well-being of their employees; this he believed to be a close and intimate relationship with the board. Given time to reflect on stakeholders, Participant 1 showed some surprise at the extensive and wide range of these.

From experience, participant 2 felt that although organisations might talk about their stakeholders, she would question whether they had good definitions for stakeholders. Participant 2 also raised the question of how organisations could identify appropriate levels of

communication when they couldn't distinguish between important and less important stakeholders. It was her view that some organisations recognised their stakeholders, but others did not, and of those that did, they could not differentiate between those that were key and those that were non-key. On a few occasions some charities identified their key stakeholders and dealt with them appropriately, but they had not been labelled as such:

I would say some are implied but not explicit. So, they might talk about who their key stakeholders are, but do they have a good definition and therefore how do they communicate with one set of stakeholders that are potentially key and how do they communicate with others that are not as key but then equally are kept engaged as stakeholders, they're kept up to date with what's going on at appropriate levels? And what I would find some people wouldn't even recognise who their stakeholders were, and other people would recognise who all their stakeholders were but wouldn't know the difference between key and non-key. And there's a couple where it was explicit in how they dealt with some people that they recognised as key, but they maybe just hadn't put that label on them (Participant 2).

Participant 2 then described the RACI tool that could be used to help charities clarify the requirements of accountability and levels of interaction with stakeholders. It was felt that it was important that the board, managers, and staff all agreed upon who were the key stakeholders. In terms of role of the charity board Participant 2 explained that she had attempted to move boards away from charity operations to focus on governance issues. The boards would have operational side updates from the chief executive but there was an attempt to draw a demarcation line to distinguish the roles of board with the role of chief executive and charity operations. Participant 2 pointed to the challenge of meeting completely different needs or demands from different funders, organisations having to deal with completely different funding applications. It was suggested that having a good understanding, a holistic understanding, of

the organisation was of great benefit. Understanding what the organisation did, why it did it, and the outcomes that were achieved meant that the story could be told to meet any funding application requirement. Regardless of the different questions from different funders, these were fundamentally about the same thing, and knowing the organisation gives confidence to adapt things for different people:

Well see my view on that is, yes, the application itself might look different between the Big Lottery and the Robertson Trust, whoever, but fundamentally, you holistically have reviewed your organisation, you know what you're doing, why you're doing it, what outcomes these things are achieving. You can tell the story in whatever form the funder wants the form filled in because you've only got one story you tell about your organisation. It's how you tell it to the different funders based on the questions they ask, but fundamentally, it's all about the same thing. That's where being on top of how well you know your organisation gives you the confidence to tweak things accordingly, when different people ask about your organisation (Participant 2).

Participant 3 identified their membership as the first group of stakeholders, adding that there was an embedded or overlapping structure since some members were also on the committee. The members also provided finance in the form of their annual membership payment; it was later added that the charity would not exist without its members. Likewise, it was commented that the charity would obviously not exist without its parent organisation. Participant 3 felt there was a need to keep their membership informed of any spending decisions and to make sure they were happy in this respect. However, there was a recognition that there was sometimes disagreement in spending decisions with members and that a balance or middle ground had to be reached. One problematic area identified by Participant 3 was the different formats of accounts required by different stakeholder groups, pointing to OSCR, the charity parent and even gift aid returns having different reporting demands. There was a feeling that

having to manage and understand data and information in order to output in acceptable format for each stakeholder was a significant burden. When asked to expand on this however, it was supposed that this was not overly challenging and was mainly an issue in their first year when adapting to the needs of the regulator. They required clarity about content requirements, and the accounting periods for parent and regulator differed posing another timing challenge:

I don't think it's overly challenging, but certainly in the first year we were registered with the OSCR we found what they were looking for was slightly different from what we had in terms of the format. So, I think at one point there was a bit of a pushback about our finances. And it just was a clarity about what was expected to be in there when it was expected to be launched, it could get a weird timeline in that we tend to do a calendar year for accounts, but always OSCR need them at a certain point in time. And I think there was some sort of storming obviously initially just to make sure we had all that in alignment at the right time, that the information is up to date for what they need and then parent need a different timeline. So, I say that's probably the biggest challenge just sort of when information is needed (Participant 3)

In conclusion, it was reasoned that they could meet information needs once they understood them, but it would be helpful if stakeholders could be aligned with what they need in terms of format and timing. Participant 3 commented that the needs of the regulator and of their parent organisation were not aligned and this could be a substantial task for a small voluntary committee to pull together what was almost the same information in different ways. Despite these challenges around alignment, it was thought that OSCR was a positive stakeholder in terms of being there to help explain the regulatory requirements. It was stated that they needed OSCR in terms of providing them with charitable status. The council was recognised as a stakeholder since they used their facilities and the chairman identified that the public could have an interest in their information so was keen to share via the website. Participant 3

explained that a second and less important tier of stakeholders existed that they were less reliant upon since substitutes existed for example their current bank. It was noted it was useful to see these tiers of important stakeholder that were essential to exist and then looking wider to those that were less important. Participant 3 reflected on the fact that overall, the organisation was not very outward looking, but the parent organisation was much better at engaging with wider stakeholders.

Participant 4 identified an accountability to funders for what they do but stated that they would look at the size of funding and share information based on this. In addition to the board, Participant 4 explained that the nature of their work made them realise they required another set of external stakeholder advisors in the form of a highly respected legal team. The legal team are vital to their service helping to keep both the charity and the clients safe. Similarly, the organisation had reached out to an external academic stakeholder advisor to inform their policy and practice. Participant 4 later added that he was confident that although they were small, their support network of stakeholders made them a robust organisation. It was explained that a key relationship and accountability was with clients since they would often work with them in extreme situations and share sensitive information with each other. Participant 4 identified trust as the key component in the charity-client relationship explaining that regular contact before and during the actual service delivery would lead to increasing amounts of information being shared between both parties. Participant 4 identified that their stakeholders could be fluid and that often there were times where they must look wider for example to the impact on the public. In addition, engagement with police could be required, and it was a case of understanding when and where to share information with the various stakeholder groups that needed to be informed. It was commented that they could see multi-level stakeholders even for such a small organisation and that it was important to be “ahead of the game” in terms of continually reviewing their policies around information sharing and not to be complacent. Participant 4

described visualising stakeholders and their information needs as an intertwined network and the task was not to lose any of the threads. It was reasoned that there are numerous issues connected to their charity and its outcomes and stakeholders are interested in this. In terms of the charity board, participant 4, identified the chair as a sort of clinical director who could offer his expertise and advice to the chief executive around client cases. This relationship was seen as vital to their service since it also allowed the board to understand their complex service. Participant 4 explained that they had a client committee who could inform the board and chief executive of their needs and this board-client-chief relationship was seen as very beneficial to all parties from the chief exec's perspective. Collaboration and agreement with users on what the charity service should provide was seen as key for the charity.

Participant 5 began by identifying that for charities with financial investments or trusts then the impact on people's lives was something that had to be stressed to their fund manager stakeholders. It was important to emphasise the need for continuous finance availability to serve ongoing needs to improve people's lives; this was not the prime focus for fund managers. Participant 5 noted that funders, trusts, and foundations are all important stakeholder for the third sector as were the local councils. The public were stakeholders that would require a marketing and communication plan to be consistent and avoid any mixed messages. It was explained that consistent messaging was also required for service users too since they also picked up on social media. Participant 5 identified that some charities had an overwhelming number of funders and stakeholders who would request different things. It was suggested that charities must open a dialogue with funders and stakeholders to negotiate the information requirements; this would be an honest conversation about the resource constraints faced by the charity. Participant 5 had experienced that funders were open to these conversations and were willing to listen and change, despite the fears that charities had over upsetting their funders:

If you talk to charities, they'll say, but we've got loads of stakeholders because we've got, I know one charity's got 33 different funders, right? And they're all asking for different things, or you know, stakeholders. It could be some local councils or community. They're all asking for different things that are a pain in the neck. And they're a necessary pain in the neck. And then all we say to them, well, why don't you go back to the funder and very gently say why are you asking for this piece of information? Because actually, that's a lot of work we don't normally, you know, collect that. So, if you really want us to, I'll get it for you. But why? But they're always a bit resistant to do that. And if you talked to the funders, the funders forum and all the rest of it, we're all in our funder's forum are talking about how this is the sort of thing we want to hear because we can change. But if you don't tell us we don't know, but it's along the lines of the charities thing of better not bite the hand that feeds us (Participant 5).

Participant 5 later re-iterated that reporting and accountability should be proportionate in terms of size of charity turnover and that charities should not fear asking for compromise in report length and detail for smaller funds. Charities should look to collaborate in this respect. Participant 5 identified charity to charity partnerships as important stakeholder relationships for the sector. It was explained that funders would often look favourably on charity partnerships or joint funding applications. To this end Participant 5 had previously brought charity boards together to discuss issues and share their ideas and practices; this proved to be valuable for all involved, but she was unsure how to encourage this more widely in the sector.

Participant 6 identified their community of beneficiaries as their first stakeholder group and explained that they had a two-way relationship since they would effectively work together in delivering services. The charity also seen the local community as an important source for their volunteers. Other stakeholders identified were their internal staff and volunteers. Participant 6

confirmed that funding would be given for a specific purpose, but some funders would allow some flexibility if they engaged in conversation to discuss their circumstances. Participant 6 had experienced that their board was very interested in charity performance and requested frequent updates and reports on activities. The relationship with the board was seen as being a fruitful one since the board would offer up their skills in areas such as funding applications. However, there were occasions when the charity management had disagreement with the board regards what would be feasible for them to deliver and commit to within the funding applications. Participant 6 felt that they could be open and candid about their challenges with their board in a way that they couldn't be with their funders. Participant 6 described working partnerships with other charities in the sector and added that they liaised with several other charities to ensure that there was no duplication of the services they provided.

Participant 7 felt that funder requirements could be very different, so this required both an understanding of what was needed and management so not to drown in the volume of information. Participant 7 explained that funders would request different report formats, so it wasn't possible to easily copy and paste or transfer information. It was explained that the charity had some fears over getting things wrong where funders had even just small difference in information requirements and format of reports. It was believed that the charity was handling the challenge of different funder requirements as best they could, but it was largely out of their control. It was explained that long-term funding arrangements were helpful since they knew the requirements, but new funders could be more problematic:

So, whilst I think we probably do manage it in the best way that we can, it's kind of out with our control at times: where that information needs to go and what sort of format it needs to go in. If you're working with a funder, say for example, Scottish Government, who we've worked with them for nine years, you pretty much know what they are going to ask for. So, I have that in the back of my head when I'm putting information together.

And I think that I know that the SG are going to ask for this, and I know that they're going to ask for that. But if you start working with brand new funder for the first time, so Glasgow City Council, we're just coming to the end of our first period of being funded by them and their reporting process is so completely different to anybody else that I've used in the past. So, it kind of depends on the length of the relationship you've had with the funder (Participant 7).

On reflection, participant 7 explained that the base information was available to be picked out from their simple database but that this still had to be arranged in the various formats. Despite the burden of funder requirements, it was reasoned later that there could be benefit to more frequent reporting in that all relevant information could be captured before being forgotten. Participant 7 recognised that they had a close connection with their local council since they would deal with them on a regular basis; whilst they did not have a close relationship with central government. Likewise, they had a close relationship with local funders who they worked with more intimately. Reporting requirements for small funders were seen as less resource intensive but they did not see these funders as being any less important. Participant 7 went on to explain that an important stakeholder group would be their partner organisations since they had a keen interest in each other's activities; this was largely to identify opportunities for joint funding, reasoning that collaboration could produce a stronger application. Sharing information about activities could also help identify and avoid any duplication of activities; it was felt that this was essential for all organisations in the sector when funds were so limited. Good relationships between organisations would be required to understand common interests for partnering. It was felt that these relationships would have to be close and intimate to know people, their motivations and what they were good at. Again, there would be benefit to the relationship for the wider community since organisations could then direct users to the right place for help. Participant 7 reflected on the fact that not all organisations were good at

communicating with others in the sector, which was disappointing since she believed that working together would be more effective for the whole community:

No, I don't think we're doing it as well as we could be. And I think there are organisations out there who do do it and do it incredibly well. But there are other organizations who are quite insular I suppose and don't actually really care what other people are doing and whether they're stepping on other people's toes. I mean, the reality is that's the reason why I've since changed organizations because the organization that I worked for were a little bit like that. And again, they're probably the biggest organization in this area. So, you can see that they felt they had a little bit of control and authority over it. But the reality is if they would just work better with everybody else, it would provide this really sort of consistent approach and really effective approach for the community (Participant 7).

However, it was reasoned that some organisations would only participate if there was a clear personal gain.

Participant 8 identified the board and members as their main charity stakeholders. It was stated that without their members or users they would not exist. The community was also acknowledged and the local authority since the charity was subsidised in terms of their rates. It was felt that there was inherent trust in the organisation since they had a long-established place in their community and a continuity and succession of members over an extended period of time. OSCR was identified as the most important external stakeholder since they were legally bound to send them information although there wasn't much correspondence beyond the legal requirement. It was supposed that government were also an important stakeholder through the child protection legislation, they were held accountable for appropriate people and activities in this respect. Participant 8 also identified anyone who contributed to fundraising

events as stakeholders; it was reasoned that there was a huge level of trust placed in them by this stakeholder group and this brought a weight of responsibility. Participant 8 felt that the committee or board had an important role to play in sharing information about what was going on in the charity with both internal volunteers and members since it was often the case that different groups within the charity would be working independently.

Participant 9 showed frustration that there was a breakdown in communication and accountability between the Charity and the Board. In his role as chair, Participant 9 explained that he was denied access to financial statements and believed there was an ongoing failure in financial accountability to the board. It was explained that there was a selective accountability to funders for example, but very little accountability to the board. Participant 9 later explained that there were deliberate distraction techniques used by the chief executive when asked for more information. Participant 9 was visibly angered and frustrated when describing this behaviour and admitted that it had eventually worn him down. The relationship between the Chief Executive, the deputy chair and himself deteriorated to the point where he felt that both had pushed him out of the organisation. Participant 9 later expressed regret that he had not reported his concerns to the regulator but said at the time the experience had left him feeling victimised and too weak. It was felt that the other board members had placed too much trust in their chief executive and that this trust was betrayed through blatant abuse of power. Participant 9 described a situation when the chief executive had placed him in an awkward situation with a funder knowing that the financial details had not been shared with the board or him as chair:

But there was selective, yeah, there was selective external accountability when the director wanted more funds. But that was all dealt with by her. So, you know, unless there was, there was one occasion I was, I was wheeled in. And I didn't know very much about anything because the information hadn't been shared even though I asked for it. So, it was a bit awkward, but obviously I wanted to, it was an external funder, a

charitable trust, you know, who do these for the benefits of their governance and checks. That was an interesting experience such as the person they sent was a volunteer who was a retired corporate lawyer, who had done work with the universities in Scotland and who was just trying to find out how we got the funding from them. I think in part by using me as a sort of puppet for that occasion, but I felt very much used and abused, rather than as somebody who should have been in charge of the whole thing, you know (Participant 9).

Participant 9 reflected upon what had been a terrible experience and suggested that because good things were being done in the community this could counter his arguments that the charity had internal accountability failures. Participant 9 explained that the charity staff rather than the board had interaction and relationship with beneficiaries and the local community. The local authority was described as a “very powerful stakeholder” within their area of deprivation. Participant 9 felt frustrated that from his perspective the council and councillors made their decisions for political reasons rather than getting work done in the community. He also drew attention to the competition for funds amongst charities within their area of deprivation and a feeling that larger charities did not respect their smaller organisation. The charity had worked in partnership with another charity before but believed this was purely for financial reasons. It was felt that the local environment including local authority and other charities was not supportive since each had their own objectives. It was also felt that the extremely competitive funding environment was unhelpful:

But you know, I'll give an example of their chief executive. She wouldn't meet with me. She kept making appointments and then missing them. I had the same sort of treatment from the Citizens Advice Bureau who were trying to deliver their services through our premises and with our help. But we do things like arrange meetings, they don't turn up and then try and arrange more and more meetings. And you think, oh, fuck off, you

know, you're disrespectful. I don't know if that's a good quote or not, but, you know, the stakeholder environment is extremely competitive because there's not very much money about and everybody's trying to make the same or grander claims about how much better they are at solving the wicked problems of urban deprivation (Participant 9).

Participant 10 recognised that as a charity OSCR were an important stakeholder with requirement to report back with audited accounts. The relationship with external auditor was also explained as being important since they could have an honest dialogue and the auditor gave him confidence that he was fulfilling his personal accountability. He went on to explain that he felt he had many stakeholders to manage in his role as treasurer, including children, parents, the levels of leadership and OSCR. Members were identified as the most important stakeholder group and there was responsibility to show them where money came from and where it went to. Participant 10 identified group scout leaders as being obvious internal stakeholders whom he had responsibility for oversight and coordination of their financial records. It was then explained that the treasurer's role was to collate and summarise all the accounting or financial information. Other stakeholders identified included a local church who provided their premises and the wider communities and towns where their members came from. Any organisation they would work with would also become a stakeholder. Participant 10 supposed that grant providers would also become stakeholders and stressed the importance of providing them with evidence that the money they had provided had been spent on what was agreed. Participant 10 confessed that they sometimes had to be creative in how they applied for funding for example arguing that they were eligible for funds earmarked for social deprivation, which he explained was only partly true. Participant 10 closed by commenting on the need for the organisation to continuously distinguish between the information needs of those directly involved in the organisation with those of the public.

Participant 11 identified their members, volunteers, and trustees as the main stakeholders of the organisation. It was felt that the stakeholders are those that do the work and would be interested in the results. Participant 11 identified their current funders as their main external stakeholder, going on to explain that a stakeholder would cease to be a stakeholder when the funding ended. It was commented on later that most of the charity time and effort was expended trying to raise funds. OSCR was identified as a stakeholder who would need to know about their charitable activities and would be in contact only if they breached any regulations. Participant 11 expressed her belief that there was a need for this type of regulation. In wrapping up Participant 11 reflected on how fundamental communication was to what they did but felt there was often a lack of two-way communication between stakeholders. It was reasoned that this was because there was a lack of understanding and a lack of desire to understand each other:

Yeah. I mean, it's fundamental really. It is fundamental because what you're describing is fundamental communication. You know, that talking that helps how you communicate with your staff, volunteers, members, stakeholders, whatever you want to call them. It's communication and that's fundamental to absolutely everything we do. But communication is two-way. You're a broadcaster and a receiver. It's the only way you ever get a message through. One has to broadcast them; one has to receive them. We're broadcasting but nobody is receiving. That's how we feel. That's my fundamental issue then. But they're not doing it because they're evil or bad, they just don't understand it. They just don't understand what you're saying. I think we need a lot more honesty. And they need to say we don't understand what you're talking about (Participant 11)

Participant 12 reflected that their most important relationship as a grant making charity was with their own funders. It was then also reasoned that they see themselves as being very responsible to the grant recipients; they felt a need to demonstrate to the recipients that they

had learned about their organisations and understood what they do. Participant 12 recounted an experience when working as a trustee with another charitable trust; the charity was having in-depth discussion and debate around prioritising their stakeholders. Participant 12 was of the view that their grant recipients were most important, but the other board members ultimately decided that donors were more important:

And we had a long discussion at a board meeting about which group of stakeholders were most important, whether the groups that we funded, the recipients were most important or if the donors were more important. And actually, the board apart from me decided that the donors were more important than the charities that we were funding. It was a board primarily of businesspeople and you know they thought, they're argument was without the money we can't give it to the group. So, I'm going without groups doing brilliant work, coming to us, and asking and explaining and letting us understand what they do and why, we would never be able to convince the donors of the need for their money. But this board was clear that the donors were more important (Participant 12).

Participant 12 explained a feeling of being “torn apart” by many stakeholder groups when working for organisations involved in direct provision of services since the number of stakeholders was overwhelming. Participant 12 expressed a strong belief that a good chief executive is required to keep the staff and organisation focussed on their outward accountability. It was noted that there was often a tricky working relationship between a board and its chief executive and had experienced several situations where reporting and accountability ideas proposed by the board were not supported by chief executive. Overall, it was felt that chief executives could be more open to the knowledge and experience of trustees; whilst equally, boards could show more respect for the qualities of chief executives. Participant 12 went on to explain that the situation is a difficult one in charities since the board could take

the view that they were offering their time and expertise as volunteers and that charity chief executives should be grateful for this. Participant 12 had witnessed situations where the relationship between board and charity had completely broken down. In these situations, there would be minimal interaction in the form of basic board meetings and papers; and no access, participation or observation of charity operations permitted by the charity. Participant 12 reflected on the conditions that were being placed on small organisations often just to access small funds and expressed a desire for these conditions to be beneficial to the organisation. It was felt that small organisations should embrace the grant conditions for their own benefit:

I think it's so tricky for organisations to know what to do, where to go for help and how to do it all. In fact, one of the organisations was talking about that this morning, a small organisation that just wanted some money for a Christmas event, you know, but we require them to have a constitution, we require them to have a bank account, we require them to have, you know, so it was how they go about doing that, but making it the best thing for them to do as an organisation rather than just having to do it, to comply, you know to put an application to us. Why wouldn't they want to do it to make the organisation future proof and build on that? (Participant 12)

Participant 12 had witnessed a change in perspective within some organisations, for example they were now committing to evaluations as opposed to feeling trepidation over their reporting requirements. Participant 12 explained that she was excited to see the transition away from doing things just to meet funder demands.

Participant 13 identified the board of trustees as an obvious stakeholder for their organisation going on to state that they would meet four times a year. Participant 13 then identified internal stakeholders as being their members who were involved in different areas of activity but seemed unclear whether all could be described as stakeholders, with some described as “maybe

less so”. Volunteers and staff were identified as two distinct groups of stakeholders, and it was explained that they had very little in the way of a hierarchy given the small numbers involved. Participant 13 suggested that they had less in the way of external stakeholders, at least in terms of their importance; these groups included OSCR, professional services, and the local council. OSCR was identified as an obvious stakeholder and they also had help and support from accounting and legal services. They also had some degree of interaction with the Council due to their lease of council land. Participant 13 explained that they had association and relationship with other Church organisations; this was a type of general agreement on for example some spiritual matters, but they remained independent. It appeared that they did not hold each other accountable for their partnership, suggesting it was simply a supportive network:

Yeah, there's no authority, not like a denomination. There's nobody has any say over our money. No say over anything, how we operate, the leadership team is completely independent. But we would have our kind of association or partnership that says we're kind of on the same page as you guys and therefore we have links with a couple of organisations that do that. Umm, that's effectively other independent churches; and that's a supportive network really (Participant 13).

Participant 13 later explained that the Church had a similar relationship with organisations that would help them support people abroad. These organisations were seen as important, and they would have to keep in touch and work together. Participant 13 explained that a small team of trustee and two financial people have access to their financial information. The view of the Church was that what members pay should be flexible and private.

5.2.2 Finding Effective Communication and Accountability Mechanisms

Participant 1 explained that the annual report and the constant monitoring of internal finances was an important internal accountability mechanism. The Board would meet quarterly to analyse and discuss the management accounts. The annual report and accounts would be shared at the AGM and although they were described as the “simplest” way to share information it was conceded that they required a lot of work. There was a belief that there had to be an internal focus on cashflow and fundraising as the main part of the board meetings otherwise other things would become harder. Webinars and the website were used to share their research reports in attempt to raise awareness and widen their influence. In addition, it was explained that some beneficiaries were involved in consultations with the charity and participated in training and programme delivery themselves, thus building further capacity. Annual proposal processes were used as an effective two-way communication with Scottish government to consult and agree upon output and outcome targets. In addition, monthly meetings would be arranged to discuss progress. It was concluded that the processes were a useful mechanism to set up next year’s accountability and reflect upon the previous year’s effectiveness. Participant 1 reasoned that they were meeting stakeholder needs through a diverse range of communication methods. A campaign approach was cited where information was shared with mainstream media outlets to raise awareness and have further impact; this was supported by social media and webinars to reach wider audiences. It was believed that these multiple media strategy led to successful outcomes for the project. Participant 1 commented on the need for regular online communication with their user groups, including dissemination of report findings, to encourage users to participate in discussions and with a spin-off benefit of influencing other sector actors. Although communication through social media and webinars was seen as comprehensive, the website was seen as being less useful. It was concluded that the online channels could be powerful ways to communicate with people by influencing, demonstrating, and getting people

engaged, but she didn't necessarily think that this was about accountability. The charity would also produce a quarterly newsletter that it would direct to beneficiaries and some other organisations that required an update. The charity would run a summer festival to engage and update their user groups and the system players and keep the debate going around their issue; the event would be a mechanism for disseminating information but also help to achieve their influencing aims:

So, it's about bringing people together and facilitating discussion if you like, and awareness raising so keeps the profile of us as an organisation up there, but actually it's disseminating information and trying to influence change in kind of another way. So, there's many different channels we would use. I guess they both meet accountability, and I guess is meeting not just what the accountability you feel to those organisations or those stakeholders, but doubling in that action and influencing channel as well? I think you know that's the smart way to do it. It's not just to see what they want. How can we produce it in a way that have impact beyond just the needs of that particular stakeholder? (Participant 1)

In a similar vein participant 1 later added that some reports could be used to serve several stakeholders but pondered that it might be the discussion around the reports that would differ to satisfy different people's needs.

In terms of communicating with communities and beneficiaries Participant 2 had experienced that organisations were seeking consultation on their own ideas as opposed to seeking consultation on needs. This "accountability for consulting" she had felt was often the wrong way round. Participant 2 explained that everyone in the organisation should understand how they should interact with stakeholders and the time and resource that should be spent on stakeholder communication. In one organisation she had worked with, a communication plan

was used to outline the different communications that would be undertaken with different stakeholders. The communication plan outlined different types of mechanism that could be used and would distinguish communication between key and non-key stakeholders; key stakeholders would receive more frequent and personal communication:

So, it actually defines here are our key ones and why they're key. Here's our internal stakeholders, who we would define as internal stakeholders and then we had a communications map. So, for every person that was mentioned whether it be board, staff, volunteers, stakeholder suppliers; we actually had a mark that said here's the types of communications we'll undertake. And we ticked off all those people who would get the different types of communications. So, whether that be things like a newsletter, access to our policies and links to our website and specific tailored training, one to one meetings and joint meetings. So, for instance if a stakeholder was a key stakeholder, they might get one to one updates; once a year if they were not key stakeholders but they were still stakeholders and they might have typically got an annual newsletter from us (Participant 2).

Participant 2 explained that all stakeholders could be kept informed of things through discussion at the AGM such as reviewing achievements, but someone would be allocated for more frequent communications throughout the year with key stakeholders. The exact nature of communication whether written, verbal, informal or formal was dependent on the stakeholder connection to the organisation. Participant 2 pointed to their use of a patron as an effective and quite unique communication and accountability mechanism believing this is an innovative way to communicate and one that not many organisations would think of. The organisation was continuing to think about the role of the patron and the ways that they could help with stakeholder communications. Participant 2 also pointed to the importance of cost-benefit when considering different accountability mechanisms citing the example of assessing effectiveness

of newsletter versus emails. The organisation has now revised their approach to significantly reduce the use of newsletters and cost to the organisation. Part of this is also setting communication expectations with stakeholders, being careful not to over commit and it was felt that this case re-enforced the need to continually review mechanisms to see if they were meeting the desired outcomes. In closing, Participant 2 revisited the idea of holistic understanding and assessment of the organisation; stating that this required multiple voices. The ideal scenario would be to include multiple internal and external stakeholders in the process to allow for multiple perspectives on how the charity was run and managed, creating accountability and feedback for improvement. Participant 2 expressed a strong belief that for this reason an organisation should always be interested in the views of its stakeholders.

Participant 3 pointed to regular committee meetings and the minute taking process as being an effective and consistent mechanism of internal accountability. It was also explained that quarterly financial reports would be presented to the committee and annually to the membership. The accounts were independently audited and published to the website for wider dissemination to the public. The AGM was important to present information on output or activities and the finances to the internal stakeholders. It was stated that “everything” was on the website including photos and blogs of meetings for people to access. When asked if accountability mechanisms were discussed by the committee Participant 3 commented that she didn’t think so, however, they recognised that there was very formal information required by funders, which they knew was different to what members wanted to know.

Participant 4 regarded accountability as something that could be achieved through word of mouth in the community; there was also trust since the community could observe the impact and track record of the charity’s service. Participant 4 explained that charity visits were arranged to allow system stakeholders opportunity to hear first-hand accounts from users. In a similar vein, the community were brought together to raise awareness of the issues the charity

was dealing with. These were successful mechanisms of communication and accountability for the charity:

Some of the things that we've shared as a kind of introduction to some people as a prompt to them to say, would you like to come through for a visit. That's how we go. The Lord Advocate, Solicitor General in the room with these two people, we have them in for two hours, but they stayed for the best part of four, just listening to what the clients had to say. And some things like that to get people in the room. Others are for raising awareness, you know of what's happening in the community. You know what? And we once we shared what was happening within it, the likes of some of the darker issues that people experience, they would be hugely surprised; because it's never really spoke about and even just raising that awareness with some issues brings it to the front of people's minds. To then say why is this issue so prevalent. And the answer is you know that we are working in one of the most deprived areas in Scotland (Participant 4).

Participant 4 went on to express a desire to share their best practice with system stakeholders to promote wider system change; good communication in this respect could influence wider policy changes. However, participant 4 believed that advocacy and influence was not easy since people would not believe until they had seen the results. Participant 4 explained that they had degrees of information sharing with various funders, citing the example of a generous philanthropist who expected, and was provided with, opportunities to visit and speak with ex-users of the service. Communication also included bi-annual visits to explain what had been done with the funds; likewise, there was an expectation and a willingness to share information with other large fund providers such as Lottery Fund. It was viewed as a good thing that Lottery fund would visit face to face and ask probing questions for example about their governance and the board, in addition to the written reports and break-down of statistics that they provided:

I think taking the biggest fund, the accountability and sharing information it's two reports a year I've got to do and to lottery, which is fine because they're very short now. They used to be quite long, but also, we have that personal interface with them, you know, they were just down a couple of weeks ago and they were asking how is the governance, what's happening with that, we see you're increasing your board, why are you increasing your board? So, they ask really quite probing questions and that's good you know, and yeah, and I explained the need for increasing the board and why we just don't want to bring bodies on to the board, we want to just you know pick up a skill base or experience or something like that. So, that interface, that personal and written report interface is really good (Participant 4).

Overall, it was felt that funder visits provided explanations for the figures and that this was a more passionate way of communicating through observation of their work. Participant 4 described attempts to engage with a local funding group, but that this had been disappointing; conversations with their philanthropist led them to believe that perception of the funder was that their service was free and already funded by the Lottery. The charity used focus groups in a college as a way of community communication and as an interface to communicate with future sector workers. Engaging presentations including pictures were seen as an effective mechanism to communicate and generate interest in the work that the charity did. The local press and various other publications were also used to share what they do with wider stakeholders; however, they were frightened by social media since there was huge scope to say the wrong thing. It was felt that it was important to take steps to ensure that the right consistent message was communicated more widely. In conclusion, Participant 4 reasoned that they had a variety of ways of communicating with such a diverse range of stakeholders.

Participant 5 began by explaining that the minute taking process was perhaps the most important internal accountability mechanism for an organisation. The minutes provided a

record of decision-making within the organisation that could be called upon at any time. Participant 5 also expressed belief that the annual accounts told an important story to all stakeholders and were the “shop window” into the organisation. The annual report was opportunity to discuss the good things about the charity but also to point out where things hadn’t worked. Websites could tell stories about impact, but many stakeholders would regard this as “fluffy” information and would wish to see the annual accounts. Participant 5 commented that it was her experience that accountants wanted more stories, narratives, and visual aids to bring the annual report to life; the annual accounts might be the only information used by stakeholders, so it was paramount to make it interesting, engaging and representative of the charity’s value. It was believed that an engaging annual report could make the difference in a competitive charity funding environment. Participant 5 believed that funders would like to hear more specific details about what money was being used for, to participate in AGMs and events to see first-hand what their money would deliver. This was perceived as being more useful to funders than anything that could be captured in the routine quarterly or bi-annual funding reports. It was explained though that charities often had an irrational fear of funders so would fail to reach out and invite them to events; there was a fear of saying the wrong thing and losing their funding. It was also suggested that organisations could send videos to funders to demonstrate what the charity does in an engaging way, for example stories from beneficiaries to the funder on the personal benefits of the services. Participant 5 commented that the typical way to connect and share information with users would be when the service is delivered.

Participant 6 described the funding return that was required by almost all their funders; these would ask for details of how funds were used and any differences between what was agreed required approval. It was suggested that this level of reporting could be burdensome on time and people and disproportionate for smaller funding arrangements:

So, every funding that you get also has to have a return. So, no matter what we do, so we've just finished one for Scottish Government. So you have got to put your outcomes, everything has to be on that, you have to, they won't just give you money and go that's great what we did- you have to tell them how well it went, is there any changes they have to get any changes so that all has to be done for every funding that we have so. You know, even if it's £500 from the local Community council, you've got to do a report on that, like to go back to them to say, you know that this is what we've achieved with that money (Participant 6).

Participant 6 later re-iterated that the requirements to satisfy small funders were ridiculous, but there could be a spin-off benefit to this process. It was felt for example that in the case of a small council fund; then the application and funding return facilitated a vital communication of community issues to the council. This meant that voices were being heard to affect change at higher levels. Participant 6 added later that “everything would go in every single funding application”. The situation was described as tricky due to the time spent completing funding applications. Also, the resources required to complete monitoring reports were significant since these required lots of information from lots of people to assess targets, outline what was achieved and write-up case studies. Overall, it was felt that the continuous nature of completing funding returns and new funding applications was repetitive and time consuming. There was also the knowledge that after all the hard work and effort the funding applications could be unsuccessful. Participant 6 explained that a recent initiative was to use project diaries for staff and volunteers to continuously record all information so that it would be readily available for them to quickly profile a project group for funding returns. Participant 6 later conceded that they could perhaps work a little bit smarter to identify where information from larger reports could feed into others.

Participant 6 identified board meetings as a mechanism for setting and discussing outcomes and their progress towards meeting their targets. Although the charity was very busy it was felt that board meetings for updates was something that she liked to do. Participant 6 also explained that weekly meetings of staff and volunteers was a mechanism of ensuring that everyone would contribute to the information that could be collated and presented to the board, reducing the burden on individuals. In a similar vein, a volunteer forum was used to allow feedback from volunteers to have influence on how the charity operated. Participant 6 explained that information would be gathered from different groups in different ways to establish what their users needed, these methods were described as the “collective voices”. This came from a recognition that they needed to be more creative in how they would collect more data from their various user groups and feedback on what they had achieved for them. The collective voices initiative aim was to collect lots of information continuously from young people in effective informal and fun ways as opposed to say formal surveys. This consultation with beneficiaries allowed the charity to tie together what users were asking for with the outcomes that were being achieved and the reporting that was then provided back to both the board and funders. Indeed, the consultations were also used to direct the charity to the correct funding for different programmes of activity. Participant 6 identified the importance and often the funding requirement for people led consultations and expressed a belief that this was the way it should be for the sector. The process of consultation and delivering for users was not without its challenges though:

You can't apply for any lottery money unless you've got a consultation behind it that says yeah, we want that, because if it's not child or people led, they will give you nothing you know, so that's as it should be. I mean it should be like that but that can be quite difficult. You know when you're running things to get everything evaluated, also you go along and maybe make changes and then see what else is missing for developing it

and just it's that continuous, you know cycle of change really that's what you need to be looking at (Participant 6).

Participant 6 explained that part of their board relationship and accountability was providing opportunity for board members to volunteer to participate and observe what the charity did; trustees were also encouraged to attend charity events. It was also the case that previous volunteers had opportunity to serve on the board to bring that knowledge of charity operations. Participant 6 stated that it would have public events to engage multiple stakeholders such as the community, their volunteers, charity partners, funders, and local authority. This would be to update a wide range of stakeholders on what the charity was doing in the community.

Participant 7 began by thinking about the different structures or systems used by their funders and how they might connect to these different funders; on reflection she reasoned that this was always on her mind. Participant 7 explained that in addition to funding reports, the charity would invite funders to visit, observe and participate in their charity activities as a mechanism for passing on information. Participant 7 thought that reaching the local community with information was a difficult thing to do but explained that they had a desire to be inclusive of all people in the community and pondered about effective mechanisms such as leaflets, social media, or word of mouth.

Thinking about the local community, one of the hardest things in jobs sometimes actually can be reaching people. It's getting that information out there. It's letting people know what you're doing and why you're doing it. So, again, it's thinking about well how can we be completely inclusive of everybody who might be in this community and again so that's you thinking about the different ways that you can share information with people. Is it putting leaflets through people's doors? Is it using social media? Is it

by word of mouth? You know, so I suppose it is something that you're constantly thinking of (Participant 7).

Participant 7 was satisfied that they had a good internal system for recording financial information and could look back at the financial audit trail if required. Informal and formal staff meetings were used to update and be internally accountable to each other; and committee meetings and the AGM were informal ways of internal accountability. Participant 7 explained that management committees would meet once a month to review a report into community activities including financial details, impact information and any unusual events. The management committee included tenants, so it was felt the meetings were an effective mechanism of accountability for the local and wider community. Participant 7 expressed the view that their committee cared about the community since they were part of it; this she contrasted with others that had random people with no real connection or stake in the local community. Participant 7 described a range of mechanisms that helped them communicate with the local community such as community notice boards, social media, newsletters, and small community engagement events; it was felt that informal chats at these events was one of the most powerful ways of sharing information.

Participant 7 identified the “thriving places initiative” in Glasgow as an attempt to connect users and various local organisations. This involves a community connector to direct users to the appropriate services but also provides opportunity for local organisations to come together to share information on their current activities. Likewise, a monthly community breakfast was seen as a mechanism that could allow local organisations to connect and share information.

Participant 8 explained that financial accountability was being achieved through their process of sharing group financial summaries and breakdowns with the treasurer. Participant 8 stated that they would talk to their members about the finances at the AGM where they would present

and explain the accounts. Furthermore, it was stated that they would provide a copy of the accounts to anyone who asked for them. Participant 8 later explained that they had an open AGM for anyone to attend, but only members and their families showed interest. The AGM was also the platform to share some plans, although there were also informal chats with those that dropped-in to the premises. Members would also be provided with basic financial updates for example on spending on an ad-hoc basis. Participant 8 explained that they had effective processes of financial accountability in terms of audit and segregation of duties for financial control. Participant 8 seemed satisfied that the OSCAR accounts, although quite basic, told the financial story of where money had come from and where it had gone and stated the purpose and main activities of the organisation. However, Participant 8 felt that the annual report had limited data and information on what they did as an organisation, with only a very limited narrative element. The reporting requirement to OSCAR was seen as a positive since it kept the volunteers to a deadline for collating and submitting information; Participant 8 reflected on the fact that volunteers were renowned for being difficult to get information out of. It was explained that members would also see what was sent to OSCAR and this would cover important financial details of money in and money out that the members would be interested in. Participant 8 identified that the charity has a lack of activity on their website in terms of communicating their activities, achievements, and performance. However, the local press was sometimes used to highlight some of their achievements and successes. Participant 8 explained that events would be held to share information with members about activities; they would describe the activities and share photographs, but these events wouldn't contain any financial details. The issue of trust was raised again to explain why a financial aspect wasn't required to be covered at the events. Participant 8 pointed to more informal lines of communication with members through verbal updates and chats whenever members happened to be on the premises. There were occasional social media and email updates sent to parents for important updates. It was

explained that parents could judge the organisation through observation, and this led Participant 8 to believe that parents then knew the organisation was looking after the children's best interests. A combination of observation and feedback from children was seen as providing more than enough evidence and accountability to members:

Yeah, I think we're probably providing more than they need. And I suppose that is really because they are physically there and see what's going on. And the kids tell them what's going on and they know what their kids are participating in. They know that we're making good use of the resources that we have. And they see the dedication of the, you know, the Scout leaders turning up week in week out to do, you know, scouting with young children. It's quite a challenge, I've helped out when people were off and its bleeding hard work. So, you know, I think they know, they know that they come in and they see these kids all zooming around the room like they were on something. And they go, my God, I'm glad you're doing that and not me. So, I think from that point of view they are very appreciative of what is done, and you know the evidence of what we do is always with them because of the nature of the charity. Because the kids are doing something weekly (Participant 8).

In addition, it was noted that due to the nature of the charity, parent members also had opportunity to volunteer and participate in various scouting activities. Participant 8 surmised that they had probably used some of the available accountability mechanisms at various times: newsletters, social media and ongoing conversations were all used to share with members.

Participant 9 explained that many of the board members took part in the various activities of the charity so had a good understanding of what the charity did. However, he felt that there was some paranoia and suspicion when he himself volunteered to take part in charity activities. Participant 9 expressed concern over the ease at which accountability mechanisms could be

abused, stating that he had experienced situations where mechanisms were manipulated to control communication and accountability. Participant 9 added that under certain conditions such as personal agendas, dishonest individuals, and weak boards mechanisms could be perverted. It was suggested that there was a need to ensure that mechanisms had to be clear, honest, and consistent. Accountability mechanisms could for example have a good external appearance, but this could hide poor internal mechanisms and relationships:

But it's how you use them and what you do with them. Yeah, these all existed in theory. But you know, they were manipulated, in my opinion, in various ways to control the communication and the accountability. Yeah, I mean, these are all fine and dandy, but you know if you can pervert them, which is easily done, you know, if you've got an agenda, personal agenda or whatever agenda, you're a dishonest person and you've got a weak board, then you know, you can have all of these things and they're all great and you know, funders like them, the money comes in. But the reality is that you've sort of bullying staff and, you know, I'll play games with your board and, you know, say different things to different people and all these kinds of things. If you don't have clear, consistent, honest communication through these mechanisms, then you know, they might as well not exist at all (Participant 9).

Participant 10 pointed to the process of sharing financial accounts up through the hierarchy of the organisation as being their main system of accountability. It was explained that his role was key in facilitating this process of accounts sharing from local, to region, to district, to national and finally to the parent headquarters of the organisation. He later described the process of preparing accounts, auditing, and sending the accounts to OSCR as explicit accountability. It was felt that the process of preparing OSCR satisfied all financial accountability and that the external audit satisfied his own personal accountability to the group and everybody else. The audit gave him “peace of mind” in that he could avoid any accusations of fraud or

mismanagement. The accountability cycle was seen as being complete since the final accounts were available to members both on the website and at the AGM. Participant 10 explained that he was satisfied that the financial records and accounts provided good evidence of how money from subscriptions and fundraising was being spent on their various scouting activities. There was an example provided of where he had interacted with the council to verify the accounting processes they followed, and he was clearly pleased that he had evidence of good accounting processes to show them. It was felt that their good proper accounting practices including the end point of audited accounts were in place to stand up to challenge or scrutiny:

I was lucky that I had the robustness of my accounts, fully audited, that when it didn't go away and then we had a councillor coming to us and saying this accusation has been made and I am entitled to see this. I was able to say as the accountant, there's the accounts, and by the way they have officially been audited by someone who's external to the organisation, and if you want to see there you go everything is listed month by month. All the statements were there. So, I had the evidence and that made me feel good because I knew then that we were able to take any scrutiny (Participant 10)

It was later explained that the wider organisation had an information system where members could access the accounts. Additional details of activities were shared with parents through the AGM and their newsletters. Participant 10 commented that invitation to the AGM would also extend to important stakeholders such as the local church who provided their premises. The AGM was seen as the critical platform for answering stakeholder questions and providing stakeholders with the information that they needed. Participant 10 felt that grant and funding applications weren't too problematic since in most cases it was simply a case of attaching a copy of their accounts. It was also reasoned that the same information source of financial records and accounts could be used to meet the needs or demands of various stakeholders including the internal scouting hierarchy or the external regulator. Participant 10 conceded that

on occasion there could be specific details required by a funder, but the information was mostly derived from the accounts, and this wasn't too much of a burden. Participant 10 later expressed strong belief that meeting OSCR requirements could also meet any internal requirements for internal financial accountability; OSCR accounts were seen as a good thing:

Yes, as long as I meet my OSCR requirements, that's the key one. If I meet my OSCR requirements, then I meet my scout requirements from anybody from the top and all the way down as soon as I do my accounts and OSCR goes that's in the right format. That's me. I've met my requirements. I don't have to do anything extra for anybody unless it's maybe a grant I have to specify. But other than that, that's enough for every stakeholder. So, it's good the fact that we are part of OSCR, it really is. That's my accountability (Participant 10).

Participant 10 described the website as being a good mechanism for sharing general information about their activities, and private social media channels to share more detailed information with parent members. Newsletters were used to share stories with the community and to encourage new members. Participant 10 went on to explain that the children themselves acted as good mechanisms for sharing information since they would share their experiences with school friends and their parents.

Participant 11 identified the AGM as an opportunity to share the annual accounts with the members. Participant 11 explained that monthly information meetings were used to open a two-way discussion with their members. In addition, they had monthly board meetings to discuss the monthly accounts, discuss the activities of their members and review their targets. Participant 11 believed that "everything" was shared with their board through their board meetings; whilst a monthly newsletter was used to inform members about their activities such as survey results. Overall, it was felt that it was a challenge to keep up regular communication

with the members and the board. This extended to their use of social media platforms where they felt the strain of trying to use various platforms to meet various stakeholder preferences. The charity website was also viewed as an effective mechanism to report to people and tell them about their activities, however this was a significant burden on resources since it took time and expertise to set up and maintain. Participant 11 suggested that workshop events were very useful for detailing their activities and explaining their issues to wider stakeholders. However, there scepticism about the value of larger events held for the sector such as their autism awareness week. Likewise Participant 11 identified an event held at parliament where an MP would be invited to attend to hear about their activities and issues for the sector; it was believed that the event didn't achieve much in raising their profile. Participant 11 expressed belief that they did need some form of PR so would submit articles for magazines and journals to communicate their cause to a wider audience. Participant 11 stated that anyone that gave them money would receive a written report and sometimes this would include some limited data on the attendances as measurement of their activity and output.

Participant 12 expressed a belief that grant making charities should be open to receiving more information from applicants and be making better use of funding application information. It was believed that funding applications could be used as an important feedback mechanism and a learning resource for other organisations:

But actually, you know, they don't want to have a type of complaints procedure cause goodness me, why should an applicant be allowed to suggest how the application process could be easier or smoother or more interesting. So, I have been involved with organisations that are absolutely closed and equally they would ask organisations for reports on how the funding would have been spent. But they're not doing anything with that information. So, you just had those filing cabinets of information of information from charities, instead of thinking right so we could probably have some guidance on

if you are setting up a part-time therapy studio in whatever therapy service. Then you probably want a part-time member of staff, you probably need two other key workers. You know, we could have built up a useful sort of vault of information if you like or resource that other organisations could have used and perhaps saved them from reinventing the wheel (Participant 12).

Participant 12 explained that they would have board meetings on the premises of their grant recipients to see what they did first-hand and be “very actively engaged” with those that they fund. It was important to understand what a charity does, and they could explain this to their own funders; it was explained that they wished to be involved with the services and the families. Participant 12 added that the grant application would also ask charities to share with others in their network as a means of snowballing the grant making from one organisation to others in the sector. Participant 12 was confident that the organisation was using all the possible communication and accountability mechanisms available; but identified open AGMs as a potentially very useful mechanism that they did not currently use. It was reasoned that the open AGM could be used to invite many grant recipients and other stakeholders such as communities and the public.

Participant 13 began by explaining that in addition to a financial walkthrough every year, members would also be spoken to on a regular basis about how money was being used on mission related areas. It was commented that not much financial detail would be given on operating costs, but they would make people aware. Participant 13 later explained that members would receive monthly e-news as a formal communication about events. The Church had annual “business meeting,” which was effectively their AGM to discuss financial and asset resources; the meeting was strictly members only. A second meeting was also run to discuss activities or “mission related” matters; this was also members only. Open public meetings were something that the charity would not do. Participant 13 pointed to monthly leadership meetings

as being an important mechanism to share information and be accountable. It was felt that it was of significance to the members to know that these meetings were taking place to discuss operational matters. Participant 13 later reflected that the members may however not be aware that the quarterly board meetings took place. Participant 13 explained that an important part of their work was funding other people and groups across the world; they sought feedback on what these groups were doing with the funds and would feedback to their membership. The feedback would be part of a Church visit and be irregular, around once every two to three years; further finance would be granted based on the information shared at these feedback visits. Participant 13 pointed to the fact that they had in past years encouraged their ministry areas to produce reports on their activities to share with the wider Church, but that these hadn't been used since Covid. Participant 13 commented on the mix of formal and informal communication and accountability approaches that they utilised with stakeholder groups. There were challenges in keeping track of the information; this was something that the charity had to constantly wrestle with:

Yeah, and discussion with people, you know, so there's a thing going on with a family who live in Africa just now and we are speaking with them and we're speaking with that external organisation that help us with them. But that's done partly on some things that we have to fill out with them formally, but also chat about and then backwards and forwards with family in Africa. Some is recorded formally, some isn't. Then yes, a mix you just have to kind of constantly think of what's formally written down, what's just informally spoken of. And yeah, some mix of things, but definitely a challenge on managing information and then accessing information is definitely a challenge (Participant 13).

Participant 13 explained that it could be hard work to encourage volunteer stakeholders to collect data and produce the information they required; he then questioned whether volunteers

should be asked to do such things given their time constraint and effort they expended on charitable activities. The charity preferred to reduce workload and ask people to share information face-to-face verbally rather than produce formal reports. It was reasoned that he could also see the benefits of relationship building with face-to-face communication. Participant 13 identified their Church service as a good opportunity and forum for sharing information about activities with members and that they could do this every week. Participant 13 believed they were not obliged to share much information via social media and identified challenges here in terms of who would be available to do this, and that the nature of social media could “cause its own problems”.

5.2.3 Being Transparent

Participant 1 explained that the Board would look for regular feedback on performance or effectiveness in their influence over policy and influencing system change or the impact on individual lives. The charity would use evaluation type information to assess the impact on individuals such as measuring differences or improvements in people’s lives. It was felt, however, that the charity was not as formal or as purposeful in how it dealt with data and information on outcomes and impact; the reasoning for this was mainly due to the size of the charity. Understanding outcomes for beneficiaries was important to them but believed that things could be done better. Participant 1 added later that he considered what they do to be complicated, so it was difficult to measure performance. The limiting factor of expertise within the charity constrained their ability to assess their performance. Furthermore, it was explained that he had experienced negative effects of trying to integrate sophisticated performance measures and questioned the need. Quantitative data and analysis were identified as an area of weakness; whereas they had better ability to tell stories and talk about their outcomes. It was

suggested that there was need for balance between quantitative and qualitative and complex and simple.

We've learned that the more sophisticated you get sometimes the harder it actually is, and sometimes actually becomes a bit meaningless. You know, the getting a balance of quantitative and qualitative. And I think it's easier to get the quality of some things, you know, quantitative can be harder. But and I don't think we've cracked the quantitative, I think we're quite good at telling stories of the changes that people have experienced and talking about the outcomes and categorising that but not so much, maybe in terms of the quantitative side (Participant 1).

Participant 1 confessed that they didn't always follow through in terms of having a proper assessment of the impact of their initiatives, feeling there was a need to formally assess the level of success, but they didn't have the time to do it. Again, it was added that assessing performance, especially long-term outcomes, was a difficult thing to do. It was felt that the board needed to be better at understanding their impact since it was critical to show this evidence to beneficiaries and funders. It was supposed that they required an evaluation and learning framework for this. Participant 1 expressed sincere regret at not having ways to effectively share their successes.

Participant 2 pointed to the European Excellence Model for guiding what data would be collected within her charities. Being clear on purpose, strategy and policies would inform that data that would be required to deliver on these strategies, for example the financial data required to deliver on the financial strategy. Other important areas of data collection and analysis would be around beneficiary satisfaction or the perceptions of stakeholders around the quality of the services the organisation was delivering. Participant 2 later added that data must be managed in order that the organisation achieved the right outputs and outcomes; there must

also be ways of measuring these for example using social return on investment (SROI). However, this was qualified by adding that SROI is used only by a few organisations since the measurements can be overly complicated. Added to this the problem of procedures and policies for storing and clearing data were described as unknown areas for a lot of organisations. Participant 2 found that there was a tendency to not communicate external data such as stakeholder perceptions of the charity including what the organisation was like to work with. There was a strong belief that if organisations failed to monitor data on these external perceptions, then it could be ruinous for them. Likewise, she felt there was a failure to have actual formal accounting and reporting of people's internal perceptions within the organisation. Participant 2 felt from her vast experience of working in the sector that appropriate data collection and measurement was an area of weakness that was prevalent in the third sector.

Participant 3 felt that the committee members had a desire to be transparent both personally and collectively since they did not want to appear to be mismanaging money and they wished to avoid any accusations to this affect. Participant 3 pointed to the financial information collected and collated by the organisation as well as data on member engagement with their service; they also collected data and information on some aspects of the charity performance and the data allowed them to track and plan for future activities. It was believed that because the organisation was small, they did not need sophisticated software to handle their data. Participant 3 suggested that for any external reporting they would tend to include more information than was required, especially if the information was already collated for another purpose. When asked further about the use of annual accounts Participant 3 explained that there was an additional need to adapt to a more straightforward format for people at the AGM; it was almost the same information but had to be translated for a different audience, primarily their membership. Participant 3 observed that that there was a spectrum of information from the stories told to lay people to what had to be lodged formally. It was the job of the committee to

translate for people and help them understand it. It was felt that too much information was shared on the website, describing this as “overkill” and meaning that people would have difficulty finding what they needed. Participant 3 explained that sharing too much information would baffle people; it was better to target information to give people what they asked for:

I sometimes think the certainly the website it's very busy because our chair likes to put everything up there. It's almost a little bit overkill cause then it's difficult to find maybe the thing you want to find, and I sometimes think if you share too much information it can baffle people whereas if they get exactly what they asked for then they get that and they know what to look for within that (Participant 3).

Participant 4 explained that their service and client information was extremely sensitive and potentially public affecting. However, they would have “planned breaches of confidentiality” agreed with clients where sensitive information could be shared with wider system stakeholders such as police and legal authorities. Sensitivity of information was clearly a major concern for the charity and chief executive, but he acknowledged the need to share with relevant stakeholders:

So, the information we get, we share with relevant bodies, so sharing is really, really important. That's been difficult because the sensitivity, there's been times I've had to get on the train with the documents because I didn't trust anyone else to take them out and head somewhere to give that information out because it's so sensitive and we were just uncomfortable sending everything out in a big email or something else (Participant 4).

Participant 4 described the collection of data and information from users as a journey from simple to specific data collection on their issues; data was used to measure performance with pre and post evaluation questionnaires. The primary data could be broken down for a variety

of purposes such as tracking longitudinal data to show the impact of the service for external stakeholders. Additional explanations were also offered when needed for example where clients had very complex issues. Participant 4 was quite certain that they had the data to share, but they could do better in terms of collating the data and thinking creatively about how to use it. Honesty was seen as an important element of accountability feeling that they should be honest with their data for example revealing and explaining any areas of poor performance. They felt that overall, they had ways of measuring their success, but the information around client cases could be extremely complex with a full spectrum of clients and client data within their database. It was felt that it was important to share this detailed information and be able to handle some intense scrutiny from powerful stakeholders such as legal authorities. Participant 4 recounted a negative experience from sharing too much information in the local media: new board members were being attracted to the charity because their funding arrangements were now widely known and, in this case, the new board members attempted to take control of the charity. The charity also has concerns or reservations in communicating what they do more widely since they fear that they do not have the capacity to meet substantial increase in user demand for their services.

Participant 5 expressed belief that detailed financial information would be the most important dimension to collect and present to the board. Financial narratives within the annual accounts were also important to explain charity financial position; it was felt it was important to explain apparent failures to avoid negative funder reactions. It was later explained that every board should be provided with the latest finances compared to budgets. Participant 5 added that financial information was often seen as boring by some board members and knowing this the onus was on the charity to make this information more engaging for example through summaries and colour coding. Participant 5 went on to explain that she had witnessed “horrible management accounts” that were neither helpful nor user-friendly. It was reasoned that a board

could be more effective in its conversations and decisions if the input papers from the charity were interesting and engaging. Participant 5 had found in her experience that most charities seemed to enjoy data and statistics related to their service provision and outputs, they loved the “soft stuff” like narratives or case study examples that would explain the success of their interventions. This was seen as a great thing by the boards, but there was often concern that charities were less interested in “boring procedural stuff” such as monitoring their bank balances. Participant 5 later reasoned that charities had lots of data but were not accomplished at showing it in an impactful way for example in their funding applications. There was sometimes some limited cost-benefit analysis, but there was a failure to incorporate engaging features such as timelines and infographics:

‘So, one thing that charities are rubbish at is actually they've got all of this data and it probably goes back years, but they're not, they're not skilled and I wouldn't be either and actually so how can you show that in a really, really impactful way? So, some charities do a little bit of cost benefit analysis. So, they'll say this is the cost of our intervention, it cost £2000 all in you know, to get this young guy back on the straight and narrow and maybe if you show he's engaging with school or something like that, right. And then you look at the cost benefit analysis of and maybe the police getting involved maybe and being removed from home, all of this and of course that number is going to be bigger. So, if you're using that sort of data and putting it in your funding application, I think you're going to get more attention. Charities are not very good at showing their data in the most powerful way. You know they just leave it as you know, 19 young people or whatever. But they need to show maybe a timeline, or you know just make it really interesting. And again, one page and if you can use infographics and whatever all the better, they're not so good at that they're not skilled at that (Participant 5).

It was stressed that charities needed to make better use of their data to convey the magnitude of the problem that required funding. In general, it was thought that charities were mostly

meeting the information needs, but it could be done in a more effective way that involved less work. Organisations needed to make their communications concise and easy to read, getting to their point quickly for the stakeholder audiences; the communications should be “short and snappy” and employ visual aids. Participant 5 felt that charities could be more open with their funders when things go wrong. Funders would understand and be sympathetic if situations were explained to them as early as possible; it was important that charities were brave enough to open an honest dialogue.

Participant 6 identified that the charity had a need to identify their outputs but also their bigger impact or outcomes for themselves internally and for their funders. Participant 6 explained that the charity would use “feedback frames” with beneficiaries to measure aspects of their charity performance. Participant 6 raised the issue of sensitive information around poverty and hungry children, stating that sharing this type of message would be viewed badly in their community. Children and parents would not wish to be identified as poor so the charity had to be very careful with the messages and information they would share via social media and other ways these messages could be accessed by the community. This would be in contrast with the more private communication with funders where the issue of poverty and deprivation could be described. In this respect, Participant 6 felt that the charity was restricted in the output and outcomes information they could share via their website and had to be careful in terms of who might access this information within their annual review. It was the view of the charity that the Council for example were careless in how they communicated this issue of poverty and hunger within their community. Participant 6 believed that they were being careful with the information that they shared, they were not lacking transparency in this respect, they were just being sensitive. It was believed that there was an obligation to treat sensitive information appropriately since people trusted their organisation and they wished to maintain this trust. Participant 6 concluded by saying that it was difficult for them to reach different people with

the right information and messages. Participant 6 believed that it was important for the charity and staff to record as much information as they could to prepare for future communication requirements such as what might be needed by the board or to compile their annual review.

Participant 7 explained that they felt a need to gather information to be ready for any future requests or demands for information. It was felt that it was a lot of work to gather information for different funders including different measurements and statistics. In addition, there was an awkwardness when this required the charity to collect a lot of personal information from their users. Data and information were something that the charity would often discuss, and they felt that streamlining wasn't possible due to funder information requirements. Participant 7 was confident that they had ways of measuring outcomes and indicators that they could evaluate themselves against. It was explained that less formal means of evaluation was required since people found surveys to be difficult. Progress and performance were also tracked using individual case studies. The charity would use engaging or interactive methods for children for carrying out group evaluations and they felt that they had established their own ways of collecting data. Participant 7 explained that they would compile their data they collected from clients, their performance data, and feed this into their funding applications.

Participant 8 felt that they didn't have much in the way of data and information around activities and performance and seen this as an issue for the organisation. It was explained that the board would attempt to discuss less obvious areas of spending and investment with their members such as refurbishments. However, Participant 8 believed that these things should be communicated in more formal ways other than casual conversations. Participant 8 commented that they would tend not to broadcast potentially sensitive issues such as members being unable to afford camps and clothing. There was good work and outcomes being achieved in this respect, but they had to be careful about sharing information that could be upsetting to individuals.

Participant 9 described the breakdown in financial accountability between the charity and the board, pointing to the fact that the board would only receive annual accounts rather than the detailed management accounts that were frequently requested. However, Participant 9 added later that the charity did have good quality data on their impact and successes in the community and could tell a good story in this respect. Participant 9 observed that there would often be enough data and information to meet funding requirements, but this was kept from the board, which he felt was totally wrong. Participant 9 questioned the motives of some organisations of moving away from full financial accounting reporting to a simpler approach that was allowed by OSCR; he had concerns that this was simply an opportunity to avoid robust accountability.

Participant 10 explained that in addition to financial data the charity, mostly through himself in role as treasurer, held other data such as data on assets and data on risk assessments for their insurance purposes. Participant 10 described the process of recording and coding all financial transactions to show where and what money was spent on; he felt this was of critical importance. Participant 10 believed strongly that the board and himself as treasurer were very transparent since they could explain where money had gone and could show this at the AGM. However, it was felt that members and any other person needed a good reason to see the ongoing accounts and had suggested to them in the past that they should wait to see the full audited accounts at the AGM. Participant 10 explained that there were very few requests to see ongoing financial records and accounts and put this down to the trust people had in the organisation. Participant 10 later expressed belief that the process of preparing the audited accounts for public publication by OSCR equated to transparency for their organisation. Participant 10 explained that a major part of his role was to pull the financial information together in a consistent and coherent form for presentation to the audience at the AGM. It was seen as being crucial to prepare and adapt accounts to an understandable format for a diverse range of stakeholders:

I prepare their accounts. I put them into a format that people can understand. Now, that's crucial for me is understanding because I'm not dealing with accountants. I am dealing with people who just want to know how much money did they bring in, how much money went out and the money we brought in, where did it come from and where did it go? It's the annual general meeting is the big one for me, for getting the most information over to the most stakeholders, because at the AGM of any organisation for the scouts you should have your parents there, when they turn up, you'll have your group executive, your stakeholders from the church. There will usually be a district rep there as well, usually a district commissioner. You'll have all the leaders, and anybody else that wants to come to it. So, anybody can join in. Anybody can come along to it. So, I've got to present these accounts in a format that I am not bamboozling them with numbers. I should be able to explain all that in a simple format (Participant 10).

Participant 10 surmised that the board and treasurer were accountable for answering specific questions around finances and spending at the AGM. Participant 10 felt that there was a need to safeguard financial information since he had experienced situations where others from within the wider scout organisation had attempted to access their own groups finances. In addition, he had also experienced situations where local organisations would pressure the group to make donations when it was known that they had a healthy bank balance. Rather than providing up-to-date current financial detail it was now preferred to direct people to the historical annual accounts for example through OSCR.

Participant 10 pointed to the sensitivity around some of the funding and outcomes, pointing to the fact that they did not wish to highlight any members that were being subsidised through funding for social deprivation. It was felt that this made the outcomes less clear but was necessary to protect their members. Similarly, it was felt that the organisation had to be careful

about sharing information since they were dealing with children, so this could often limit the detail they disclosed about people and activities.

Participant 11 explained that it was difficult to collect data from their membership given the age demographic, their disabilities, and their lack of IT knowledge. Participant 11 pointed to some basic output or activity data that they collected and collated such as attendance records, their log of phone call enquiries and their meetings with people. It was added that they were able to provide this basic engagement with service data if required and this was seen as part of the charity's accountability. Participant 11 expressed some concerns around the organisations ability to measure performance and in fact uncertainty around what performance meant for the charity, it was felt that it would be difficult to measure the quality of their service:

I think we did a kind of performance measure when we had the Big Lottery money. And it was kind of a difficult thing, isn't it? It's a very odd thing performance because it's the quality of it. So, if you said 10 people came to a meeting, is that good or bad? If 30 came, is that good or bad? If 30 come and it was boring was that bad? But if 10 came and it was really good was that good? So, performance measure is odd, an odd thing to do. Yeah, I mean, we're not making anything. Uh, we're not producing anything, so that would be hard to measure and we're not trying to sell anything (Participant 11).

It was reasoned that ultimately the onus was on the funder to decide how the charity had performed. Participant believed that performance measures in the wider charity sector could be misleading and stated that long term impact measures would be of most value.

Participant 12 expressed a belief that grant making charities should be open to receiving more information from applicants and be making better use of funding application information. It was believed that funding applications could be used as an important feedback mechanism and a learning resource for other organisations:

But actually, you know, they don't want to have a type of complaints procedure cause goodness me, why should an applicant be allowed to suggest how the application process could be easier or smoother or more interesting. So, I have been involved with organisations that are absolutely closed and equally they would ask organisations for reports on how the funding would have been spent. But they're not doing anything with that information. So, you just had those filing cabinets of information of information from charities, instead of thinking right so we could probably have some guidance on if you are setting up a part-time therapy studio in whatever therapy service. Then you probably want a part-time member of staff, you probably need two other key workers. You know, we could have built up a really useful sort of vault of information if you like or resource that other organisations could have used and perhaps saved them from reinventing the wheel (Participant 12).

Participant 12 expressed the view that organisations in the sector did not have good data and information systems. It was observed that charities she had been involved with would often have separate systems for communicating, holding member details and finance so questioned whether they could process and present their data effectively. Overall, it was believed that organisations in the sector were collecting data, but they didn't understand it or do much with it. It was explained that this was a serious issue for the smaller organisations in the sector who were often “blissfully unaware” of their data. Larger organisations with full time staff members were much better at data analysis and reporting since they had more effective people and systems. However, it was stated that whilst software systems could be good at generating reports on outputs, there was still a lack of focus on larger impactful outcomes across the whole sector. Participant 12 felt that the funding process could be helpful in this respect since it would often force organisations to think carefully about their data as part of their evaluations. Participant 12 explained that due to their values and ethos they had to manage the

communications very carefully by people in the charity to ensure consistency in style of language and their charity message.

Participant 13 felt that most activity information for example attendance would be something that was kept within the different activity groups and wouldn't normally be something that was more widely shared. It was reasoned that others didn't need this information and the organisation wasn't particularly guided or informed by the numbers. This was made clear when asked if some data about activities and participant numbers might be shared or discussed by the board:

No, not particularly, no, we do have informal conversations with the leaders, all the different activities, but we don't hold reports and we don't host statistics per se. Uh we're not measuring. It's not important how many people come to things necessarily. That's not a primary thing for us. We're more concerned with how is it going and what sort of spiritual impact is happening as opposed to yeah, there's 30 kids at this, there's 20 kids at that, or there's 25 people go to the café every week. We're not so driven by numbers (Participant 13).

Participant 13 stressed that spiritual impact or quality was more important than numbers and quantification. However, it was later explained that despite difficulties and some reservations with measuring performance they did evaluate with a quite informal evaluation questionnaire. Also, it was felt that their area leaders should seek to understand how things were going through informal discussion. Participant 13 expressed a strong belief that people could be overwhelmed with too much information reasoning that balance was needed in terms of thinking about how much information to communicate to inform people. In addition, there was a need for them to consider balance of communication given their limited resources. Participant 13 later questioned the culture of constant communication and didn't think that this was necessary for leaders and

organisations. It was felt that organisations were under too much pressure to say too much and questioned if people wanted to be overwhelmed with the volume of information; it was something the charity would resist:

I think we're quite content, you know, because you've gotta keep that balance of, you know, we've got limited resources and time in terms of communication. And I think there's a danger that, you know, in that sort of very consumer orientated culture that it feels as if sometimes leadership teams or organisations are just constantly having to feed people information and I don't think that's necessary. I don't think we think it's necessary, I don't think that's what people want really. I think there's a kind of pressure to say too much and it's people don't want it; they're overwhelmed with information. But we are an open door so if people want to find out they can come and ask. I don't think we should be spending all our time writing reports and informing people, you know the 24/7 culture is just, we would push against that. It's not good. It's not healthy (Participant 13).

Participant 13 explained that much of the information that would be sent to members would be done an ad-hoc basis when required although they would ensure that they would receive the formal accounts and reports. Information for external stakeholders would also be ad-hoc and be in the form of informal discussion or chat.

5.2.4 Stakeholder Apathy

Participant 3 felt that lots of things were communicated to the membership but had a sense that the membership lacked interest and rarely responded. It was her belief that the membership only wanted basic information related to activities that they could engage with; detailed financial information was of interest to the committee but not to the membership. It was explained that the members didn't appear to have any interest in charity information, but it was thought that they would become interested if something appeared to be wrong or indeed if the information provision was suddenly halted. Participant 3 surmised that members were interested in the solvency and continuation of the charity, but they were not interested in the nuts-and-bolts details of what happens behind the scenes. Likewise, it was felt that despite the wealth of information published to the website there was little engagement other than by those that might already be engaged or interested.

Participant 5 suggested that although it was important to reach out to stakeholder funders it was still the case that funders would often decline invitations or not respond since they themselves were too busy.

Participant 7 noted that initiatives to connect local organisations together through "thriving places initiative" could only be successful to extent that the organisations would engage, there were many that would not engage or commit. It was commented that organisations often preferred to do their own thing rather than committing to partnerships and the wider information sharing this brought about.

Participant 8 showed some disappointment that their members didn't engage much for example with the AGM but reasoned that this was largely due to the trust shown in them and a belief that the organisation and its committee had their interests at heart. It was explained that there were attempts to share information with members, but they rarely engaged or asked questions;

again, it was believed that this apparent disinterest was because of the trust they had in the board. Parents seemed happy to re-nominate the committee each year, so this was also taken as a sign of trust. Participant 8 described some of the events where copies of the annual report would be made available but noticed that most members would not look at the accounts, they were not interested. Participant 8 questioned whether the fact that their accounts were audited contributed to trust since she was unsure if members were aware of the audit process; something that they might only know if they looked at the accounts. Participant 8 then pondered on whether OSCR accounts should be shared before meetings to prompt members to come along and ask questions. Likewise, the AGM was unrestricted access for the wider community and other scouting affiliates, but only attracted those that were directly involved in the organisation. Participant 8 explained that they had more successful engagement when the AGM was combined with other events, but in large she felt that people just let them get on with things, which she identified could cause potential problems in the future:

So, we've tried to combine it with another event. So, we, for example, we had a slide show type of thing and then it was the AGM after it so that they would come for the slide show and possibly a few more would stay behind for coffee and things like that. And that's the only way we're managed to entice any more than the usual handful that come along just for the hell of it I suppose or maybe because they are genuinely interested in how we spend the money. But as I see it, they just leave us to get on with it, which is probably not a great thing because it's alright for just now for the people that we have, but if that was to change you know if they didn't have as much integrity. So, I suppose there's maybe that kind of inbuilt you know the type of folk that get involved are likely to be quite decent folk anyway. But I do sometimes think it's just the auditor and me (Participant 9).

Participant 9 recounted his experience of witnessing a lack interest and engagement amongst his fellow board members, explaining that the deputy chair for example was more interested in personal issues. Much of the lack of interest was put down to inability of the board to understand certain processes and the financial data; he observed that the rest of the board were happy in their ignorance. Overall, Participant 9 felt that there was a lack of demand for information from the rest of his board. This was not helped by the fact that information processes weren't made clear within the organisation and at best this led to papers that were hastily prepared at short notice for the board.

Participant 10 explained that not a lot of parents would come to their AGM; it was reasoned that the attitude of the parents was to pay their subscription for activities, and they weren't really interested beyond this. Participant 10 seemed satisfied that the accounts were available and that parents could see the value they received from their membership if they would take an interest in reviewing the accounts:

Not a lot of the parents come to the AGM. Their attitude is sort of my kids go to the scouts one day a week. That's it. I'm rid of them for a week. I'll pay my subs. So, I'm not really interested. You get the odd one or two, and I've never had any questions on that. But any parent that chooses to analyse our accounts, they'll see that actually they're getting very good value because their kids are getting more out of it than they actually put in. And that's all because we're able to fundraise. It's just all, and yes, so parents can see if they want, we're very transparent. If a parent comes to us and says where's the money going then we can tell them, we can show them at the AGM (Participant 10).

Participant 11 explained that the charity had limited contact with their funders pointing to one funder that required a six-month review to tell them what they had done “and then they go

away”. Participant 11 felt quite strongly that no-one had a significant interest in their organisation beyond their obvious internal and external stakeholders; believing that people had more interest in high-profile charities or those with more interesting and compelling missions. Government was identified as not having a solution for their issues, so they had experienced a lack of engagement; the charity expected government action or intervention rather than just raising awareness. There was a feeling that although small organisations had some power to exert pressure, progress was slow, and government were not listening or responding. At local level, Participant 11 felt that they attended as many council meetings as they could to share information but felt frustration that it led to no progress on their issue and often were just paid lip service to have the appearance of a consultation.

Participant 13 reflected on the fact that not all members would turn up to meetings or read things so described information sharing as a “battle of information to members”. The participant reasoned that they at least made sure that they would get the formal accounts and reports across to the membership.

5.2.5 Summary

The empirical findings reveal that small charities attempt to prioritise their stakeholders, but this is a perplexing task; the number, variety and fluidity of stakeholders can overwhelm small charities. Charities recognise that the relationship with their board which includes their accountability is critical, and see that failures occur where the relationship breaks down. The findings show that member-based organisations prioritise accountability to their members since they are viewed as essential to their survival and their reason for existing. The findings show that small charities can be overwhelmed by the diverse needs and report formats demanded by their funders. Charities believe that there is an increased need for open and honest dialogue with funders to negotiate and seek compromise on reporting obligations. The findings also

provide evidence that there is a trend towards more positive engagement with funder evaluations and reports since they have perceived benefit of charity learning and improvement.

Advocacy charities seek wider sector influence so seek to build relationships to collaborate with sector partners and government. The findings demonstrate that charities are mindful of both potential benefits of partnership with sector support groups and other charities and potential drawbacks of competition for funds in the sector. The findings highlight the importance that small charities place upon accountability to their beneficiaries often consulting and collaborating to guide their activities and feedback on activities and local impact. Trust is seen as the key component in charity-beneficiary relationships, trust is seen as intrinsic but also viewed as something that can be enhanced through information sharing.

The findings demonstrate that small charities are using a wide range of mechanisms to connect and share information with their stakeholders. Charities are employing a mix of formal and informal, and public and private accountability mechanisms. However, the findings suggest that charities require more understanding of why and how different accountability mechanisms should be used. Charities perceive that trust on the part of stakeholder groups reduces the need for accountability and accountability mechanisms. The findings show that small charities weigh up the cost-benefit of different accountability mechanisms and appreciate the need for increased consultation with stakeholders to set communication expectations. Consultations, however, are a major resource challenge for small charities. The findings demonstrate that whilst funder reports and returns can be burdensome, charities could further consider how the same information can be adapted to meet multiple user needs.

The findings reveal that internal management accounts, board meetings and minutes are viewed as essential internal accountability mechanisms. In addition, the annual report and AGM are viewed as vital for internal accountability between charity, charity board, volunteers, and

members and to a certain extent to the wider community. However, the findings suggest there is further potential to use the annual report and AGM to engage stakeholder groups. Social media is widely used by small charities to raise general awareness, widen reach and influence yet charities have concerns over information disclosure via this media. Social media presence is also a burden on valuable resources of money, time, and people in the small charity sector. The findings reveal that events and festivals are being used by many charities to allow stakeholders to observe and participate in charity activities but could be more widely used in the sector to engage charity boards, partners, and communities. Likewise, the findings show that networking initiatives to connect charities, partners and beneficiaries are under-employed in the sector.

The findings show that small charities often fail to manage and understand their data. Many small charities do engage in simplistic performance measurement but there are various levels of competency and expertise across the sector. The findings reveal that many charities share basic statistics and data on outputs with their boards, but charities tend to be better at producing qualitative accounts of their activity and performance. Charities and their treasurers are satisfied that OSCR processes fulfil their financial accountability to internal and external stakeholders and are mindful of a need to be financially transparent to avoid accusations of wrongdoing. Small charities believe that trust reduces demands for information and accountability including the demands from members for financial accountability. The findings reveal that charities perceive the need to adapt their reports and information to meet different stakeholder needs for example producing more accessible financial reports for their membership. However, some charities acknowledge that they are not always effective at doing this.

The findings demonstrate that sensitivity of information is a concern in the small charity sector with charities having to judge what, when and who they share sensitive information with; this

may place some limits on transparency. Trust is identified by charities as motivating protection of sensitive data and information. Charities are mindful that there are drawbacks from sharing too much information such as overwhelming stakeholders with excess volume or the potential for people to take advantage of their financial situation. Some charities also hold the belief that there is too much pressure on the small charity sector to share information given their limited resource.

The findings show that stakeholder apathy is prevalent in the small charity sector with many charities frustrated at the lack of engagement and interest amongst stakeholders. Charities do not have a solution but are having some success by combining more engaging events with information dissemination. The reasons are believed to be lack of interest in the finer details of operations and finance, lack of knowledge, and a lack desire to learn on part of beneficiaries, members, and indeed charity boards. Charities are failing to engage in partnerships and networking due to narrow self-interests or simply lack of time resource to commit to sharing information. The findings suggest however that some stakeholder groups such as charity boards and funders express desire to attend charity events or AGMs.

Chapter 6: Discussion

6.1 Introduction

The research set out to explore the issue of small charity accountability. The literature highlights that several characteristics and forms of accountability are being created and enacted across the charitable sector. It is evident that charities have various types of stakeholder relationship and often employ a wide range of accountability mechanisms to discharge their accountability to stakeholders. Furthermore, existing studies show that charities often prioritise some stakeholder groups over others and stakeholder salience produces dominant forms of accountability in the sector. Upward accountability to powerful funders and regulators is identified as being dominant in the wider charity sector; however, balanced or more holistic forms of accountability are also found. Theoretical literature provides further understanding of charity stakeholder relationships by employing both stewardship and agency models to explain the principal-agent relationships in the sector (Puyvelde, 2012). However, it is clear from the literature that the nature of stakeholder relationships, characteristics of accountability and use of accountability mechanisms are an under-researched area in the small charity sector. In this chapter the evidence from the empirical findings is compared to this literature that is largely focussed on the wider charity sector.

The chapter begins its reporting of results in Section 2 by discussing perceptions of accountability in the small charity sector, analysing the ways in which charities begin to identify their internal and external accountabilities to various stakeholder groups. The chapter also discusses the ways in which charities begin to understand the concept of accountability and the nature of charity accountability.

In Section 3 the chapter then critically examines the ways in which small charities prioritise and build their relationships with stakeholders. The nature of stakeholder accountability

relationships is described for the charitable sector including the accountability mechanisms used to discharge accountability. Several issues are identified for discussion from both literature and findings, namely trust building, transparent information, and the challenge of stakeholder apathy.

The discussion of the need and ability of organisations in the sector to change, to develop and improve their accountability to stakeholders, and respond to wider environmental challenges, is carried forward to inform the conclusions and recommendations. The discussion concludes by addressing the issue of how small charities can balance their accountabilities given their limited resources.

6.2 Perceptions of Accountability

This section explores the findings around the participants' broad perceptions of accountability and is compared with the charity accountability literature reviewed in previous chapters. There are three main thematic areas to the empirical findings: identifying external accountability, identifying internal accountability, and forming understandings of accountability.

6.2.1 Identifying external accountabilities

The empirical findings show that charities and their boards identify a variety of funders to whom they are accountable including government, local authorities, subscribing members, trust funds and private donations; accountability to funders is seen as fundamental and obvious. Accountability extends to the public, especially where charities hold some public funds. Certainly, there is evidence of upward accountability to funding providers and government in the small charity sector as identified by Baur and Schmitz (2012) and Mourey et al. (2013) and a hierarchal accountability as identified by Smith et al. (2018). The findings highlight that there

is a perceived need to meet funder demands and requirements, to provide detailed accounts of how and why activities are undertaken and to meet external expectations. Charities believe it is important to be accountable to funders for what was agreed; the evidence funders require would include details of outputs and impact. Overall, this supports the findings of Populous (2016) that external fund providing stakeholders are often most interested in reporting of the benefits and social solutions delivered by charities. The findings reveal that accountability is also perceived as being created when charities instigate a funding application. Some charities and charity boards believe there is a need to go beyond minimum reporting to external stakeholders to provide an understanding of community impact, supporting Keating and Frumkin's (2003) assertion that charity accountability is multi-faceted and must go beyond communication of financial performance. Accountability to clients, beneficiaries and community is identified by charities as being extremely important in the sector, in some cases, superseding the accountability to funders and regulators. This contrasts with findings of Smith and Miller (2018) who found evidence that small charities did not prioritise beneficiaries but merely kept them informed out of a moral duty. Several participants stated that there is a feeling of accountability to small local communities where people are connected. The empirical evidence supports the conclusion of Connolly and Hyndman's (2017) that despite the apparent power, legitimacy and urgency of funders, charities do not necessarily prioritise funders over beneficiaries since funder and beneficiary interests are aligned. Furthermore, there is convincing evidence of downward accountability to beneficiaries and local communities in the small charity sector as identified by Cordery et al (2011) and Baur and Shmitz (2012).

The findings demonstrate that charities perceive an accountability to wider stakeholder partners who have a role in supporting the charity. Trust is seen as an important backdrop to accountability; charities feel obligated to be accountable to funders or subscribing members who show trust in them. The empirical evidence here provides further evidence of a "virtuous

circle of accountability and trust” existing in the small charity sector (Hyndman and McConville, 2018, pp227). The findings show that accountability to the regulator OSCR is identified as an obvious accountability for the regulatory format accounts and this accountability extends to auditors or independent examiners. Those participants who had served in treasurer roles unsurprisingly identify financial accountability to OSCR and funders in the form of detailed financial records and accounts. The empirical evidence shows that treasurers exhibit an identity accountability in both their perceptions and behaviours around personal responsibility for accountability (Unerman and O’Dwyer, 2012). One participant stated that there are clear benefits to being self-funded since this means there is no obligation to be accountable to external parties, therefore avoiding perceived imposed accountability (Agyemang et al, 2017).

6.2.2 Identifying internal accountabilities

The empirical findings illustrate that charity boards perceive responsibility and accountability for internal governance and control; this extends to accountability for employee welfare. The role of the board is identified as something that requires more clarity, understanding, and agreement between boards and operational managers. Charity boards are not always clear on their accountability for governance and oversight and often venture into operational matters. One participant, however, holds the view that there is a need for a shared accountability between chief executive and the board to spread risk and responsibility. Charities identify responsibility to the charity mission and wrestle with the uncertainty over the flexibility of mission and constitution to accommodate different activities. The issue of mission drift is identified as a serious unintended consequence that most charities acknowledge and try to avoid; other charities, boards, staff, volunteers are not so mindful of their accountability to

mission and their objectives. One participant believes that their charity has responsibility to cease and wind up since there has been a failure in accountability to the charity mission. There is evidence here to further support the view of Najam (1996) that given the complex scenario of multiple external stakeholders, NFPs often defer to internal accountability to their mission and staff. There is also empirical evidence to support the argument that tension to satisfy information requirements of disparate stakeholder groups is often to the detriment of the charity mission (Hardy and Baliss, 2013). Overall, there is evidence to support the finding of O'Dwyer and Unerman (2008) that conflicts arise where a charity attempts to balance its accountability to stakeholders with their charitable activities and mission.

Where charities have over-arching or parental structures the need for accountability is seen as obvious since the parent dictates how resources are to be used. Within these types of structures, a chain of internal accountability is identified, from local group finances and activities to the local treasurer to the committee and upwards to local and regional overseeing bodies. This resonates with research identifying hierarchal accountability within these charity structures (Smith et al., 2018) and internal instrumental responsibility where transactional exchanges occur between management levels with a focus on financial reporting (Knutsen and Brower, 2010). One participant observes a multi-generational accountability, posing a problem for how to communicate effectively with generations of staff and volunteers within organisations.

6.2.3 General understandings of accountability

The empirical findings show a variety of understandings of accountability across charities and charity boards. Charities and charity boards perceive an accountability for performance and how resources are being used to achieve the charity mission, suggesting an internal felt accountability aligned with charity mission (O'Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015). This provides

further evidence that charities are dealing with the burden of extended accountabilities to society for achieving charity purpose and mission (Ebrahim, 2010; Worth, 2009; Anheier, 2005). The findings demonstrate that charities with subscribing members understand that their accountability is primarily to these members for how their funds are being used. Charities and their boards make the connection between accountability and responsibility to stakeholder groups, in agreement with the notion that accountability is both being held accountable and taking responsibility (Chisolm, 1995; Najam, 1996). The findings also agree with Gibelman and Gelman (2001), that accountability has a wide meaning both conceptually and in practice, thus charities default to a focus on the information needs of stakeholders. The findings show that the term ‘accountability’ is not commonly used in the sector; however, this phraseology can arise when discussing regulators or funders or sometimes when decisions are seen to impact stakeholders. Charities and boards suggest that accountability is not a common phrase and is not discussed as often as it should be, but there is a belief that accountability still forms a large part of their charity work. The findings reveal that accountability is not well understood in the small charity sector, and trustees are in fact often fearful of the magnitude and scope of accountabilities, supporting the views of Connolly and Hyndman (2004) and Roberts (2009) that accountability is quite ambiguous in nature and in need of clearer definition. A need for board members that understand roles and responsibilities is identified by charity boards, especially to support and guide new appointees. The findings reveal that charity boards do not always understand or engage with financial information and financial terminology and some charity boards perceive that this limits their ability to be accountable for financial oversight. The findings also show that not all charity boards understand the requirements of charity governance, and this includes concepts and phrases around accountability. There is often resistance to learning since board members can find these matters to be uninteresting, preferring to focus on charity activities. One participant identified that new people coming to

the charitable sector often do not understand that there is a need to be accountable and report to funders and other stakeholders; this is a new concept to them. The findings support the findings of Hyndman and McConville (2017) that charity managers perceive accountability as an important concept and recognise a need to offer an account of how resources were used. However, the concept and scope of accountability is not well understood in the small charity sector.

Charities connect accountability with transparency and demonstrate that a motive driving their attitudes and behaviour is the need to avoid accusations of wrongdoing. This supports the view of Smith and Miller (2018) that small charities are concerned about public perception of small charity scope for errors and fraud and the finding of Hyndman and McMahan (2011) that charities fear that negative publicity undermines fundraising. The findings show a belief amongst charities and their boards that they have plenty of scope to improve their understanding of accountability and the accountability context in which their charities operate. Most charities are not implementing tools such as 'Ecomap' or 'RACI' to improve understanding of the charity environment and its stakeholders. If a charity cannot understand itself and help external stakeholders understand the charity, then this adds to the suspicion and mistrust in the sector identified by Cordery and Baskerville (2007). One participant identifies a need to understand sensitive and public-affecting issues, which create an accountability and responsibility for public safety. It was found that board members of trust fund providing charities prioritise accountability for the sustainability of funds. In addition, charitable trust funds believe they have a role and responsibility in the sector to demonstrate the highest standards of their own accountability and to demand accountability from those it funds. This provides strong evidence of a felt accountability amongst trust fund providing charities, which is voluntary, moral, and ethical in nature (Agyemang et al, 2017). The findings also demonstrate that the perceived need for accountability is lessened where trust exists between

charity, users, members, and the community. These findings provide further evidence of an intrinsic social trust in the sector to support Keating and Thrandardottir's (2017) criticism of models of rational trust and the charity accountability agenda. However, the findings again show that the very presence of trust creates a desire amongst charities to demonstrate their accountability, which is in support of Hyndman and McConville (2018).

One participant believes that since charities enjoy legal and financial benefits then there is a responsibility and accountability to demonstrate value for money to stakeholders. The participant also expressed concern that charities can exercise selective accountability to manage their external image, despite argument from literature that honesty, transparency, and integrity are quite natural features of a charity (Dhanani and Connolly, 2012). The findings show that treasurers link accountability to the process of preparing financial accounts; this is seen as a personal accountability to many stakeholders i.e., a felt identity accountability (Agyemang et al, 2017). Treasurers believe that the process of preparing OSCR format accounts satisfy personal and organisational accountability to all internal and external stakeholders. This supports the findings of Alsop and Morgan (2019) that OSCR's approach to cash-based accounting is sufficient for discharging accountability to a wide range of stakeholders.

6.3 Building Stakeholder Accountability Relationships

The following section explores the findings around participant experiences, behaviours, and attitudes to their stakeholder accountability relationships and is compared to the charity accountability literature reviewed in previous chapters. There are four main thematic areas: identifying & understanding their stakeholders, finding & using effective accountability mechanisms, being transparent with stakeholders, stakeholder apathy.

6.3.1 Identifying and understanding stakeholders

The empirical findings demonstrate that charities often cannot identify important and less important stakeholder groups thus appropriate levels of communication are difficult to establish for some in the sector. Charity boards, managers and staff do not always agree upon their key charity stakeholders. However, the findings show that charities do identify that there are levels or tiers of stakeholders: those essential for the charity to exist and other less important groups. The findings offer further support of Smith et al. (2018, p.5) conclusion that organisations must identify stakeholder hierarchy by asking the question “to whom are we accountable”? Some charities are cognisant of a need to review policies around information sharing with stakeholders and acknowledge that there can be numerous issues connected to charity activity and outcomes that generate interest from stakeholders. The findings highlight that some charities identify that the fluid nature of stakeholders, where new stakeholders emerge or are created in different situations, poses a serious challenge. This echoes Koppell (2005, p.94) view that there is potential for “multiple accountabilities disorder” where numerous stakeholders are connected due to various finance sources and charitable activities. Overall, the empirical findings agree with Hyndman and McConville (2017), that charity managers are mindful of the importance of managing stakeholder relations and meeting their expectations. The findings also show that charities endeavour to meet the Charity Commission’s (2004) imperative for good relationships with stakeholders and to meet their information needs, the challenge of prioritisation notwithstanding. Grant and fund-providing charities, for example, do not consistently prioritise their stakeholders as these charities are intermediaries there is disagreement between prioritising principal funders or the grant recipient charity. The findings show that charities are often overwhelmed by the sheer number and variety of charity stakeholders, however, O’Dwyer and Unerman (2007) argue that charities must embrace the

benefits of a wider and more holistic stakeholder engagement. Connolly and Hyndman (2017) also conclude that more holistic accountability is desirable for the charitable sector but would require significant support. The difficulty in satisfying all stakeholders groups or establishing stakeholder priority could be addressed by focus on one key stakeholder group to enhance accountabilities for all (Connolly and Hyndman, 2017).

The empirical findings illustrate that the relationship between charity board and the operational side of the charity is crucial; roles and accountabilities must be determined and understood by both parties. It is observed by some but not all charities that a demarcation line between charity board and charity operations is important. However, some charities operate with overlapping structures where charity workers and members also serve on charity committees and boards. This reduces information asymmetry between internal charity actors such as board, managers, members, and volunteers; and leads to increased goal alignment, suggesting an internal stewardship dynamic in the sector (Jocombe, 2006; Caers et al, 2009). The findings show that charities are being accountable to their boards for performance and activity updates; boards often advise in areas such as fund applications. Challenging internal working relationships do exist in the sector and disagreements between chief executives and board regarding reporting and accountabilities are common. The findings provide evidence that charities perceive a benefit of close, trusting, and supportive relationships with their board, allowing for an openness and frankness around challenges. The findings also show that charities identify that the board has a key role in sharing information for internal and external accountability since they have oversight over the whole charity. Charities and charity boards identify the risk of serious internal accountability failure in the sector: where relationship between charity executive and charity board break-down; where there is minimum interaction between charity and board; and where there is a lack of trust and respect between charity and its board. Most charities are mindful of need for good charity-board relationships and need for robust internal

accountability to the board. This suggests that despite the need for an internal instrumental accountability for financial performance and outputs (Knutsen and Brower, 2010), charities favour a socialising accountability to their boards with closer and less formal relationships (Roberts, 1991). Overall, the findings demonstrate that charities struggle with the board-charity dynamic. The evidence suggests that some charities and board relationships are explained by stewardship theory through their goal congruence, collaboration, and trust. However, despite a desire for close relationships, some charities and their boards exhibit an agency problem as they show evidence of goal conflict and distrust (Tosi et al, 2003; Puyvelde, 2012).

The findings show that small charities prioritise paying members since they are both funder and beneficiary of services, believing they would not exist without members; it is therefore important to keep them informed and satisfied. The findings highlight that disagreements between charities and members can arise and a middle ground or compromise is the usual outcome. The empirical findings provide further evidence of complex charity-member relationships and the relevance of both stewardship theory and agency theory in explaining these relationships (Chen, 2004). The empirical findings also support Cordery and Baskerville (2011) and Desai and Yetman (2005) argument that information asymmetries can be reduced for beneficiaries through further involvement as members. Charities believe that trust in their organisation can be developed and maintained in the community if there is continuity and succession of their members over a prolonged period. The empirical findings provide further evidence that normative downward accountability is a natural priority for membership charities to best serve their member interests (Loft et al, 2006).

The empirical findings reveal that small charities often struggle with the burden of meeting different needs of different funders; there is an administrative burden in adapting reports to different formats to meet the different needs. This provides further evidence that whilst single reports may not be particularly onerous, it is the combined and multiple demands from multiple

stakeholders that impose significant burden on small charities (Smith and Miller, 2018). One participant identified that a holistic knowledge and understanding of a charity makes it easier for charities and their boards to adapt information to different needs. The findings show that charities are afraid of making mistakes where funders have even small differences in their requirements, in agreement with Smith and Miller (2018) who found charities were anxious and insecure in meeting accounting procedures to satisfy large funders. New funders and updates to regulations or parent requirements represent new reporting challenges to be overcome for small charities. Most small charities recognise a need to build strong long-standing relationships with funders, for example the Scottish government, to reduce the stress of fund seeking and the administrative burden of adapting to different disclosure requirements. The findings highlighted that charities can often spend most of their charity time and effort trying to raise funds, illustrating that charities appreciate that accountability in the form of financial reports and statements influences donors' perceptions of a charity and the decision to donate (Parsons, 2007). The empirical findings provide substantial evidence that small charities feel the pressure of an imposed upward accountability to their funders (Agyemang et al, 2017). Charities perceive an end to this stakeholder accountability when funding comes to an end. Charities identify a need for more honest and open dialogue with their funders and a negotiation on reporting requirements. Overall, the findings show that agency theory and principal-agent view are the best description of charity-funder relationships in the small charity sector. However, there is some evidence that small charities employ stewardship strategies such as relationship nurturing, reciprocity, responsibility, and reporting since objectives are fundamentally aligned (Kelly, 2001).

The empirical findings show that small charities believe that reporting and accountability for the sector must be more proportionate to size and turnover. Funding charities identify a fear and resistance to dialogue amongst fund-seeking charities, despite a reported willingness of

funders to listen and compromise. The empirical findings agree with Roberts (2001) call for more socialising forms of accountability focussed on closer relationships and shared social mission as an alternative to hierarchal accountability. The findings show that charities often feel the need to be creative in funding applications to convince funders that they are eligible to funds earmarked for tangential areas of interest. Despite the administrative challenge, some charities perceive there is a benefit of regular reporting to capture information and report whilst this is fresh in memory. Charities perceive that contributors to fundraising events are important stakeholders and the trust shown by contributors brings with it a weight of responsibility and accountability. The findings highlight that positive change is occurring in some parts of the sector, with charities being more willing to engage with funder evaluations. The evaluation process is more likely to be seen as a positive process that can improve a charity rather than a burdensome hurdle imposed by funders. Funding charities believe there is further potential in the sector to embrace this mindset. This agrees with Ebrahim's (2003) conclusion that evaluation information must be useful for internal charity decision-making and enable reflection, learning, and self-improvement for the charity. One participant expresses relief that since their charity is not reliant on external financing beyond their membership, this reduces the burden of relationship building and accountability to funders. This again shows a desire amongst some small charities to avoid an imposed accountability (Agyemang et al, 2017).

The empirical findings show that charities identify straightforward procedural relationships and communication with OSCR. Reporting to OSCR is seen as necessary to retain charitable status, there is a legal obligation, but not much correspondence beyond this. The findings support a view that small charities tend to have a straightforward upward, imposed, and functional accountability to the charity regulator (Ebrahim, 2003). The findings show that small charities tend only to communicate with OSCR if breaches of regulation occur and charities report positively regarding OSCR's willingness to guide them through their regulatory requirements.

This is in contrast with Smith and Miller (2018) who found that small charities experienced significant anxiety and pressure for upward accountability to regulators and legislators. Treasurers identify auditors or independent examiners as offering a crucial supportive role, providing confidence that personal and organisational financial accountability was robust. Charity treasurers take responsibility for internal and external accountability, citing their own personal accountability to members, levels of internal leadership and OSCR. The findings once more demonstrate identity accountability on the part of treasurers (O'Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015). Overall, there is little empirical evidence of the phenomena of co-optation, where upward accountability to powerful regulators can detract from accountability to less powerful stakeholders (Baur and Shmitz, 2012). However, the charity-regulator relationship indicates a clear principal-agent relationship as defined by agency theory (Puyvelde, 2012).

The findings show that advocacy charities attempt to build working relationships with the government and often seek feedback on the extent to which their information can influence at local and national level; there is a perceived need to connect to and influence system players. The Scottish government is identified as an important fund provider and charities engage in relationship building to both secure funds and attempt to influence policy. Advocacy charities demonstrate expressive accountability in articulating their values and beliefs to wider stakeholder groups (Knutsen and Brower, 2010). Unsurprisingly, small community-based charities perceive a closer connection with local government rather than national government. The empirical evidence suggests that agency theory and stewardship theory are both valid in describing charity-government relationships and are not mutually exclusive (Tosi et al, 2003).

The findings demonstrate that some charities build strong working relationships with partner organisations for example those that deliver all or part of services to beneficiaries in the sector. Advocacy charities have difficult relationships with service delivery partners since they have a role to educate or criticise practice. Charities dealing with complex social needs build

relationships with wider stakeholders such as legal teams and advisors; there is a perceived need to be accountable to these groups. The findings show that the importance of charity partnerships is often under-estimated in the sector: funders look favourably on joint funding applications and charities and boards can come together to discuss common issues and challenges. The findings show that charities do not always seek charity partnerships where they can; this lack of connection and information sharing between charities often leads to duplication of services within communities. Some charities identify a need to work with partner charities to be more effective for the whole community; however, they perceive resistance and lack of motivation elsewhere in the sector. Small charities therefore limit their strategic accountability to the extent that they can be responsive to the community's ongoing needs and collaborate and support other community voluntary sector organisations (Cordery and Sim, 2018). Charities are uncertain to what extent there is a responsibility and accountability to partners, informal and fewer demanding relationships are preferred. The findings show that competition for funds represents a serious challenge for the sector. Charities believe competition in the sector is unhelpful, and pits charity against charity, leading to resentment and not necessarily a more efficient allocation of funds. Ebrahim (2002) identifies that funder evaluations that focus on short term easily quantifiable outputs will favour those charities who are more able to simplify their output data and information. This leads to less funds for those with more complex programmes. The empirical findings show that both stewardship theory and agency theory can apply to charity-charity partnerships; where trust and close relationships exist or alternatively where distrust can exist between partners (Puyvelde, 2012).

The empirical findings highlight that charities believe it is important to communicate activities and impact to beneficiaries. Charities identify trust as being the key component for building relationships with clients and beneficiaries; this trust is built upon the information being shared and leads to yet further information being shared between charity and beneficiaries. This

provides further evidence of the positive compounding effect of stakeholder trust in the charity sector (Hyndman and McConville, 2018). Charities often consult and collaborate with beneficiaries, placing them at the forefront to drive charity activities. The empirical evidence shows that small charities largely view themselves as agents of principal beneficiaries despite the level of trust perceived in them (Cordery and Baskerville, 2011). The public is often seen as a key stakeholder and consistent communication is seen as essential to avoid mixed messages. Charities identify a need for two-way communication with local community; the local community is identified as both user of services and provider of volunteers and volunteers. This provides further evidence that charity managers are eager to engage with the public, despite the uncertainties around the exact information the public would find useful (Hyndman and McConville, 2017). The empirical findings also show that small charities do not lack downward accountability due to limited power and urgency of beneficiaries and community as cautioned by Cordery et al (2011) and Mourey et al (2013). One participant believes that accountability can be more effective if stakeholders are more honest about what they do and do not understand about a charity. Overall, the empirical findings suggest that there is desire for accountability to beneficiaries in the small charity sector; this shows potential for a purpose-driven accountability, which links performance to purpose and can serve many stakeholders (Uddin and Belal, 2019).

6.3.2 Finding and using effective accountability mechanisms

The empirical findings show that charities in the sector employ a wide range of communication and accountability mechanisms to connect with a diverse range of stakeholder groups. Charities are employing a mix of formal and informal, and public and private communications with their stakeholders. This aligns with the recommendation by Hyndman and McConville (2017) that

accountability must be discharged through various mechanisms to develop and maintain trust in individual charities and the wider sector. Furthermore, the empirical evidence mostly contradicts previous studies of charities that found that there is often a lack of mechanisms to facilitate downward accountability (Jayasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011; O'Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015). The findings identify that word of mouth could be a type of accountability mechanism in close-knit communities. Charities also believe that where there is a track record of meaningful impact in a community, trust is created and lessens pressure and demand for accountability. However, the findings demonstrate that charities require more understanding of why and how they should communicate with stakeholders. The findings provide further evidence that “charity accountability is complex and dynamic and operates along multiple dimensions- involving numerous actors (patrons, clients, selves), using various mechanisms” (Ebrahim, 2003, p. 815).

The findings show that periodic reports on charity activities are used in the sector to serve the needs of multiple stakeholders, although charities are often uncertain to what extent these different needs are being met. Communication plans that identify stakeholders, accountabilities, appropriate levels of communication, and effective accountability mechanisms are being used by some charities in the sector to help in this respect. This echoes the concern of Cordery, Belal and Thomson (2019) that without a suitable framework, charities will struggle to identify and manage their range of potential accountability responsibilities. It is evident from the interviews that charities continue to think about the cost-benefit of employing different communication and accountability mechanisms. The findings also highlight a need for charities to set communication expectations with their stakeholders and wider consultation with stakeholders is identified as beneficial for feedback and achieving accountability. Charities in the sector are finding novel and creative ways to collect information and consult with their beneficiaries, collecting feedback on outcomes and impact to discharge

accountability to boards and funders. Consultations with beneficiaries is important to charities, allowing charities to consult on and evaluate desired outcomes and impact; however, the process of evaluation and change is a serious resource challenge.

The findings show that internal management accounts are a vital internal accountability mechanism from charity to board. Even though charities struggle at times to meet their commitment to regular board communication, board meetings and the process of taking minutes are identified as important accountability mechanisms in the sector. The findings show that regular meetings with committees, staff and volunteers are viewed as an essential form of internal accountability in the sector. Fund-providing charities also underlined that their board meetings can take place on funded charity premises to share more information and be actively engaged with their charities.

The findings highlight that the annual report and the AGM are two crucial mechanisms of accountability to inform members, volunteers and to some extent the wider community. The AGM is used in the sector primarily as a mechanism of internal accountability to present information on finances, activities, and outputs to members. The annual report or OSCAR format accounts are often being used as a formal and robust form of accountability mechanism to serve many internal and external stakeholders. Connolly and Hyndman (2017) found that large donors expected regulation-compliant annual accounts; however, they found that small donors and beneficiaries had little appetite for these formal communications. The findings suggest that treasurers are satisfied that the processes of preparing and sharing financial records and reports meet multiple internal financial accountabilities through various levels of an organisation. This supports the argument made by Connolly and Hyndman (2004) and Hyndman and McDonnell (date) that stakeholder needs can be partly met through the release of the annual report. Charity boards, professional accountants and treasurers believe that charities are not tapping into the full potential of annual reports to provide more comprehensive and engaging accounts of

charity activity and performance. This agrees with Cordery et al. (2019) and Kemp and Morgan (2019) who conclude that standard regulatory format accounts may fall short in facilitating comprehensive stakeholder accountabilities. The findings show that there is an eagerness amongst some funders to participate in charity AGMS to access more detailed information. However, open AGMs are underemployed in the sector despite their potential to serve multiple stakeholders; charities in the sector often have members-only AGMs. Hyndman and McConville (2017) call for an effective mix of public and private mechanisms in the sector to cement trust between charities and their stakeholders.

The empirical findings show that social media, websites and in some instances, webinars, are identified by charity leaders as being useful accountability mechanisms for the sector to share information on activities, raise awareness, and widen influence. The findings show that advocacy charities engage in multi-media strategies to demonstrate their impact, encourage user participation, and widen influence- although this is not always viewed as accountability. However, charities in the sector are uncertain regards the quantity and variety of information appropriate for dissemination through social media. The findings demonstrate that small charities do not always communicate their activities, achievements, and performance through their websites. This can limit small charity accountability since previous research shows that stakeholder groups such as public and individual donors prefer informal, accessible, publicly available communications (Laughlin, 2008). The findings identified that social media and websites were viewed by charity leaders as effective communication and accountability mechanisms in the sector, but charities are burdened with the time and expertise required to set up and maintain these systems. The findings provide further evidence that charities perceive the benefit of engagement with the public and increased charity visibility through their websites (Hyndman and McConville, 2017). However, the findings show that several factors limit implementation in the small charity sector. Charities are fearful of the negative outcomes that

can occur if inconsistent or wrong messages are communicated through social media. Local news outlets are used by some charities as a viable means of sharing information more widely with stakeholder groups. Overall, the empirical findings show that small charities could further leverage the benefits of websites and social networks identified by Saxton et al (2014) and Bellante et al. (2018). These potential benefits include strengthening stakeholder relationships, attracting human and financial resources, and increasing interaction and participation with a wider range of stakeholders.

The empirical findings show that some small charities believe annual proposal meetings and consultations with funders are effective two-way information sharing mechanisms; previous year can be reflected upon, and next year's accountability can be agreed. Funding applications, funding returns, and monitoring reports are seen as burdensome on time and people in the sector, particularly for small funding arrangements. However, charities do see the benefit of two-way communication with funders since the reporting requirements allow charities to communicate the community issues and needs to funders such as local councils. The findings support those of Hyndman and McConville (2017) that managers of charities struggle with meeting private direct reporting demands of funders but view this as necessary for transparency and trust building. In addition, charities acknowledge that they can work smarter in terms of identifying where information from reports could feed into other reports. One participant suggested that robust financial records and comprehensive OSCAR format accounts could be used as the basis for meeting multiple funders reporting requirements; this was not problematic. However, Ebrahim (2003) and Mourey et al. (2013) suggest that financial records and accounts are primarily a tool of upward accountability and have limited use in facilitating downward accountability to beneficiaries and the community. In addition, the focus here is on a functional accountability for short-term outputs and resource use, with limited strategic accountability for long-term impact and outcomes (Cordery and Sim, 2018). The findings also highlighted a belief

that fund-providing charities could be making better use of funding application information; this information could be used as a learning resource for other charities.

The research shows that events or festivals are employed by some charities in the sector as a mechanism for disseminating information and discharging accountability to user groups and communities. Events also encourage debate and interest in the charity issue or mission. Informal chats during events are viewed as a powerful way of connecting with stakeholders and sharing information to be accountable. Participants confirmed that funders are often keen to attend events to observe first-hand what their money had delivered, but this was underappreciated by charities. Indeed, many charities do not see the potential of public events to engage wider audiences including charity partners and local authorities. The findings show further scope for small charities to embrace mechanisms that facilitate accountability to wider communities and beneficiaries, to share prospective information relevant to a charity's future direction (Connelly et al., 2013; O'Dwyer and Boomsma, 2015). One participant pointed out that videos demonstrating impact on beneficiaries were a simple yet powerful way to demonstrate and discharge accountability to funders. The findings also reveal that board-charity relationships and accountability could be improved by providing opportunity for board members to participate and volunteer in charity activities and events. However, the findings also show that some charities have more scope than others to allow stakeholders opportunity to observe, volunteer and participate in charity activities. Charity visits are seen as effective accountability mechanisms to allow important system players and funders to have direct observation of charity activities, outputs, and impact. The empirical findings support the conclusion of Hyndman and McConville (2017) that charities appreciate the benefits of private mechanisms such as direct observation and participation. However, not all charities are taking action to implement these accountability mechanisms. The nature of some charities also means there is regular contact with members so regular informal communication is possible, preferred,

and often viewed as more effective than formal lines of communication. This supports previous studies that found that participation as a form of downward accountability is a priority for membership charities (Ebrahim, 2003; Loft et al., 2006). It is evident that initiatives are being rolled out in the sector to connect users and local charitable organisations and facilitate information sharing, but not all charities are engaging.

Overall, the empirical findings show that small charities employ a variety of accountability mechanism tools (discrete devices or techniques), but accountability mechanism processes (ongoing and multi-faceted) are mostly under-employed. Ebrahim (2003) identifies participation, self-regulation, and social audits as accountability mechanism processes. The information gathered in the present study confirms that some small charities are self-regulating through for example seeking accreditation and certification. It is also clear that small charities in the sample would only partially meet the requirements for social audit e.g., the ability to identify and communicate effectively with stakeholders, and ability to employ robust performance measures to guide charity improvement and disclosures (Ebrahim, 2003). However, the empirical findings show that small charities are meeting some levels of participation as defined by Ebrahim (2003) such as first level use of public meetings, dialogues, and communication with charity members. In addition, small charities are meeting second level and third level participation to a certain extent through community participation in charity programmes or the ceding of power to communities to determine charity activities. The accountability mechanisms for the small charities in the study tend to be retrospective (historical reporting) in nature, with limited prospective forward-facing mechanisms such as long-term plans being discussed, produced, or disclosed. The empirical findings demonstrate that aspects of Cordery and Sim's (2018) principles-based approach to accountability mechanisms are being adopted in the small charity sector. The principle of balance is in evidence as small charities are using a variety of mechanisms to satisfy both powerful and less

powerful stakeholders. The principle of multiple-use mechanisms to meet all needs and reduce administrative burden requires further consideration by small charities. The principle of variation, since charities have unique profiles and activities, seems to be in evidence since charities employ different combinations of accountability mechanisms.

6.3.3 Being transparent with stakeholders

The interviews demonstrate that charities are providing feedback on charity performance to their boards, funders and to a lesser extent other stakeholders. However, there are various levels of competency and comprehensiveness in reporting outputs, impact, and outcomes. Charities find performance measurement to be challenging given the complexity of charity services and the time and human resource required to manage their data and evaluations. This provides further evidence to support the conclusions of Lumley (2011) and Carnochan (2014) that social outputs and outcomes, and performance reporting mechanisms are notoriously difficult to master in the complex charity sector. Performance is seen as an elusive concept in the sector with many charities uncertain of what performance means for them; charities therefore often defer to funders to determine what constitutes a performance metric. This provides evidence that small charities do collaborate, albeit through necessity, with stakeholders to some extent in design of performance measures, in contrast with the findings of Hyndman and McConville (2013). Charities are often overwhelmed with the quantity of data required to be collected and collated in anticipation of funder information demands; whilst other small charities are concerned at their apparent lack of data on activities and performance. The findings demonstrate that small charities often do collect pertinent data but fail to understand it or fail to understand what to do with it. The findings provide further evidence to support Hyndman and McKillop's (2018) view that the move towards increased disclosure of financial and

performance information (outputs, outcomes, impact) is extremely problematic for the sector. Overall, there is empirical evidence to suggest that instrumental accountability is more dominant in the small charity sector, focusing on reporting of measurable outcomes. Expressive accountability, articulating values and accountability to beneficiaries, community, and mission, is shown to be desirable but difficult to measure for small charities (Knutsen and Brower, 2010).

Sophisticated performance measures such as SROI are not widely used in the sector due to their complexity; simple unsophisticated performance measures on basic output or user engagement data are more common. Charities in fact often enjoy sharing measurements and statistics on their basic charity outputs with their boards and do use tools such as questionnaires to collect data on their impact on beneficiaries. This agrees with Hyndman and McConville's findings for larger charities that there has been an upward trend in the sector of reporting on outcomes and outputs (Hyndman and McConville, 2013). The findings demonstrate that charities are often better with qualitative data, being able to provide narrative accounts of activities and impact on lives, but are less adept at handling, analysing, and producing quantitative information. Small charities are often not particularly numbers led; instead, focussing on qualitative accounts, feedback, and informal discussions. Charities therefore do not always have effective ways to assess and communicate their performance or level of success. This supports the view of Lehman (2007) and Loft et al. (2006) that information asymmetries can exist between principal-funders and agent non-profit managers in the sector, which may lead to charities drifting away from their objectives. However, there is some evidence that small charities are using a combination of numbers and narrative based reporting to offer a balanced view of the charity to satisfy a range of stakeholders (Hyndman and McConville, 2013). Data collection and measurement is a weakness in the sector, including feedback data on beneficiary satisfaction and wider stakeholder perceptions of charities. This

provides further evidence that few charities provide context through benchmarking of outputs and outcomes over time or against other charities, which seriously undermines the transparency and assessment of charity disclosures (Hyndman and McConville, 2013).

Small charities have a desire to be transparent and financially accountable at individual and organisation level to avoid accusations of wrongdoing. One participant, however, is concerned that some charities like his have moved toward simpler accounting approaches allowed by OSCR to avoid more robust financial accountability. The findings demonstrate that charities have a further need for narratives to explain apparent financial failures within the accounts to avoid negative funder reactions. In addition, charities are not always brave enough to have open honest dialogue with funders to discuss their challenges and failures. This is understandable given that the reporting of missed targets are evidence of charity or management failure, which can harm the organisation (Hyndman and McConville, 2013). Charities, and in particular treasurers, believe that the processes and procedures followed to produce OSCR accounts fulfils transparency and accountability. Treasurers also take responsibility and an accountability for addressing specific questions or concerns related to annual reports and the AGM. Charities normally do not receive requests to see current financial records and up-to-date accounts, they believe that this largely due to trust from stakeholders such as their members and the community. This is further evidence that intrinsic social trust reduces the pressure on charities to discharge accountability to stakeholder groups (Keating and Thrandardottir, 2017).

The findings demonstrate that small charities are mindful of the need to adapt or target their information for different audiences to make this information accessible and understandable to the stakeholder groups. It is seen as necessary to translate complex information that may for example be required by OSCR or funders into something more straightforward for laypeople such as charity members. However, the findings show that small charities are not always

effective at simplifying their information into a form that is more concise and digestible. The findings provide evidence that charities are attempting to meet the needs of beneficiaries identified by Connolly and Hyndman (2013) for additional explanation or narratives to support numerical data. The findings show that charities are often dealing with sensitive social issues and information; this could limit charities' ability to disclose data on aspects of their activities and performance. Charities have difficulty in determining where, and when, and how and with whom sensitive information can be shared. They feel obligated to treat sensitive information appropriately since their clients and beneficiaries show trust in them, and there is a desire to maintain that trust.

Small charities perceive a disadvantage in providing too much information, for example through their websites, as stakeholder users of the information can be overwhelmed and may have difficulty finding the information they need. One participant expressed a strong belief that small charities were under too much pressure to process and produce excess volumes of data and information: questioning the value of the information culture. This echoes the concerns of Gray et al. (2006) that there are unfair demands being placed on charities to legitimise themselves. The findings reveal that charities are fearful of sharing too much information regards their financial position and activities, which serves as wider advertising of their service to potential users. Small charities believe they are vulnerable to both internal and external parties seeking to take advantage of surplus funds; and fearful of insufficient capacity to accommodate new service users.

The findings demonstrate a need for charities to make their annual reports and other periodic reports to funders and their boards more engaging. This echoes the call of Laughlin (2008) for more engaging accounts of charity activity and impact termed 'accessible-entity accountability', as opposed to 'formalised-entity accountability' of typical annual reports. Management accounts for example are often found to be neither helpful nor user-friendly for

charity boards. One participant demonstrated that management accounts that are presented to boards can lack detail required for transparency so represent an internal accountability failure. Charities may have interesting data available to them, but they are not often accomplished at showing this in an impactful way with engaging features. The empirical findings show some contradiction with Alsop and Morgan (2019) who found that charity managers believed that information presented to trustees should be simple to understand and relevant for managing the charity.

6.3.4 Stakeholder apathy

The empirical findings show that charities perceive a lack of interest on the part of various stakeholder groups. One participant identified that there is little interest in their small charity beyond their obvious internal and external stakeholders: government, public and others have more interest in high profile charities. This supports Hyndman and McConville (2017) argument that stakeholders are often unwilling to engage and so attempts at discharging accountability and trust building can have limited success. Charities believe that despite attempts to share information more widely, there is often little engagement with this and limited positive impact for the charity itself. Hyndman and McConville (2013) identified that this perceived lack of stakeholder interest partly explains why charities are less likely to pursue rigorous reporting of their performance. The findings reveal that small charities are uncertain how to engage stakeholder groups; however, they believe that they are doing what they can to connect. Having information available such as the financial records and accounts give small charities peace of mind that they are meeting their responsibilities.

The findings highlight that charity boards, committees and funders tend to be interested in the financial details whereas members and beneficiaries have little interest in detailed financial

accounts, operations, governance, and management. However, charities believe that members and community become interested when things go wrong or if their information is suddenly withdrawn. Charities view disinterest from members as a marker of significant trust, believing members are satisfied that the charity and charity board are acting in their best interests. This provides further evidence of existence of rational trust in the small charity sector (Keating and Thrandardottir, 2017). Likewise, charities have mixed success regards attendance and engagement in AGMs from members, community, and wider stakeholder groups; this is also largely perceived as evidence of trust in the charity. The findings show that small charities are having more successful engagement where AGMs and presentation of financial accounts are combined with other charity events. The findings highlight that there are instances in the sector where even charity boards show a lack of interest and engagement with financial accounts and reports. Participants in the sample proposed that the lack of interest was due to inability of board members to understand the financial information and a lack of motivation to learn.

The empirical findings show that charities are often reaching out to funders to participate in events, but invitations are often declined or ignored by funders. Charities are mindful that funders are themselves often too busy. Funder interest in charities varies across the sector: some funders have close and regular contact; other funders demonstrate little interest beyond periodic reviews. The findings demonstrate that initiatives to connect local organisations, create partnerships and improve information sharing in the sector are only partly successful since many charities fail to commit time and effort to these partnerships. Charities that are willing to take part in partner initiatives believe that other charities unwilling to do so are isolated and self-interested.

6.4 Accountability by charity type

Overall, the empirical findings agree with Cordery et al (2015) that management and governance, activities, financing, and regulatory features can define a charity and its accountabilities. The findings show that the charity-board arrangements for management and governance substantially determines the nature of charity internal accountability. The findings illustrate that the challenges and issues around accountability to funders is determined by the range, power, and influence of finance providers. The findings also illustrate that the activities of small charities create accountability primarily to beneficiaries but also to other stakeholder groups. The regulatory environment also demands accountability to the charity regulator, OSCR for all small charities. The empirical findings provide further evidence that charity type is a major factor in determining small charity accountability (Cordery and Sim, 2018). The findings show for example that small advocacy type charities prioritise accountability relationships with government and system players to widen their influence on behalf of their beneficiaries. The findings reveal that membership charities prioritise accountability to their members, recognising multifaceted accountability as provider of finance, user of charitable service, and potential volunteers. The findings also highlight that small trust or grant making charities occupy a special space in the sector, being accountable to their own fund providers and requiring accountability from their funded charities. The empirical findings show that classic charities, supporting disadvantaged groups, demonstrate a balance of upward and downward accountability to a wide range of stakeholder groups. However, the empirical findings also suggest that the challenges and issues around managing stakeholders, producing transparent accounts of charity activity, selecting accountability mechanisms, all within extreme resource constraints, are common across the small charity sector.

6.5 Summary of main findings and revisiting the theoretical framework

The following theoretical framework was proposed in chapter 2 as a summary of the main findings from literature review and as a tool for guiding the research project. The theoretical framework or model provided a hypothetical explanation and indeed an expectation of how accountability is created in the small charity sector.

Figure 2: Constructing and enacting accountability in the small charity sector

Source: Author

The theoretical model proved to be accurate in describing how small charities and their stakeholders interacted through accountability mechanisms and information sharing practices to create forms of accountability and emergent charity-stakeholder accountability relationships. Trust proved to be a pervasive or integrative theme for the research, motivating, mediating, and enhancing accountability in the sector. Whilst the model is robust in how it describes the big

picture of small charity accountability, more interesting, and nuanced explanations and understandings of accountability and stakeholder accountability relationships were revealed by the research.

The findings show that there a variety of understandings of accountability in the small charity sector and a variety of perspectives and approaches to building stakeholder relationships. The findings reveal that a range of accountability mechanism are being used to discharge small charity accountability to stakeholders, although charities have scope to consider how to make better use of these. The findings also highlight that limited resources in the sector are limiting small charities' ability to provide transparent accounts of their performance and activities both internally and externally. Overall, different forms and characteristics of accountability were found to exist between charities and their charity stakeholder groups. Charity-funder dynamics demonstrate upward, instrumental accountabilities, but charities show preference for more socialising forms of accountability with their funders. Indeed, funders often show a willingness to move towards these types of accountability relationship. Charity-beneficiary dynamics demonstrate that downward, socialising forms of accountability exist, leading to a more balanced holistic accountability for the small charity sector. The importance of the charity-charity board relationship dynamic emerged from the research, and the potential here for various forms of accountability. Like the charity-funder relationship, small charity managers show preference for close and trusting relationships with their boards i.e., socialising forms of accountability, in preference to instrumental or functional forms of accountability. In addition, the charity-regulator relationship dynamic provided surprisingly little evidence of burdensome, imposed accountability in the small charity sector. The charity-member relationship revealed that accountability to members is complex and multi-faceted, with myriad forms of accountability at play between charities and their membership. Trust is shown to be a crucial determinant and explanatory factor in charity stakeholder relationships and accountability,

especially in the charity-beneficiary and charity-member relationships where both social trust and rational trust are relevant in equal measure.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter discussed the empirical findings in the context of previous relevant academic and professional literature. The discussion provided evidence of mixed understandings of accountability in the small charity sector. The discussion also presented evidence to show that various forms of accountability exist in the small charity sector, formed through different approaches to stakeholder relationship building and use of various accountability mechanisms to discharge accountability.

This chapter moves on to revisit the research questions and discuss the extent to which answers were found to these questions through the research that was conducted. The overall aim of the study was to explore accountability in the small charitable sector within Scotland and was achieved through a two-stage mixed method approach, with focus on the latter stage qualitative interviews. A sample of both charity managers and charity board trustees provided their participant accounts for thematic analysis. The empirical evidence uncovered an interplay of understandings of accountability, perspectives on stakeholders, and knowledge of accountability mechanisms at work in the small charity sector.

7.2 Research Questions

The following section reflects on the research questions and the extent to which these research questions were answered by the evidence presented in previous chapters.

RQ 1 What are the accountability perceptions and attitudes of people in leadership positions in small charities?

The empirical findings show that there is uncertainty around definitions of accountability and what accountability means for individual charity managers and board members. Small charities agree that their accountability is limited to the extent that they understand the nature and scope of their accountabilities. The findings reveal a perception amongst small charities that they require additional education regards charity accountability but acknowledge that attitudes could improve around embracing change and engaging with learning resources. Small charity leaders perceive accountability as responsibility to stakeholders and express attitudes that prioritise the charity mission and their beneficiaries. These findings agree with academic literature for the wider sector. Accountability to funders for how funds were spent is perceived as being extremely important to small charities as is accountability for delivering services to beneficiaries. The findings also show that small charity leaders perceive accountability as being connected to transparency and their attitudes reveal that they wish to avoid accusations of wrongdoing, particularly in respect of their financial accountability. The expectation of the researcher was that given limited resources, small charities would demonstrate limited forms or characteristics of accountability in their attitudes towards personal and charity accountability. There was an expectation that small charities would by and large simply seek to meet imposed, hierarchal, upward accountability to powerful funders and regulators. In addition, it was expected that small charities would demonstrate an internal, felt accountability to charity mission as per previous studies. These forms of accountability were in evidence in the perceptions and attitudes expressed by participants, but a surprising, unexpected finding is that a more comprehensive and holistic accountability exists in the sector. Small charities demonstrate a clear commitment to downward accountability to beneficiaries and to some extent their wider communities.

RQ 2 What stakeholder groups are prioritised by small charities and what is the nature of their stakeholder relationships?

The findings show that small charities identify a wide range of stakeholders but often have difficulty in prioritising or identifying key stakeholder groups and their information needs. However, the findings provide evidence that accountability to funders and beneficiaries is of paramount and equal importance in the small charity sector. Trust is a key factor in the charity-beneficiary relationship with evidence showing that a foundation of trust reduces perceived need for accountability but simultaneously motivating charities to be accountable to their service users. There is evidence that small charities perceive and foster both relational trust and rational trust with their beneficiaries and wider communities, agreeing with views expressed in the academic literature, the two theories of trust do not appear to be mutually exclusive. The evidence shows that funders have power and influence to exert an imposed and upward accountability upon small charities. Instrumental accountability is dominant in the charity-funder relationship. Small charities demonstrate a preference for socialising forms of accountability in their relationships with funders and would like to see more consultation, collaboration, and compromise from funders. Likewise, small charities indicate that they have preference for socialising forms of accountability with their charity boards, to build closer and more supportive working relationships. Internal accountability to charity boards can be merely functional and feel imposed where charity-board relationships break down. The issues around the charity-charity board internal accountability dynamic emerged as a surprising finding for the research. Another surprising finding for the research is the charity-regulator relationship; the expectation here was that this would be a burdensome, imposed, upward accountability for small charities as per findings of previous studies. However, the evidence suggests that small charities mostly perceive demands from OSCR as necessary, procedural, and non-problematic; indeed, some suggestion was made towards a more socialising form of accountability where

OSCR offered some compromise and support to small charities. The findings show that small charities could be doing more to reach out and engage with partner charities to support each other and deliver more effectively for their local communities.

Overall, the findings show that both stewardship and agency theories can describe the accountability dynamic between principal-agents in the small charity sector. Agency theory currently offers the best description of small charities' relationships with funders and regulators, yet there is scope and a willingness on both sides to move towards stewardship arrangements. Stewardship theory currently offers the best explanation of charities' relationship with their beneficiaries and local communities due to collaboration and trust. The findings show that both agency theory and stewardship theory are applicable to the charity-charity board relationship; those with formal relationships focussed on instrumental accountability or those with less formal, close, and supportive relationships focussed on socialising forms of accountability, respectively.

RQ 3 What types, quantity, and quality of information are being produced and shared by small charities to be transparent?

The empirical evidence suggests that small charities have more scope to convey transparent information around various aspects of charity activity and performance: financial, outputs, impact, mission, management, and narratives. The findings show that these types of information are not always shared by charities through their accountability mechanisms and the quantity and quality of that information are limited by their financial and human resources. The findings agree with previous academic literature that limited skills and expertise in the charitable sector is limiting small charity ability to collect and analyse data and to develop and deploy performance measurements. This is limiting the type, quantity and quality of

information that can be produced and shared by charities. Performance measurement is particularly problematic for small charities with uncertainty around what performance means for each charity. With limited resources, small charities tend to measure only their most basic identifiable outputs and to some extent their short-term impact on lives of beneficiaries. Sophisticated measurements including measurement of effectiveness and long-term impacts and outcomes are also not adopted by small charities. Dedicated specialist software for data collection, collation, analysis, and production of reports are not used in the small charity sector due to people and time constraints. The findings also demonstrate that small charities often lack knowledge and expertise to adapt and tailor their information to meet different stakeholder audiences. Likewise, small charities both under-appreciate and lack the skills to offer more engaging, quality accounts of their charitable activities, performance, and successes to a wide range of internal and external stakeholders. However, there is evidence to suggest that small charities do attempt to balance their quantitative and qualitative information disclosures by using narratives and stories to supplement financial and quantitative data. Overall, the findings suggest that despite recognition of a need for accountability to various stakeholders, and their best attempts to meet these needs, small charities have limited transparency due to the factors identified above.

RQ 4 What are the perceptions and behaviours around use of accountability mechanisms in the small charity sector?

The empirical findings reveal that small charities adopt a wide variety of both public and private accountability mechanisms to share information and discharge accountability to internal and external stakeholders. Given limited resources, there was an expectation that small charities would use only a few, mostly mandatory, mechanisms; the use of such a wide variety

of mechanisms is a surprising finding for the research. However, small charities are uncertain over extent to which mechanisms can have multiple use and some mechanisms such as open AGMs, open meetings, events, charity visits are under-employed as public mechanisms. The findings show that small charities perceive private direct communication as effective means to discharge formal and informal accountability to various stakeholders. Board meetings, the annual report, and AGMs are perceived as the best means for facilitating internal accountability and are utilised by most small charities to discharge accountability. The annual report is also seen as a straightforward accountability mechanism to meet external requirements of the charity regulator. A further surprising finding for the research was the extent to which internal and external financial accountability was satisfied through the OSCR financial records and accounts. These were perceived and employed, mostly by small charity treasurers, as multiple-use mechanisms to satisfy internal management needs and external demands from funders and regulator. Small charities use websites and social media to engage with wider external stakeholders but are uncertain of the quantity and types of information to share; small charities are often fearful and distrustful of online methods. The findings reveal that charities employ mostly discrete accountability mechanism tools such as reports, newsletters, and meetings. Small charities have scope to consider more continuous accountability processes such as stakeholder observation and participation, ongoing consultations with beneficiaries, and seeking accreditations.

RQ 5 What effect does charity type have on accountability perceptions and practices in the small charity sector?

The findings suggest that whilst charity characteristics such as management, governance, financing, regulator, activities, and stakeholders are important in determining the charity

accountability context, the issues and challenges of accountability are common across the sector. Likewise, whilst charity type such as classic charity, charity trust, advocacy charity, or membership-based charity are important to understand the charity accountability landscape, there are common issues and challenges for small charities in discharging accountability to their stakeholders. For classic charities that provide support and services to beneficiaries, the findings show that small charities attempt to balance upward and downward accountability. The findings show that charities with subscribing members clearly prioritise their members with myriad forms of accountability in evidence including hierarchal accountability, socialising accountability, functional accountability, felt accountability, and both instrumental and expressive accountabilities. Despite previous academic research suggesting that charities have unique accountability profiles as identified above; there is evidence to suggest that small charities are better defined by their common features of resource constraint and intimacy with their local communities.

7.3 Recommendations

This section reflects upon the findings around the need for organisation or sector change; this includes discussion of accountability solutions being employed or considered by charity managers and charity boards. The empirical findings from over-arching theme 3 found within Appendix 7 largely inform these recommendations for the small charitable sector. There are three main thematic areas: ability and attitude to change, environmental challenges, accountability tools and approaches.

7.3.1 Ability to change and attitude towards change

The empirical findings show that board skill set, and recruitment are crucial to support charity governance and accountability in the small charity sector. Recruitment of high-calibre board trustees is a problem area for small charities. Many charity boards struggle with concepts, terminology and features of accountability including financial data and techniques. The findings indicate that charities and charity boards engage with training and sector support to different degrees: some boards do not necessarily perceive the need for training, others feel threatened by it, and some boards are unclear about what support is available. Although many charity boards recognise that they have a responsibility in suggesting how charities can improve their communication and accountability mechanisms, they could be doing more in this respect.

Overall, the findings suggest that charity managers and charity boards must engage with support resources for the sector, and sector support organisations must do more to signpost and flag the resources that they offer to small charities. Sector support organisations and regulators could perhaps do more reaching out to small charities to provide guidance to fundamental concepts such as accountability and accountability to stakeholders. Charity boards should take the lead in identifying resources for their charities given the time pressures placed upon often voluntary charity workers. Ideally, support organisations for the sector and government could do more to encourage participation amongst able and professional people to take up charity management and board roles in local communities or at least temporary advisory roles.

The findings demonstrate that resource constraints of expertise, money and time are restricting charity capabilities to capture and share information with stakeholders. The empirical evidence uncovered supports previous findings in the third sector that highlight ongoing financial and staff resource constraints (Mitchell and Berlan 2016, Back-Mortensen and Montgomery, 2018). Charities question how much limited resource should be directed towards data and

information to satisfy stakeholder needs, fearing this can be to detriment of core activities and services. Resource constraints in skills and finance are seen as barriers to growth and development of stakeholder accountability approaches in the sector. IT and data are an area where small charities lack expertise. In addition, the empirical findings provide further evidence that skills in data analysis and evaluation are lacking in the small charity sector. The findings show that resource constraints are a major contributory factor where charities evidently meet only minimum levels of information disclosure. Charities are concerned and regretful that they often do not have the resources and systems to share their positive impact stories more effectively. The findings reveal that charity workers often feel forced or obliged to take up roles such as treasurer or secretary without the proper skill set since more able people are unavailable. The findings agree with previous studies that identified limited expertise and capability in data analysis and design of evaluations in the third sector (Carnochan et al., 2014; Bach-Mortensen and Montgomery, 2018). Small charities have limited volunteers and time resource to set aside the time required to think clearly about their stakeholders and accountabilities.

Overall, the findings suggest that small charities require more guidance and support around achieving a manageable and balanced communication with stakeholders. Sector support organisations could look to provide simple and effective approaches to data analysis and performance measurement for small charity sub-sectors, and charities themselves could do more to foster charity partnerships and communities of practice to share simple approaches to performance measurement. Despite the limited time resource, charities must dedicate time to consider their approaches to stakeholder accountability, since the research process has demonstrated the value of this type of reflection to all participants in the study.

The findings highlight that small charities and charity boards are often resistant to change; recruitment of new people can challenge the status quo and bring new skills for example in

data management or data analysis. Longstanding roles on boards and committees are often a barrier to change and there is need for charities and charity boards across the sector to discuss the need and scope for change more often. The findings also showed that charities require more urgency in implementing change where the need is identified. Organisational culture is critical in explaining small charity attitude to change, with staff resistance to evaluations and lack of board support being key factors in limiting information transparency (Ogain et al., 2012). The empirical findings show that charities believe small incremental changes are more viable for the sector rather than large system changes and the findings demonstrate that charities have more scope to consider how to tweak their current systems. Resistance to change is particularly problematic where charity founders are entrenched or where there is lack of separation between role of CEO and board trustee. The findings illustrate that parent organisations or overseeing bodies must think carefully about the negative impact on volunteers of enforcing too many administrative changes. On a positive note, the findings demonstrate that many charities across the sector are embracing evaluation processes with more enthusiasm as opposed to traditional fear.

Overall, the findings suggest that sector support organisations and other stakeholders such as funders must convince small charities and their boards of the benefits of embracing change. These changes must be small, incremental changes that contribute to the ongoing development and improvement of charities to the benefit of all, indeed small changes should be celebrated in the sector. The findings suggest that small charities would benefit from fostering a culture of accountability and transparency; however, this must be in the spirit of improving charity effectiveness in serving beneficiaries, be encouraged rather than imposed, and be proportionate to charity size and resources. The findings also highlight that small charities require some inspiration around the use of accountability mechanisms. Several participants in the research made clear that they are unaware of the extent to which mechanisms have multiple use or extent

to which information can be easily adapted or supplemented to serve multiple stakeholders. The findings demonstrate that charity events and open AGMs, for example, have untapped potential in the sector to meet multiple stakeholder needs. The findings highlighted the need for more engaging and accessible accounts of charity activity in the sector, to this end small charities would benefit from straightforward guides and templates to simplify preparation of visually appealing reports. Again, some advice and promotion of communities of practice for data presentation and accountability mechanisms would serve the needs of small charities in simplifying the discharging of accountability in the sector.

7.3.2 Environmental challenges

The impact of Covid brought with it serious operational challenges in the sector yet opportunity for charities to learn and grow in the face of crisis. The findings reveal that new digital skills were learned and used to connect remotely with beneficiaries and reach out with information to wider stakeholder groups. General awareness of digital solutions has been accelerated in the sector and charities are taking stock of what has worked best and should be taken forward. However, the findings demonstrate that Covid has had a serious impact on charity membership and participation; many charities are having to rebuild before they can contemplate how to improve their information sharing processes. The findings show that charities feel a dialogue with certain funders is required to remind them of ongoing social issues in communities beyond covid and covid recovery.

The ongoing cost of living crisis is having serious impact on all parts of the charitable sector with direct impact on beneficiaries and direct impact on volunteer supply and funding availability for charities. Charities identified that limited volunteerism and financial stress would constrain ability to meet stakeholder information needs. However, charities identified

that strong stakeholder relationships developed through good dialogue and information sharing were critical for sustaining them and their sector. Charities recognise the need to be more outward facing and accountable for their impact to attract and retain finance and members during a cost-of-living crisis. Most charities also identified the need for good communication with service users to build stronger trusting relationships.

The findings demonstrate that the competition for funds has intensified in the sector. Charities are concerned that intense competition for funds could see funds allocated to those charities that are most convincing rather than most effective. Some charities recognise that if they seek guidance and support to improve their communication and accountability, they could gain a competitive edge. Charities mostly appreciate the need for honest communication amongst local organisations to better understand the variety of issues in the community. Charities recognise that there are benefits to working in partnership with other charities but are often suspicious of intentions and motives.

The findings show that charities are bracing themselves for increased demand for transparency and accountability as beneficiaries, funders, members, and society seek evidence of value for money in times of austerity. However, some charities had experienced patience, understanding, and flexibility from funders regarding meeting their objectives in challenging times. Charities also feel the weight of responsibility and accountability for delivering supportive services in stressful and threatening times for their beneficiaries. The findings demonstrate that charities are committed and accountable to delivering on the charity mission and purpose during challenging times. One participant expressed frustration at the direction of legislation and trend for increased information and accountability in society; this was seen as an unnecessary burden for small charities.

7.3.3 Accountability tools and approaches

The findings show that small charities are embracing the idea of a communication plan to various extent across the sector. Communication plans are providing charities with an outline of stakeholders and identifying the information organisations should share with distinct groups. The findings demonstrate there is plenty of scope for further development and uptake in the sector. Likewise, detailed project plans and diaries are being considered by some charities to enhance internal accountabilities and feed into reports that meet external accountabilities. The findings reveal that very few charities across the sector are embracing tools and concepts like the Ecomap or equivalent to better understand their charity context and connections with stakeholders. Likewise, tools such as RACI diagrams that outline stakeholder information expectations and requirements have limited uptake in the sector. One participant endorsed a strategic tool known as the ‘lasting difference toolkit’ to help in the management and sustainability of small charities. The findings show that charities require intervention or training from experienced practitioners in the sector to implement these tools.

The findings show that newer digital solutions such as webinars are being used for sharing information and discharging accountability in response to Covid. Small charities mostly do not use specialist off-the-shelf software for data management and reporting either due to lack of awareness of these solutions, lack of willingness to learn, or lack of people and time. The findings demonstrate that small charities must be more selective and intelligent with their data to avoid being overwhelmed. Small charities tend to be re-active rather than pro-active regards handling data and information. The findings mostly agree with Ortega-Rodriquez et al (2020) that information and computer technology has emerged as a major mechanism of information disclosure and accountability. However, small charities are uncertain of potential for social media to satisfy various stakeholder needs and have some fears over its ability to be

manipulated. The findings suggest that small charities require some further guidance from sector support organisations in achieving balance and security in their use of online media.

To conclude, the findings highlight that many charities are making limited use of resources available from organisations such as the SCVO; identified by some charities as a free resource to help in all aspects of running a small charity. In addition, not all charities or charity boards are signed up to newsletters of OSCR and SCVO that can inform charities of important changes and the help available to the sector. The findings reveal that some charities identify need for more collaboration between and amongst local charities and funders to discuss streamlining of reporting requirements to benefit of all. The findings suggest that funders, and in particular fund providing charities, should take a leadership role in the sector for standardising their approaches to funding applications and monitoring reports to lessen the burden on small charities. In addition, given the fear and trepidation of imposed upward accountability amongst small charities, funders and fund providing charities have responsibility to reach out and reassure small charities, to foster stewardship type relationships and socialising forms of accountability. The findings demonstrate that the charity-charity board relationship is critical to charity success and for charity accountability. In addition to training on technical matters such as governance and financial management, sector support organisations must emphasise the softer skills required of boards to support their charities. The findings show that small charities prefer close relationships with their boards. Small charities are willing to demonstrate an internal functional and instrumental accountability to their boards, but this must be through supportive partnerships that can foster joint charity and charity board success, learning and growth. Small charities show that they require internal socialising forms of accountability with their boards, and they will continue to demonstrate a felt accountability to their social missions. The findings suggest that the charity regulator OSCR is functioning effectively for the sector and imposing minimal pressure on small charities. Treasurers of small charities are also

confident that their financial records and OSCR format accounts are robust and flexible enough accountability mechanisms to satisfy multiple internal and external stakeholders.

7.4 Reflections and Recommendations for future research

This section offers final reflections on the research that was undertaken and recommends further research opportunities. The discussion begins with a reflection on contribution to charity accountability research and the impact of the research for the small charity sector. The discussion then acknowledges the limitations of the study before identifying the potential for further research.

The research adds to the understanding of accountability in the charitable sector, in particular the research makes a significant contribution to accountability literature in the small charitable sector of Scotland. Past research conducted by the SCVO, for example, examined the nature of stakeholder trust in the sector, but this study looks to inform policy and practice of accountability from the small charity perspective. The research process also contributes to the personal and professional development of the researcher across the various academic and practical aspects of research. Of particular significance are the new skills gained in qualitative interview research. The research also highlighted the passion and dedication of, mostly volunteers, in the small charity sector, which is both inspiring and uplifting.

The research will contribute to the support resources and guidance available to individual small charities. Participating charities and their charity actors, and contacts in sector support organisations such as the SCVO, Scottish TSIs and Inspire Scotland have shown great enthusiasm for the research project and have requested a summary of the research findings and recommendations. It is hoped that the research report will contribute to support of small

charities in their locales and communities and the researcher looks forward to ongoing collaborations and working relationships with these organisations.

Future research outputs in the first instance include a report of key findings to enhance understanding and provide recommendations for improvements in accountability management practices in the sector. This will be achieved through presentations and preparation of a summary report to be made available to sector support organisations such as Scottish TSIs and other organisations with a keen interest in the study such as Inspire Scotland. The hope here is that the research can contribute to improvements in practice to benefit local community charitable organisations. A brief report on the research findings and recommendations will also be made available to the research participants for their own use and wider dissemination amongst their network of contacts since several participants are active in the charity finance and charity education and training communities. Charity accountability continues to be an ongoing conversation in the academic community, for example, the upcoming special focus within 'The British Accounting Review' on digitalisation in NGOs, explores many aspects of accountability in the current era of digital transform for NGO and charity sector. Indeed, data, information and technology emerged as an important theme for this research; this highlights the opportunities to engage with academic journals to share and publish the valuable findings and insights gained from research of the small charity sector. There exist further opportunities for academic output through relevant academic journals that have an ongoing interest in charity accountability such as 'Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly'. In addition, possibilities for presentation at various conferences such as those organised by the SCVO are being considered as viable platforms for sharing valuable research findings and insights to inform policy and practice.

The research has several limitations. Firstly, with extra time and resource the researcher would have liked to carry out a more robust first stage quantitative survey and analysis. This could

have been of equal weight and importance to the second stage qualitative interviews. It became clear during the research process that a combination of ongoing environmental pressures for small charities (Covid and Cost of living crisis) and the obvious difficulty in finding confident and willing participants in the small sector would limit survey research. Feedback from several sector support group contacts including the SCVO, TSIs and Inspire Scotland suggested that recruitment would be difficult in these challenging times for the sector. The researcher chose to adopt a more straightforward 'pre-interview questionnaire' to collect some basic quantitative and qualitative data from participants in advance of interview. The researcher also purposively widened the research to include views and perspectives from those in leadership positions in the small charitable sector i.e., both charity managers and charity board trustees. This was to achieve a more balanced and nuanced view of accountability and increase likelihood of achieving a good number of willing participants. Secondly, despite evidence that data saturation was reached with participants, this was a judgement call on the part of the researcher; it must be acknowledged that further in-depth interviews may have uncovered further new evidence and insights. Thirdly, as with all qualitative research, the external validity of the research is a point of contention, despite the researcher's best efforts to incorporate various charity types and charity roles within the study. Several participants were selected based upon their experience of serving in numerous roles, across various charity types to add more substantial representation to the study. The limitations of the research lead into the following section that suggests scope for further research in area of small charity accountability in Scotland.

The research undertaken highlights that small charity accountability is a research area that has plenty of scope for further exploration. Several avenues for further research have been identified:

- A larger sector wide quantitative survey to compare to the research findings, find supporting or conflicting evidence and test the research conclusions of this research. A larger sector wide survey would have to adopt a suitable sampling approach to achieve representation of different sectors e.g., quota sampling. The research would also likely have to be undertaken with a sector partner with access to a wide membership base such as the SCVO. A small number of charity leaders were sampled in this research.
- Sub-sector specific research to examine in detail the unique accountability context of sub-sectors such as religious organisations, scouting organisations, advocacy organisations, trust fund providing charities. These charity types were represented to some extent in this research, but not focussed on specifically.
- Stakeholders focus group research to bring together and share perspectives and insights on small charity accountability across key stakeholder groups such as charity managers, charity board members, volunteers, accountants, funders, beneficiaries. This could lead to more comprehensive multiple perspective solutions for small charity accountability. The perspectives of charity managers, charity trustees, and to some extent charity funders were explored in this research.
- Sector support organisation focus group research to explore the rich and detailed perspectives and experiences of these important sector stakeholders. This would enhance understanding of the infrastructure of support available for small charities and engagement levels and engagement strategies in the sector. These perspectives were explored to a limited extent in this research since some participants had previous sector support roles.
- Small charity financial accountability focussed research to explore the perspectives and behaviours of accountants, auditors and independent examiners, treasurers, and charity boards. This would enhance understanding of financial systems and scope, challenges,

and limitations of financial accountability in the small charity sector. Financial accountability was explored to a certain extent in this research through perspective of treasurers and charity boards.

In summary, there is need for further small charity accountability research to better understand the ongoing issues for the small charity sector and to find innovative solutions to the accountability challenges faced by small charities.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Invitation to an interview

Information sharing in the voluntary and charitable sector: a study of small organisations in Scotland.

An invitation to take part in a short interview...

The interviews are part of a doctoral research project exploring communication and information sharing within the charitable sector of Scotland. Themes or areas that are important for the study include: accountability, stakeholder relationships, information produced and shared by organisations, and the mechanisms or practical ways of sharing that information. Your views as a **Board/Committee Member or Senior Manager/Decision-Maker** of one of these organisations are crucial in enhancing our understanding of the practices and challenges around this important issue.

The target audience for this questionnaire are Charity board members or trustees, or managers of small charities. For this study, “small”, is defined as those organisations operating below a threshold of £250,000 annual income.

I know that you would find the discussions interesting and enjoy sharing your opinions and experiences. The aim of this study is to enhance understanding and contribute to the support of vital organisations like yours that operate in our local communities across the country. Participation in the interview will offer opportunity to reflect on some important challenges faced by your organisation. The research results will be shared later with you with a view to enhancing some important aspects of your organisation.

The interviews will be relaxed, informal, worthwhile, and rewarding to you and your organisation! A participant guide is provided beforehand so that you will be ready and confident on the day of the interview. In addition, a link to a short ‘pre-interview questionnaire’ will be provided in advance to collect some data and provide more background to the study. Interviews are conducted at a date/time that suits you and use the Microsoft Teams VC software- you simply click on the link to join in. Interviews are taking place ideally in the months of July, August, and September of 2022. The interview will typically last around 1 hour.

If this is something you and your organisation (or anyone else in your organisation) would be interested in, please contact me by email: Gerry.mcpake@uws.ac.uk

Best wishes, Gerry (researcher, lecturer at UWS)

Appendix 2: Extract of 'Pre-interview questionnaire' guidance

Introduction

This questionnaire is part of a doctoral research project exploring the issue of communication and information disclosure for small charities in Scotland. Your views are crucial in enhancing our understanding of the practices, issues, and challenges around this important issue. The target audience for this questionnaire are Board or Committee Members or Managers of small charities. For this study, "small", is defined as those organisations operating below a threshold of £250,000 annual income. You should be familiar with any reports prepared by your organisation, information that is shared, and the communications of the organisation. If you feel that another Board or Committee Member or Manager would be better placed to answer questions around your organisation's communications, information sharing, and disclosures then please direct them to this survey.

If you feel that this project is relevant and important to you then your participation would be greatly appreciated. However, your decision to take part is voluntary. The questionnaire should take around 10 minutes to complete. Please answer all questions and provide any further thoughts in the spaces provided. Your information will be treated in the strictest confidence. Your data will be anonymous and stored on a secure drive with password protection. Data will only ever be shared between researcher and research supervisor across a secure network. You will not be identified by either your name or organisation name in this study. Your data will be used for the primary purpose of completion of this doctoral research project being undertaken at University of the West of Scotland. These results will not usually be widely published but may be taken forward into an academic or professional research paper.

I hope that you find the questions interesting and enjoy sharing your opinions. The aim of this study is to enhance understanding and contribute to the support of vital organisations like yours that operate in our local communities across the country. Participation in this survey will offer opportunity to reflect on some important challenges faced by your organisation. The research results will be made available later to facilitate further discussion, collaboration, and enhancement of your organisation.

Accountability

This section introduces the issue of accountability as it relates to your organisation and your charitable or voluntary sector. Accountability refers to the sharing of information about your organisation and its activities; and Accountability refers to the request for information about your organisation from various parties internal and external to your organisation.

Accountability includes a consideration of WHAT your organisation is accountable for e.g., use of financial and other resources, quantity and quality of services, impact in the community. In addition, Accountability requires you to think about the reasons WHY your organisation is accountable e.g., for legal reasons, to attract finance, for ethical reasons. Accountability must consider the question of to WHOM is your organisation accountable e.g., finance providers, local community, users of your service, your own volunteers- this question will be dealt with more specifically in the subsequent section on stakeholders. An organisation must also consider HOW it will demonstrate or achieve its

Accountability i.e., ways of sharing information- this question will be dealt with in the final section of the survey.

Engaging with Stakeholders

This section explores the issue of stakeholders that are relevant to your organisation and your charitable or voluntary sector. When answering the questions below you should consider any persons or groups internal or external to the organisation who interacts with or are impacted by your organisation and its activities.

Examples of stakeholders include: your trustees/board/committee/management, employees or volunteers, members, regulators, government & local authority, finance providers, beneficiaries/users of your service, local community & the public.

Accountability Mechanisms

Accountability mechanisms refer to the variety of practical ways in which your organisation may communicate, disclose, or share information with its stakeholders. This can include different tools, processes, and media formats. These communications and information disclosures could for example be shared with your community, the wider public or be more private or direct in nature between the organisation and individuals or individual groups e.g., finance providers or users of your service. The accountability can be formal e.g., board meetings or annual reports or more informal e.g., newsletters and conversations.

Transparency

Transparency refers to the quantity and quality of information that is produced and shared by your organisation e.g., the types of information produced and shared and the ability of this information to provide people with what they need. Accountability mechanisms have potential to incorporate a number of different types of information. Types of information could include financial summaries and accounts, information regards services delivered and activities undertaken, information about how the organisation is run and managed, information regards the impact being made in the community. The following question grid asks you to consider the types of information that you produce and share through your different accountability mechanisms.

Identifying the type(s) of information shared: FINANCIAL = financial resources and spending. OUTPUTS = measuring or putting a number on what you do or provide. IMPACT = measuring or putting a number on positive change made to community and beyond. MISSION = measuring or explaining how activities are achieving organisation mission. MANAGEMENT = information about managers/committee/board and roles. NARRATIVE = explanations of the numbers and/or your activities.

Appendix 3: Introduction to the participants, their roles, and charities

Participant 1 is the chair for a charity that has 88 trustees. The participant joined the board in 2015 and took up the role of chair in 2020. The participant considers the organisation to be small in terms of turnover, but they try to have a large national impact. The organisation offers support to those caring for people with disabilities and advocates for change in policies and practice at local and national level. The focus of the organisation is on promoting self-directed support.

Participant 2 has broad experience in the charitable and non-profit sectors having occupied several trustee roles over many years. In addition, the participant has wider sectoral experience through work with Scottish third sector interfaces (TSIs) and involvement with Anti-poverty and Governance forums. The most recent organisations she has been involved with are trustee positions with a health and social care partnership and trustee roles with a charity that supports unpaid carers and a charity supporting ex-prisoners with various wrap-around services. Participant suggests that she will reflect significantly on a 'European Excellence Model' that provides a framework for how to run an excellent organisation, having experience of using this through her work with Quality Scotland. The participant has attempted to embed these principles in several organisations that she has worked with.

Participant 3 is a trustee and treasurer of an organisation that provides advanced driving assistance and tutoring. Although the primary role is to serve on the board as treasurer, the participant explains that she is also involved in the provision of the charity's services. The participant went on to explain that she considers the organisation to be a small local organisation with a small income. The primary source of income for the organisation is member subscriptions or donations, which are bolstered by some fundraising and grants.

Participant 4 is the chief executive of a charitable organisation that offers support and intervention for children through a “psychosocial program”, the chief executive considers this service to be a unique psychosocial intervention. The charity offers its service to the public and are based in an area of deprivation. The chief executive explains that the service is high level and equivalent to highest standards offered by the NHS or in the private sector.

Participant 5 is a highly experienced professional in the charitable and non-profit sector being involved with a high-profile sector support organisation. The participant has many years’ experiences of providing educational support around strategy, evaluations, and general board training. The participant currently occupies five different board roles across different charity sub-sectors including treasurer, chair and general trustee positions for financial trust and service providing charities.

Participant 6 is involved in a local charity operating in an area of deprivation. The charity itself has been running for around 30 years. The activities and services of the charity are around children, young people and families. They provide meals through breakfast clubs and lunches and a variety of family activities. The charity works with schools and churches in delivering their services. They have a small team of two full-time staff and several volunteers and sessional staff, the participant is the senior manager or chief exec of the organisation.

Participant 7 is the chief executive of an organisation that works with people in the community in an area of deprivation. The organisation has been based in this area for around 10 years. The organisation helps support a wide range of people with various challenging circumstances: people in recovery, people with poor mental health, and the parents and families. Funding is provided in most part by Scottish government and a local council community fund, these arrangements are pending soon so there is some funding uncertainty.

Participant 8 is a treasurer for a local scout group offering scouting activities for young people. The local committee has three core members: chairman, scout leader and treasurer. The charity raises funds through a combination of member subscriptions, fundraising events, and donations. Participant 8 is a professional accountant who volunteers service as trustee and treasurer. The local scout group is part of a larger regional, district and national organisation.

Participant 9 served on the board as both chair and treasurer of a community regeneration charity in an area of deprivation. The participant immediately indicates that this was a negative experience. Participant 9 has also served as a treasurer for a small unincorporated association but explains that for the interview he will reflect on his 10-year experience working for the community charity.

Participant 10 is currently involved with 3 non-profit organisations, with his main organisation and focus for reflection being a scouting group charity in which he has served as chair and has served as treasurer for the last 15 years. The participant has been involved in various other non-profit and voluntary organisations over a 20-year period, having broad experience of serving on various committees.

Participant 11 has had roles for around 10 years as secretary and convenor for PASDA, an organisation that offers support to parents of autistic adults. The organisation has been a Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation (SCIO) for around 5 years. The organisation is financed through a combination of membership payments, donations, and trust funds.

Participant 12 is very experienced in the charity and voluntary sector including working for a third sector interface (TSI) hub in areas of governance and funding. The participant has delivered education programmes on fundraising and has been a fundraising consultant for the sector. The participant will reflect upon different experiences in the sector including trustee

roles in grant making charities and trustee and staff roles in several other organisations over several years. The organisation is a Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation (SCIO).

Participant 13 is an Elder (member of the leadership group) and a trustee serving within an independent Church or Church family. The Church is a registered charity. The Church provides a means for members to worship and serve and has around 200 members and associated family members. The organisation has a constitution and a statement of faith, which states what they collectively believe in. Most Elders (leaders) are trustees and are the decision-makers for the Church.

Interview Participant Guide

Firstly, thank you for considering taking part in this interview. Your participation would be greatly appreciated and your views, experiences, opinions are valued.

The purpose of this document is to give you some background to the study and prepare you for the interview. The most important thing is that you feel comfortable and confident with the process. For your convenience, comfort, and flexibility an online VC interview has been selected. Although we have some important issues to discuss the interview will to my view be relaxed and informal in nature. I am sure that you will find the questions interesting and will enjoy sharing your opinions and experiences. The aim of this study is to enhance understanding and contribute to the support of vital organisations like yours that operate in our local communities across the country.

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of the research is to explore the ways in which small/micro charitable organisations are sharing information with their stakeholders. For this study, “small”, is defined as those organisations operating below a threshold of £250,000 annual income. Your views and experiences as a Board or Committee member or Charity manager and representative of your organisation are crucial in enhancing understanding of this issue for the sector. Board or Committee members should have experience of day-to-day operations and be familiar with any reports prepared by the organisation, information that is shared, and the communications by the organisation. Themes or areas that are important for the study include: accountability, stakeholder relationships, information produced and shared by organisations, and the mechanisms or practical ways of sharing that information.

Your agreement to take part

If you feel that this project is relevant and important to you then your participation in this interview would be greatly appreciated. However, your decision to take part is voluntary. The interview should take around 1 hour to complete. With your permission, the interview will be recorded and stored securely on the MS Teams platform. This recording will be deleted upon transcription into text. Your information will be treated in the strictest confidence. Your data will be stored on a secure drive with password protection. Data will only ever be shared between researcher and research supervisor across a secure network. You will not be identified by either your name or organisation name in this study- only your role and the activities of your organisation will be discussed in the research findings. Your data will be used for the primary purpose of completion of this doctoral research project being undertaken at University of the West of Scotland. These results will not usually be

widely published but may be taken forward into an academic or professional research paper.

Participant Consent

If you have read the section above and wish to participate in this study, please indicate your consent on the day of the interview. You will be asked if you agree to the following on the day:

I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information.

I understand that my participation in this study is completely voluntary, and I may exit the survey (or interview) at any point.

I agree to a recording of this interview (which will be deleted once transcribed to text)

I agree to take part in this study.

PLEASE NOW SEE THE “PREPARING FOR THE INTERVIEW” SECTION BELOW.

Preparing for the interview

In addition to the interview, there is a short questionnaire that offers a good introduction to the issues that are relevant to this research project. Please take the time to complete before commencement of the interview. Along with the information below the survey offers good preparation for the interview and will also provide some valuable data/information. The survey is found here: <https://forms.gle/2YfLJ7uWVDzqc5k86>

It is suggested that participants might take some time to consider the themes or areas that will be explored below before commencement of the interview. Participants may for example wish to confer/discuss with fellow members and/or assemble and consult with relevant organisation documents and information. The themes/areas are:

Theme 1- Accountability (background).

Here is a brief definition or explanation of Accountability:

Accountability refers to the sharing of information about your organisation and its activities; and Accountability refers to the request for information about your organisation from various parties internal and external to your organisation. Accountability includes a consideration of WHAT your organisation is accountable for e.g., use of financial and other resources, quantity and quality of services, impact in the community. In addition, Accountability requires you to think about the reasons WHY your organisation is accountable e.g., for legal reasons, to attract finance, for ethical reasons. Accountability must consider the question of to WHOM is your organisation accountable e.g., finance providers, local community, users of your service, your own volunteers. An organisation

must also consider HOW it will demonstrate or achieve its Accountability i.e., ways of sharing information.

The type of things we might discuss here include what things the organisation feels it is or should be accountable for and the reasons for this.

Theme 2- Data & Information (background).

Here is a brief guide to types of data & information that are relevant about most organisations in the sector:

Types of information could include financial summaries and accounts, information regards services delivered and activities undertaken, information about how the organisation is run and managed, information regards the impact being made in the community.

FINANCIAL DATA = financial resources and spending. OUTPUT DATA = measuring or putting a number on what you do or provide. IMPACT DATA = measuring or putting a number on positive change made to community and beyond. MISSION DATA = measuring or explaining how activities are achieving organisation mission. MANAGEMENT DATA = information about managers/committee/board and roles. NARRATIVE DATA = explanations of the numbers and/or your activities.

The type of things we might discuss here include the data and information that is collected about the organisation and what is or can be done with it.

Theme 3- Stakeholders.

Here is a brief definition of a stakeholder and a list of possible stakeholders:

A stakeholder is any persons or groups internal or external to the organisation who interacts with or are impacted by your organisation and its activities. Examples of stakeholders include: your trustees/board/committee/management, employees or volunteers, members, regulators, government & local authority, finance providers, beneficiaries/users of your service, local community & the public.

The type of things we might discuss here include who your stakeholders are, the relationships you have with them, and managing their information needs.

Theme 4: Accountability mechanisms.

Here is a brief definition of accountability mechanisms and a list of possible accountability mechanisms:

Accountability mechanisms refer to the variety of practical ways in which your organisation may communicate, disclose, or share information with its stakeholders. This can include different tools, processes, and media formats. These communications and information

disclosures could for example be shared with your community, the wider public or be more private or direct in nature between the organisation and individuals or individual groups e.g., finance providers or users of your service. The accountability can be formal e.g., board meetings or annual reports or more informal e.g., newsletters and conversations. Examples include Annual report, Annual review, Newsletter or Press release, producing plans, Website & social media, AGM, Board/Committee meetings, Meetings open to the public, Stakeholders observing or participating, Direct or Private communications, Consultations with beneficiaries, Audit or Independent review, Accreditation or Certification.

The type of things we might discuss here include the accountability mechanisms your organisation uses (or do not use) and why, the scope of some mechanisms to have multiple uses, and the features, benefits, and challenges of different accountability mechanisms.

Theme 5 Closing thoughts and Current Issues.

The type of things we might discuss here include any final thoughts on the issues that were explored and anything relevant we have missed. Also, we can reflect on the issues above as they relate to ongoing and future challenges for the sector such as impact of pandemic, cost of living crisis and financial constraints. Are the issues above pertinent and urgent?

Appendix 5: Semi-structured interview schedule

Introduction:

Personal notes: There may be some participants with experience of serving on Board/Committee of various organisations. Questions must be re-phrased to accommodate. Participants might speak to one, a few or broad experiences, current or more recent).
“Thinking/Reflecting on the organisations you have been involved with...”

Thank you for agreeing to take part. Your views are important and there are obviously no right or wrong answers- your honest opinions, views and sharing of experiences are most important.

Can I just confirm that you read the ‘Participant Interview Guide’ including the section on your agreement to participate? Are you happy to participate? Again, as per the guide, I can assure you that your data will be handled in a secure and confidential manner, you will only be identified by organisation activities and role- your name and organisation name will not be used.

If you don’t mind this meeting is being recorded and transcribed using the Teams software. The video recording is only there to help with transcription and will be deleted when text transcription is complete.

Organisation and Role:

Question: Could you provide a brief description of your organisation and its activities?

Question: Could you briefly describe your role in the organisation?

I have a few questions organised around the five themes I indicated in the ‘Participant Interview Guide’. Themes 1 and 2 (accountability and data & information) are to provide some background and context to support the focus of the interview, which are themes 3 and 4 (stakeholders and accountability mechanisms). Theme 5 allows us to pick up on anything else you feel is relevant and some consideration of what this all means for your organisation moving forward (closing thoughts). There will likely be some overlap between thematic areas since they are inter-dependent.

Theme 1 Accountability.

This first theme explores your views on accountability and what it means to you and your organisation. Accountability means to “offer an account” of the organisation, its activities, and its performance e.g., how it is run or managed, what resources it has under its control, how resources have been used, what has been delivered or achieved. The ‘Participant Information Guide’ offered a brief definition and explanation of accountability.

(May have to provide a reminder for participant re definition/explanation of accountability.)

Main Question: What things do you feel you, your colleagues and the organisation are accountable for- and what are the reasons for this?

Further probing questions if required:

- What type of things are you accountable for?
- What type of things are you not accountable for?
- Who are you accountable to?
- Would you say you hold yourselves to account- internally?
- Why are you accountable? What drives your accountability? And any motivations for being accountable? How important is this idea of accountability to you and your organisation?
- Is accountability something that is regularly discussed within the organisation?
- Is this a difficult question to address for you and the organisation?

Theme 2 Data & Information.

This leads us to consider the data & information that could “offer an account” of the organisation and its performance e.g., financial, and other assets or resources, outputs such as activities and services delivered, outcomes (positive impact) achieved for the community, narratives that explain activities and achievements.

The ‘Participant Information Guide’ offered a brief explanation and examples of data & information that are typically relevant to organisations in the sector. I hope that you found this to be helpful.

(May have to provide a reminder to participant re typical data and information for organisations in the sector.)

Main Question: What types of data and information are collected about the organisation and its activities?

Further probing questions if required:

- What do you do with the data and information? Summarise, Analyse, Prepare reports?
- Does the organisation have any established ways of measuring how it is performing?

- Can you provide some detail or examples of the processes or ways things are done and the people involved?
- Would you say that you are satisfied with the way your organisation manages data about itself or could more be done? Is this something that has been discussed within the organisation?
- Any other thoughts on the issues or challenges with handling this data and information?

Theme 3 Stakeholders:

Having considered the idea of accountability and the handling of data & information in your organisation we now turn our attention specifically to your organisation's stakeholders. These are individuals or groups that the organisation (in this context) may share information with.

Again, the 'Participant Information Guide' offered a brief definition of a stakeholder and provided a list of possible stakeholders for organisations in the sector. I hope that this was helpful.

(May have to provide a reminder to participant re basic definition and some examples of typical stakeholders in the sector.) Finance providers, Regulators, Beneficiaries/Users, Local Authority, Parent organisation, Internal Board/Committee/Volunteers.

Main Question: Who are your organisation's stakeholders, and can you describe the relationships you have with them?

Further probing questions if required:

- Who do you feel are the most important/prioritised and why?
- What types of information do you share with your different stakeholders? How often? When?
- What are the benefits of being able to supply stakeholders with information they need?
- What challenges do you face in supplying your stakeholders with the information they need?
- To what extent do you believe you currently meet information needs of your stakeholders?
- Can you give any examples of positive or negative experiences related to the issue of providing stakeholders with information?

Theme 4 Accountability mechanisms:

We can now think about the practical means by which the organisation can share information with its stakeholders to be accountable (“discharge accountability”). These are methods of sharing information about the organisation or “offering an account” of, its activities, its performance, and achievements are called “accountability mechanisms”.

The ‘Participant Information Guide’ offered a brief definition of accountability mechanisms and examples of possible mechanisms that could be used by organisations in the sector. I hope this was helpful.

(May have to provide a reminder to participant re definition of the term accountability mechanism and some examples of mechanisms that could be used)

Main Question: Practically speaking, how does the organisation communicate with stakeholders and share information to “offer an account” of itself?

This can be both internally and externally. This could be phrased more succinctly as what accountability mechanisms do you use?

Further probing questions if required:

- What would you say are your most important or most used accountability mechanisms?
- Can you give some examples of information that are shared/disclosed using the different mechanisms?
- What are the factors that determine your choice of mechanisms used i.e., have you thought about why do you use some mechanisms and not others?
- Are there any mechanisms that currently have multiple uses i.e., used to provide information to more than one stakeholder or stakeholder group? Are there any that could have multiple use?
- Can you see any potential for making better use of your existing mechanisms or adopting some new mechanisms to improve information sharing with stakeholders? Is this something anyone in the organisation has discussed?
- Can you give any examples of positive or negative experiences related to the use of accountability mechanisms?

Theme 5 Closing thoughts and Current Issues:

- 1) Any final thoughts on the issues explored above or anything relevant you think we have missed?**

There are ongoing and future challenges for the sector, especially in context of covid and the cost-of-living crisis.

- 2) In this context do you have any thoughts on the importance of the issues above around: building stakeholder relationships, meeting stakeholder information needs, use of accountability mechanisms going forward for your organisation?**

Appendix 6: Ethics Approval Letter

18/11/2021

Dear Mr Gerry McPake,

Your application 17174: DBA Ethics application (GMcPake), submission 14304, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC.

You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix 7: OVER-ARCHING THEME 3: Need to Change and Find Solutions

This over-arching theme explores participant accounts of how they recognise the need for change and the need to find accountability solutions. As part of the conversation around accountability, accountability to stakeholders and accountability mechanisms, participants would inevitably reflect on their organisations need and capability to make changes. These reflections would often include a consideration of the organisation's current situation and steps that would have to be taken to improve their accountability to stakeholders. Several stakeholders identified tools available for the sector; whilst others reflected on the environmental challenges that could be barriers or instigators of change. The over-arching theme captures lower-level interpretive themes of 'environmental challenges', 'ability to change' and 'accountability tools'. At the lowest descriptive thematic level participants described several issues related to themes such as 'covid impact', 'cost of living crisis'; the charity's 'attitude and desire to change', 'resource constraints', 'external support resources'; and accountability tools of 'multiple use mechanisms & information', 'specific tools & approaches'. The process of coding and re-coding at different thematic levels eventually produced the following thematic structure:

Figure 16: Thematic structure 'Need to Change and Find Solutions'

Source: Author

Ability of organisations in the sector to change

Participant 1 pointed to the importance of frequent monitoring of the skill set of the board since people “come and go” in small voluntary and charitable organisations. Board recruitment was seen as very important for the organisation to maintain levels of expertise across different roles in the organisation, for example in area of campaigning. Participant 1 later identified evaluations as an area of weakness for the organisation, expressing some regret that they had failed to capture and share information on successful programmes due to their resource constraints:

We have not captured that, that impact in an effective way yet. So, we don't have the evidence to go back every year to funders to get the funding to come into this and to continue to support it. So, it's one of those bits where the evaluation process hasn't been as effective as it should have been and it's critical because it's probably for me one of the most effective change programmes I've ever seen. So, to miss that opportunity was an error, a big error on our part, and we're only now beginning to address how we overcome that. So, you know, but it's a question of timing and capacity. It's very difficult (Participant 1).

Participant 1 later commented that their board structure was a “critical vehicle” for representing and addressing the needs of their beneficiaries; it was felt there was room for improvement in how the board was structured. Participant 1 also reflected on the fact that their constitution was broad enough to accommodate growth in their service to beneficiaries but identified that growth is a dilemma for small organisations like theirs:

Yeah, well see, it's a dilemma because I think this is the challenge for a small organisation. Do you stay small? That is the big question. I think we had a real dilemma actually when our last director finished; they wanted me to be a new director and a

new director to lead the organisation, and in a small organisation that director is pivotal. If you get the wrong person, it's going to be disastrous. But the question did arise and what is the organisation going to become and that's a point where you really do start to challenge the nature of the organisation's board. But we've still not cracked the question do we stay small? You know, there's so much more we could do (Participant 1).

Participant 1 went on to explain that staff preferred to work for a small organisation with a flat structure since this gave them more responsibility and made their work more worthwhile. The resource requirements in terms of skills and finance were also described as being a major challenge to their growth therefore it was reasoned that it was more realistic to find ways of growing slowly. Participant 1 concluded the interview by commenting that the interview process had been extremely valuable since it had provided dedicated time to think hard about stakeholders and accountability.

Participant 2 expressed concern that organisations were mostly reacting in ad-hoc manner to operational and governance problems as they would arise, rather than adopting tools and processes that would promote regular scrutiny and prevention:

And if you have a major blip, you just deal with it there and then and take the consequences of that. Or do you want to avoid this and have no problem, have no big bill, bad publicity, whatever. So, are you more inclined to do some regular maintenance around, you know, how well is the organisation running? Are we complying with all the policies, and do we know why we're complying with them, and we keep the policies up to date, all that stuff. It's educating board members to realise they are accountable for knowing all that stuff is running well (Participant 2).

Participant 2 reflected on the fact that it would often require new people to enter or engage with organisations to challenge the way things were being done e.g., people with experience in data management or analysis could suggest ways to improve. Participant 2 observed that unless an organisation was “healthy enough” then they would not take the time to challenge what they do and settle for what was always done. It was later commented that many organisations in the sector had focus on good service delivery but were less inclined to think about their infrastructure and sustainability. In addition, participant 2 identified that only those organisations with a continuous improvement mentality were likely to implement tools to enhance understanding of stakeholders and stakeholder communications. As a word of caution, participant 2 later reflected that there could be occasions where board members and managers may wish to introduce new strategies, but large-scale change was not required. Refinement and incremental improvement are often required rather than brand new initiatives and wholesale change. Participant 2 concluded that there should be reflection on current systems or ways of working to avoid replacing or duplicating for example existing reports. There was a strong belief too that organisations should be making better use of what they already have and would benefit from tweaking rather than re-inventing.

When asked whether the organisation would discuss potential for doing things differently regards data and information sharing, participant 3 stated that they would not often discuss the need for change or scope to do things differently. It was felt that longstanding roles could be a barrier to change whereas new appointments could instigate conversation and action for positive change:

We don't really. I think one of the problems we have in our group as you can imagine is the people willing to be on the committee, which is probably something that comes up in lots of small groups. So, the secretary's been in the role for a long, long time, they have been in the role for about maybe eight years or something like that. So, there's

not changes regularly. And I think that would start to generate new ways of doing things. I think when I took over as treasurer from the old treasurer there was frustration with him about the way he did things. When I came the committee had a very clear ask of, we just want better information better organised. So that was something that came about. But I think that we do sometimes get stuck, we don't ask questions about how we would do it better or handle it better (Participant 3).

Participant 3 later added that there was a failure by the organisation to act on some discussions they had around social media adoption; it was felt strongly that the group dynamic of the committee, including age profile, meant that they were stuck in their ways, tending to do the same things. It was acknowledged that this way of operating in a routine fashion could be detrimental to their organisation. It was later commented that the organisation did not think about their communication or accountability mechanisms, they would simply be driven by what was required; with limited appetite for change they would only change if demanded by the regulator. However, their small size and limited resources was also an explanatory factor in their resistance to go beyond the minimum efforts of information disclosure. Participant 3 later reflected on the fact that lack of knowledge and skills of people was an important factor and there was a feeling amongst committee members that they were being forced to some extent to do their roles without the proper skill set, for example the secretary or treasurer roles. It was felt that there should have been some more support, especially where things are unique or different to standard approaches for example with the format of accounts. However, it was her experience that OSCR was a positive and supporting stakeholder in this respect, offering advice, guidance, and clarity around what was required to meet regulatory obligations. It was believed strongly that volunteers in small community groups may not have the skills and training to meet the accountability challenge and issue, and the availability of support resource was questioned:

Obviously as you often find in community groups, it's kind of volunteers that step up to do these things and maybe not trained specifically in the role. So, you know, is there ongoing support that's needed to help people do those things, I mean, and we just haven't tapped into it? But you know what, if you wanted organisations like ours to do more reporting, then is there support available for that, even if it's sort of online? Whatever kind of detail to do the things or so that you give people the skill to be able to do it (Participant 3).

Participant 3 also expressed some frustration around changing requirements and expectations of the parent organisation, who would sometimes impose changes around the constitution and rules for committee membership. It was felt that overseeing bodies could have a negative effect on motivation amongst volunteers if they become more stringent with what they want from the organisation and its staff.

Participant 4 suggested that attracting high calibre directors was a problem for their charity and elsewhere in the sector. The management team lent heavily on the directors and some wider stakeholders to advise and consult on difficult and sensitive matters relating to service provision in addition to the general oversight and governance. The Chair for example was retiring soon, and it would be difficult to replace such a valuable stakeholder. Participant 4 explained that he felt it important to continually review their policies around information sharing to be ahead of any developments and avoid complacency. However, IT was identified as an area where there was a lack of expertise, which could limit their access and use of digital information. Furthermore, it was later reasoned that they needed a social media strategy to share details on what they do and the impact that their programs have, but they simply did not have the time to work on this:

We're looking at the moment to upgrade, we don't have a social media strategy Gerry, but just because of what I covered you know, we haven't been able to devote time to things like that. It's been very difficult, but now we're looking to expand on that, just reach out across different platforms and what we share will detail, you know, the issues faced by our clients, what are prominent in their community, which then cover the impact of the program overall is what we'd like to share. Not really to say that we'll advertise, we will obviously still maintain the GPs as gatekeepers, but just to make people aware of what's happening in the community (Participant 4).

Participant 4 later added that they were confident they had data to share, but they had to think hard about how to collate this and think creatively in how to use it effectively. Participant 4 expressed deep regret that they had failed to share information on most of their positive stories. Several stakeholders had advised sharing more information regarding their service and achievements, but there were reservations over advertising a service with limited resource:

We've got so many positive stories that we've hardly ever touched, less than 1% has ever been put out there, and I think that's one of the failings of us. And you know guys like our philanthropist or even our legal advisors have said you need to get that message out there more. But our worry is when we put that out there, we don't have the capacity level (Participant 4).

Participant 5 commented that it would be beneficial for charity managers to be able to enhance their reports with visual aids such as infographics but noted that most charities were not skilled at these types of things. It was later added that charities often did not have the skills for data analysis or evaluation and had very little time to think about creative ways to communicate, but a solution would be to bring in people with the necessary skill sets:

You've got all of this data; this really shows how big the problem is, so how do we get that over? How necessary is this funding, you know, the funding application and you've got all this data that shows it's really necessary. Presentation and evaluation. And guess what? They're busy, you know, delivering the service, and it's no disrespect to anyone that works in charities, that they're not, they don't typically employ evaluators and data mining analysts, but you can, you know, you can get the help parachuted in (Participant 5).

Participant 5 later reflected that although the board should not interfere, they should be helpful in this respect by finding the external people that were needed. It was also believed that the board had a role in suggesting how the charity could improve its communication mechanisms, such as recommending how the operating team could summarise or adapt their financial reports. Participant 5 expressed some excitement around the positivity in seeing trustees that were willing to take the time to learn how to become more resilient and sustainable. However, it was found that board resistance to change was a negative constraining factor, especially where founders opposed changes that were not aligned to their initial vision for the charity. It was felt that it was particularly problematic where the founder was both a CEO and a Trustee, often able to hold sway over other trustees for board decisions. Several solutions were offered by participant 5 including forcefulness in citing rules and regulations to force change, or write-in a reasonable maximum period of registration. There was a strong wish for all charity boards to have separation between the roles of CEO and the board of trustees.

Participant 6 felt that they had struggled to balance their time constraints between the need for continuous consultation and evaluation, and undertaking the actual work involved in delivering their service. It was also difficult to recruit board members locally since those that were viable would often be involved with other groups, there was also a concern that new board members may often want to change the way that things were being done and this was seen as a negative.

Participant 7 expressed a strong belief that as a charity it was important to them to put aside time for reflection and improvement. Part of this self-improvement was a consideration of their relationships with stakeholders and their ways of sharing information. Participant 7 later reasoned that it was important to evolve as an organisation and look for different solutions to the accountability challenges; they hadn't found the perfect system yet and were unsure of what was available:

But I suppose the important thing is that we try, that we do reflect, and we do try to evolve and move with the times, there's continual evolution I suppose. There's different sort of software and stuff, that captures all these informations, and it's just about finding the one that works I suppose better for you, and that you can pick information in and out of. I don't think we have found that quite yet; I don't think we have found the perfect one. Again, is the perfect one out there? I don't know, but I'm sure that there's probably something out there that is better than what we're currently doing (Participant 7).

Participant 8 expressed a desire to receive more feedback and opinions from their members; it would happen informally through casual chat but not through more effective mechanisms such as the weekly meetings or the AGM. It was felt that not much more could be done to change this. It was explained later that the charity itself could be better at sharing information rather than relying on these informal mechanisms. It was felt that a lot of positive things were happening quietly in the background, for example grants being used for asset purchases and property improvements. On further reflection it was reasoned that sharing more information could be useful in attracting more children and members:

I don't think we do make enough of it; it's all left to very informal devices like the, you know, just people picking the kids up, noticing things being said by the scout leaders to

the kids, the kids telling the parents. But it's never broadcast beyond that. I mean, we could probably have a bit in the place about, you know, getting a Covid grant and beefing up the whole place and things like that. But we just, we just do things quietly in the background, probably don't draw attention to it enough, and in actual fact it would help us because it might get more scouts in (Participant 8).

Participant 8 then turned to thoughts around their capacity to handle any increased interest in their organisation, but also reasoned that positive news stories or disclosure around their activities would likely encourage more participation and volunteerism to support their service. Participant 8 reflected on the fact that it would take small effort to bolster their newsletters for example with information on their plans and spending. However, it was felt that they didn't spend enough time thinking about better ways to communicate, explaining that they would "bumble along and don't really change what you do, you just do the same thing over and over".

Participant 9 believed strongly that their organisation and others in the sector should be reaching out for help with governance and accountability. However, he was frustrated that both the charity board and chief executive were not motivated to do this since it might affect the ability, especially of the chief executive, to control and direct matters. Participant 9 later explained that he had tried to ignore some of the issues he had identified with the role being played out by the chief executive, but problems came up when he attempted to challenge the status quo and make changes. It was explained that there was great frustration at working within a board with inadequate knowledge to undertake their roles. It was felt that data and information was scarce within the organisation but questioned whether the board would have the ability to process and understand it. Overall, there was a feeling that the chief executive was stifling any significant change and was able to control a weak and incompetent board of trustees. Participant 9 later reflected on the fact that most of the board had never really contemplated the need for training around governance and accountability. The treasurer, as a professional

personal, had undertaken training but other board members didn't see the need and felt threatened:

The board never thought they needed any training. You know, the new treasurer who, you know, was a professional person before, took himself on courses run by OSCR and run by other similar organisations, which was great. But the others didn't think they needed to be. You know, they just thought they were part of the communities that were there, and I think they were probably threatened. And I think for sure they were very threatened by all of this kind of stuff, and they probably saw the executive director as a sort of protector of them and their deficiencies (Participant 9).

Participant 9 later expressed the opinion that the chief executive and board were resistant to meaningful feedback processes since this would hold up an unflattering mirror to the organisation and people involved. With some sadness it was observed that things could have been different if the right skills and educated people had been involved with the organisation. It was believed strongly that small charities like theirs must have the foundations of good basic governance and accountability in place to ultimately be effective in helping the community. Participant 9 suggested that meaningful change would not be possible in their charity whilst these foundations were underappreciated. It was acknowledged that guidance and support was available to help build and improve their organisation, but with their mindset people were unlikely to engage with this.

Participant 11 took time to reflect on the challenges of keeping up with the various digital platforms; they tried to use them all to some extent, but there was a lack of staff and funding for staff. There was lack of finance to maintain their IT systems and indeed to meet their ongoing running costs:

The challenge is, I mean, when I was young there was only writing letters or phone calls. But now there's so many platforms from email, WhatsApp, Facebook etc etc. So, we try and do all of them, and some people answer some and not others. Oh, I never reply to my emails, or oh I don't use WhatsApp, or God I hate Twitter, you know. So, we try to do a bit of everything and just tweak it a bit for each platform. But the main challenge is, yeah, lack of staff and that's what most of the funding is for. You know, who's gonna pay for my IT? Who's gonna pay for the virus checkers, and the maintenance, the office rent and the accountant who needs paying. The payroll system? You know all these things we need money for, and so yeah that is the main challenge (Participant 11).

Participant 11 later commented on the challenge of maintaining and managing volunteers. It was felt that volunteers required a lot of guidance and support, but they simply did not have the resources for this. It was then reasoned that the organisation did not have much scope or ability to do any more in terms of information sharing given they were busy volunteers and were unable to employ people to do this. It was explained that they were unsure how to do more reaching out to stakeholders and required advice on these matters:

I mean, I already work, I should think 30 to 40 hours per week in my voluntary role and I still have my daughter, and I still have to run the house. And most of the board members would say the same, they don't have quite as much time. But the paid members of staff, yeah, I'm sure we could reach out more, but I don't know how, I'd like more advice on how to do that. But more than that, I would like funding. I'd like funding to employ more people to do these things (Participant 11).

Participant 11 expressed some frustration that many board members did not understand the concepts and terminology around accountability. It was felt that many board members found

the financial details and techniques uninteresting and so there was resistance to learning about these critical aspects of board oversight:

One of the difficulties I think from the countryside is that most of the board members haven't got a clue. I think if you use those kinds of words people turn off immediately. They're not the least bit interested. It's really hard to get trustees engaged because it's never been part of their life. I don't want to know about accountability mechanisms. I don't want to know about spreadsheets. They don't want to know about the terminology that accountants use, they're not the least bit interested. They want to know when are they gonna get a mental health nurse or when are they going to get a job, you know, all that kind of thing. They're not the least bit interested (Participant 11).

Participant 12 expressed some excitement at witnessing a change in perspective within the sector, with many organisations now committing to evaluation processes as opposed to traditional feelings of trepidation around reporting requirements. It was exciting to see the transition away from doing things simply to meet funder demands:

And it's interesting, having been, you know, in the sector for a very long time. I've seen that transition from funders asking for reports and organisations going oh no I've gotta do this, rather than a genuine commitment to evaluation over everything they do. And that evaluation is really important across all of their activities, rather than just being something, they do because a funder demands. And that's been really exciting to see! (Participant 11).

Participant 13 explained that they didn't make much use of social media and that this was not updated regularly, largely because they did not have the people to do it. It was also believed that the organisation was not necessarily obliged to share information on social media and suggested that social media communication could cause problems. When asked about the wider

issue of sharing information with stakeholders, it was reasoned that the organisation was doing its best with limited resources. However, it was also felt quite strongly that resources could be wasted on such things and to the detriment of their actual activities and service:

I think we're trying to do as best we can. You know I think there's always room for improvement obviously, but you know, we're a volunteer organisation primarily. We wouldn't want to put lots of resources into management things like that, we'd want to put our effort into the actual kind of front-line of actual doing the work type stuff. So, we would want to keep governance as light as possible, and we think that should be the presiding culture, but we recognise that you want to put things in place that are good. But it's just being careful it doesn't become a kind of tick box type of thing. What are the key things that actually need to be done and stick to them and not get too carried away with all the other stuff that can maybe just take up too much time. That would be the concern with this stuff (Participant 13).

Environmental challenges for the sector

Participant 1 identified Covid as having a serious impact on their ability to operate, given their vulnerable beneficiaries. However, Covid led them to develop webinars and online channels to allow them to reach out with information to their users and wider stakeholders. This was described as a great learning experience allowing the organisation to develop useful skills to take forward. Participant 1 reflected on the current economic conditions or cost of living crisis commenting that there would be a serious direct impact on their beneficiaries and on the government funding to support their organisation's activities. It was felt that strong stakeholder relationships re-enforced by effective ways of sharing information would be critical to maintain small organisations like theirs:

I think, which is crystal clear to me, is only those that have got those strong relationships and those relationships are formed by how good you are reporting and maintaining those relationships in terms of information sharing and in terms of dialogue and discussion. You know, so for us if the Scottish Government funding went, we'd probably not be here, that would be the end of us. So, the fact that we've been building that relationship with them and now meeting them on a monthly basis, you know it used to be every six months, but now it's monthly as well. You know, it's those types of things that are going to be critical to sustaining the third sector, particularly small ones (Participant 1).

Participant 2 observed that Covid had acted to speed up charity awareness of digital solutions. In some organisations she noticed that Covid had been good for kickstarting change in organisations as they realised that they could reach out to people online; this had in some cases resulted in increased uptake of services. However, there were downsides to not having private face-to-face meetings where issues could be discussed honestly e.g., with the unpaid carers organisation the cared for person could be in the room during online sessions. There was a feeling that all organisations should reflect on their Covid experience of what worked and what didn't work to instigate changes where appropriate.

Participant 3 commented that Covid had a serious impact on their membership and participation. It was reasoned that the organisation would need time to rebuild before they could contemplate more reaching out to their stakeholders with information. The issue of capacity was also raised with the concern that wider information sharing could attract too much interest and place too much of a burden on limited resource:

So, it's difficult and obviously Covid has given us a lot of problems in terms of membership because people have just fallen away from all sorts of activities. So, we

almost need a rebuild before we can do more reaching out, because if we want the things, I think we're afraid of social media, if we grow a bit too quickly, do we have a backdrop to be able to support that? So, I think that's a bit of fear of sharing information too widely is that then? Participant 3

Participant 3 identified that increased financial pressures due to a squeeze on the cost of living would mean that people would want more value for money and an increased accountability for that money. There would be increased scrutiny of the sector when users discriminated to select only legitimate organisations that were well managed. It was felt that service users, as well as funders, would seek assurances in the form of robust information that showed beneficiaries were indeed benefiting from services. There would be an increased threat to their organisation in the form of both increasing costs to themselves and their service users.

Participant 4 explained that he, and the organisation more widely, had felt the weight of accountability during Covid due to the increased reliance on their service. The accountabilities to their users and the various connected stakeholders around their service were more onerous. Indeed, the charity itself had almost succumbed to the financial and human resource pressures enacted by Covid and participant 4 expressed anger around their ineligibility for support:

It was touch and go, lottery was told not to fund projects that weren't specifically dealing with Covid and some of the big charities that shut down and they took furlough. We didn't take furlough. We were running with twenty-five significantly damaged clients, sexual assaults, all sorts of things like that nature. And you know, staff, the staff members were burnt out completely. I gave lottery such a hard time for that. And then the government set up a scheme for supporting charities that managed to function, but because we didn't make a profit or charge our clients, we were declined access to that

fund. And that was Scottish Government, and again I spoke to ministers up there and said that's disgraceful. So, there's lots of things that we did challenge (Participant 4).

However, Participant 4 later commented that in wake of Covid and the cost-of-living crisis, there would have to be more focus on mission and needs rather than the pursuit of funding, which some charities were guilty of. It was also acknowledged that funders such as Lottery Fund had shown patience and understanding in circumstances where the organisation had struggled to deliver on all their objectives; it was felt that the Lottery Fund had been brave in this respect.

Participant 5 pointed to the fact that charities were often competing with others for the same pot of money. It was reasoned that charities must make better use of the resources that were available, for example, guidance around governance and how to communicate charity governance; this would be critical in giving a charity a competitive edge in securing funding:

So, see if I was asked about my governance, I would make sure that I'd done some of the SCVO self-check-up and then I would report those results back, you know, just use the resources that are out there. It's a competitive business, you need to be better than the charity next door because that means you might get the money. And they won't. But that's, I'm sorry, the reality. If there's one pot of money you want your organisation to get it, so do as much as you possibly can to put yourself ahead (Participant 5).

Participant 5 later commented that although charities can often be in competition, they could still have dialogue with one another. From personal experience it was strongly believed that it was beneficial for boards to come together, coalesce and discuss solutions for common issues but conceded that there was uncertainty around how to encourage this in the sector.

Participant 6 expressed a strong belief that their charity had to follow their charitable mission and purpose even during the difficulties of the pandemic. It was felt that the charity had a duty

to deliver on its mission, they were accountable for this, whereas the local council for example did not have such accountability. It was later commented that there was an expectation on the third sector to help with the energy and cost of living crisis, but that the sector required more financial support to do this; this was demanding and challenging. There was frustration and annoyance with local authorities for believing that small charities could do things cheaply and that volunteerism was free:

There's an expectation of the third sector to deliver things like warm banks, heat hubs and all of these things. But who's paying now? Well, you could open up your churches, your halls and stuff like that. Are you gonna give me any money to do that because we have seen more and more people coming forward looking for support, but not getting more and more money. So, you know, people expect us to do social work, will expect us to go to the foodbank and get a parcel and take it to someone and because we've got relationships with people, you can't really say no we're not doing it. So, that's become quite challenging, just the ongoing demands on the third sector. I would say that the local authority think that you can just do things cheaply. And you can't. And they always think volunteering is free as well and they forget that it's not! (Participant 6)

Participant 6 felt that chief officers of charities could come together but countered that not all would be completely honest and collaborative since they would often be competing for the same funds. It was reasoned that there was less funding available but even more organisations demanding those funds. In challenging financial times, it was believed that external communications with councils and funders was becoming more and more critical to charitable organisations like theirs.

Participant 7 explained that their stakeholder relationships had become even more vital now in the wake of challenges like Covid and the cost-of-living crisis. There was an increased need

for good communication between local organisations to understand the wider challenges in the community and with their users to build strong trusting relationships. It was also important to understand the services offered by other local organisations:

So, I think our relationships with stakeholders are going to be so much more important because the demand for services like that, whether it's energy, whether it's cost of living, whether it's mental health, things like that, it's going to soar, there's no ifs or buts about it. People are going to struggle. It's gonna be a tough few months, probably longer than that, you know, where people's lives are impacted in such a negative fashion. So, the stronger the relationships that we can have with our stakeholders the easier it becomes to ensure that we are getting the right level of support for the people in our communities. The only way we can do that is by having really strong relationships with the people, well I suppose for the community, because actually we need them to trust us enough to come to us. I definitely do believe that the relationships that we have will positively impact the way that we can react to a crisis when it is put to us (Participant 7).

Participant 7 later reflected on the need for clear communication with funders to make them understand ongoing community issues beyond just Covid and the Covid recovery.

Participant 9 expressed the view that the work of the charity sector was becoming even more vital and there was a need for all stakeholders to perform their part well. The situation he had experienced of poor governance and accountability was counter-productive and there was increased need to move away from personal objectives and towards the charity mission. Participant 9 also expressed some concerns over the competitive charity environment, concluding that funds would be directed to charities that were most convincing rather than most effective:

And talk about the competition over the same resources, you know, who does that serve? Are we supposed to get better quality outputs from these organisations? No. We're gonna get less good quality outputs from these organisations, we're gonna find its survival of the most duplicitous! That the ones that can, you know, give the best pitch, and tell the best story. But I really believe that governance and accountability, that topic that you're looking at, it's one of those ones which is just so essential. And so yeah, the priorities for the future has to be making that much higher quality and maybe changing things on a bigger basis (Participant 9).

Participant 10 expressed a strong belief that sharing information had become more important to them as an organisation, believing that society now demanded more transparency. It was thought that during times of austerity people wanted more detail on how money was being spent and that members would demand increased accountability when member subscriptions were raised:

Over the years it has become more important. You have to share more information. We're now living in a society where everybody wants transparency and so you have to share the information. And I think in terms of austerity, people want to know where the money is being used, what they're getting for their kids, what the benefits have been, especially now, and it's really difficult. If we can't get the fundraising coming in, we're gonna have to put the subs up. So, it's gonna have to be a bit more realistic, which then it's going to make us even more accountable to the parents because they want to know where the money has gone (Participant 10).

Participant 12 suggested that Covid has forced some positive change on organisations in the sector, where these changes may not have been seen as possible before:

I think Covid in particular made organisations in the sector do things differently and I think a lot of that has stayed and it's been really exciting! So, things that organisations were going oh our members would never do that, they did within 6 months because they wanted meetings to go ahead on Zoom. So, things change, but it's trying to convince trustees of the value of that, it can be tricky sometimes (Participant 12).

However, participant 12 had also witnessed the strain on organisations as people would go beyond their responsibilities and funding remit. In this environment of limited financial resource, it was felt that it would be extremely difficult to manage various stakeholder information needs. It was reasoned that the sector had changed on both the charity side and funder side. There was justification for being positive since funders had become more flexible post-Covid and indeed charities had become more creative in how they were delivering their services. However, there was a negative impact on finances and volunteer supply post-Covid and moving into a period of financial hardship:

I think that post-Covid the sector is very different from the pre-Covid sector, and I think funders have changed. I think funders have become a little bit more flexible than they were. I think organisations have become more creative about how they deliver their services and activities. Umm, I think volunteers have become less available to an extent because they're busier now and with the impending cost of living crisis, I think it's going to be very, very hard for services that are heavily reliant on volunteers. So, I think we're seeing a very different sector now than here was, you know, five years ago (Participant 12).

In conclusion, participant 12 felt quite strongly that organisations would now have to be cleverer in attracting and retaining members and finance; they would have to convince people to choose their charity over other things. To this end it was believed that organisations would

have to be more outward facing and more accountable and honest about their impact: the charity story would have to be told more effectively.

Participant 13 expressed frustration at the trend of increasing legislation and information demand; this was creating an ever-increasing administrative burden on organisations like theirs. It was felt that although intentions of government might be good, it was unhelpful to the extent that more information did not necessarily lead to benefit of more wisdom:

But it's also being wise with the time stewarding, with the time and effort that we have. So, you know, culturally we have increased exponentially the legislative demands. But I would say at the same time as the demand has went like that (raises hand quickly), wisdom and to know what to do with stuff has gone like that (drops hand quickly). There's cross-correlation, that basically government and local government, for all good intentions, put in all these rules, regulations, and everything, and actually it's because people just don't have the wisdom to do know what to do with what they have. And it needs to stop. We're just on this merry-go-round of creating more and more legislative, obligatory type stuff, and it's where's the wisdom? There's none.'
(Participant 13).

Accountability tools and approaches

Participation 1 pointed to the need for their organisation to examine or develop evaluation and learning frameworks to improve the quality of their information. In addition, it was commented that a more robust communication plan would enable the organisation to share and influence in a more effective and timely manner. Participant 1 reflected later on how effective online communications such as webinars could be in sharing information with beneficiaries and wider stakeholders.

Participant 2 explained her attempts to introduce an understanding of the context in which organisations operate, through building an ecomap of organisational environment with the organisation at the centre. It was explained that this conceptual thinking was lacking in all organisations beforehand. Participant 2 continued to explain that organisations should consider who surrounds them and that they should recognise layers of stakeholders:

I've not got any organisation where this has already been in place, so this has been a concept I have tried to introduce, and I've always been keen to get organisations to understand the context in which they operate. So, what does their ecomap look like and try to get organisations to build up their own ecomap so that when you look at their organisation at the centre, who do you surround yourself with and who are you accountable to? So that's the first layer of stakeholders, and who are your key stakeholders? (Participant 2).

Participant 2 later re-visited this thinking by adding that organisations must consider all possible relationships, those that are essential to exist both internal and external, people of interest, or people that may have potential conflict or work in the same space. There was a strong belief that organisations must then expand to understand not just local, but national and international contexts that would help them understand, assess, and manage their accountabilities. It was later opined that not all organisations would want or need an extensive ecomap, but it would be dangerous not to have some kind of picture of stakeholder environment. Organisations would be unaware of their dependencies and their impact on stakeholders and so be unable to plan or make contingency plans without these tools. Additional tools were also recommended by participant 2 to bolster understanding of charity context and accountabilities such as the RACI diagram to identify who's responsible, who's accountable, who must be consulted, and who must be informed. From experience this was a tool that was under-employed yet could be effective to instruct people of their position and

accountability for certain things. Participant 2 went on to explain that a communication plan had proven to be effective in some organisations and recommended this for other organisations in the sector. The plan only emerged where organisations had a continuous improvement mentality. The communication plan outlined different communications that would be undertaken with different stakeholders and helped where people asked about different aspects of the organisation:

We came up with an overall communication plan for the organisation and within that a communication policy. So, it actually defines here are the key ones and why they're key. Here's our internal stakeholders who we would define as internal stakeholders and then we had a communications map. So, for every person that was mentioned whether it be board, staff, volunteers, stakeholders, suppliers; we actually had a mark that said here's the types of communications we'll undertake. And we ticked off all those people who would get the different types of communications (Participant 2).

Participant 2 concluded by pointing to possible off-the-shelf solutions for those organisations that wanted to learn and devote some resources. 'Salesforce' for example was being used in some organisations and could be used to collate information on beneficiaries such as the referrals and help that was given. A key benefit was that this software solution could generate the information for reports that would be needed to communicate with funders.

Whilst reflecting on the accountability challenges facing small charities, participant 5 identified a need for proportionality. An example of creating a proportionate risk register was cited and a suggestion that charities had to make more use of the available support resource from organisations like the SCVO for such things:

Make sure that whatever you're doing is proportionate, just because the rules say for instance that you should have it, it's good governance to have a risk register. OK, that

doesn't mean to say you have a risk register that runs to pages and pages. You could have a risk register that just has five things on it, because that's what matters to your organisation. Your organisation is under, I don't know, £100,000, so make things proportionate. Don't make extra work for yourself. Use all the resources that are out there. Join SCVO. I don't work for SCVO, I'm not on commission, but if you're under £100,000 you can join SCVO for free. It's great and they've got lots of stuff that really help you in all aspects of running your organisation (Participant 5).

It was recommended that the board of trustees should sign up to both OSCR and SCVO websites and newsletters. The SCVO for example published newsletters highlighting issues that the board could then raise with the operating team. It was reasoned that the operating teams were often very busy, so identifying support resources should be within the role of the board.

Participant 6 explained that a recent innovation in the organisation has been the 'project plan' for internal communication between those who apply for funds and those that deliver the service. The plan sets out what the money must be used for and those delivering the service are involved in breaking this down into smaller outcomes and recording their detailed activities. The plan was used to keep volunteers on track with the outcomes they should be delivering and made clear why some activities should be pursued but others should not. The project plan had also proven useful for external use, in providing the details required to feed into further funding applications. The project plan had led to the organisation building in "roadblocks" within their funding applications, providing a level of transparency in explaining negative impacts on charity performance.

When pressed on the issue of finding more time to consider their accountability mechanisms, participant 7 showed some enthusiasm for collaboration with and amongst funders for streamlining their reporting requirements to the benefit of all:

100% yeah, and maybe that's where, you know, it's actually more about getting stakeholders, the larger stakeholders, involved in that as well, because actually do they realise that there's so much work has to go into each particular funder. They probably don't because they're only concerned with their own issues, understandably. You know, so maybe there needs to be a wider network there of people coming together to say what information are you likely to need and how can we streamline it and make it a more usable format for anybody that needs to kind of deal with it (Participant 7).

Participant 7 went further by adding that they could see the benefit in local organisations coming together to identify solutions to common funding and reporting challenges to ease the burden on their sector.

Participant 10 explained that robust financial book-keeping systems and detailed accounts meant that the foundation financial information would always be available to meet various stakeholder needs. Requests for financial information were being met easily enough in his role as treasurer for both internal and external purposes; he was satisfied that their accounting information could be adapted to meet multiple stakeholders needs:

A lot of them, whoever is going for funding, they were asking for grants, we have to fill in a few forms. One of the aspects will be, can you send us a copy of your accounts for last year? So, I copy the accounts, it gets attached to the form and away it goes. The scout association need to see your accounts, it's the same piece of information and they just pick out what they need. And if there's forms to fill in for OSCR, I just fill in the details for my accounts and then I send a copy of the accounts. So, it's all coming from the one place and that's enough to cover anything and everything. There's maybe occasionally, for applying for a grant, they want specifics: what are you going to buy with this, how much are they going to be? So, the information's always there and it

doesn't matter how far up the tree it has to go, it's usually the same information (Participant 10).

Participant 12 identified that there were CRM software solutions that could improve their data and information processes, but the labour time involved would be overwhelming. The downside was that organisations might be collecting a lot of data, but failing to do much with it:

So, I think very few organisations have yet to get their act together to move to Salesforce or RazorsEdge, or one of these, you know, customer relationship management systems, because they're expensive. And I mean it's certainly one of the things that my community fund is thinking about. But it's so labour intensive to set it all up. So, although the resource is free, Salesforce is free, the time it's gonna take to put the data in is pretty overwhelming at the moment. So, organisations collect all that sort of stuff, but I don't think they do anything very much with it (Participant 12).

Participant 12 later suggested that organisations, particularly small organisations, had to be more selective in the data or information they keep for themselves to avoid being overwhelmed. It was concluded that since they were all volunteers there was a severe time constraint and on reflection, they were being inefficient in the ways they handled data. There was a feeling that there must be easier ways to process data, but they were limited by the skills they had at hand. It was explained that management of data and information tended to be reactive rather than proactive or strategic. Overall, it was reasoned that they were doing enough to get by and that they were “good enough”, but to grow they would need to improve their data structure. In closing, participant 12 described the ‘lasting difference toolkit’, which could aid in the management and sustainability of small charities. It was her experience that smaller

organisations tended to be short sighted, for example in looking only toward the next grant, so had benefited from deployment of this more holistic and strategic tool:

I don't know if you've come across the lasting difference toolkit. There's a free toolkit that's been developed by some people who used to work for evaluation support Scotland, and they're looking at the sustainability of organisations. It's a free toolkit, it's called the lasting difference and it gives organisations five pillars to work with. Obviously one of which is income, but it's looking at how that organisation becomes more robust and becomes more fit for the future. And so, I use that quite a lot with smaller organisations because they tend to just think hand to mouth and when's the next grant (Participant 12).